

EVOLVE**2**CARE

**D1.1 – Roadmap on navigating
the complexities of enabling
innovative technologies in
transitional care**

WPI – EVOLVE2CARE experimentation space
framework

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List of Abbreviations

TG#1	Target Group 1: Innovators (researchers, SMEs, startups)
TG#2	Target Group 2: Accelerators / Investors
TG#3	Target Group 3: Living Labs
TG#4.1	Target Group 4.1: End-users (Care units, hospitals, practitioners)
TG#4.2	Target Group 2: End-users (individuals, patients)
TG#5	Target Group 2: Policy makers / Regulatory bodies
TG#6	Target Group 2: EU initiatives (i.e., EIT Health projects)
ROI	Return on Investment
EMA	European Medicines Agency
FDA	U.S. Food and Drug Administration
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act
MDR	Medical Device Regulation
EHRs	Electronic Health Records
RPM	Remote patient monitoring

R&D	Research and Development
RN	Registered Nurse
UC	Use Cases
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
M4	Month four of the Action
M19	Month nineteen of the Action

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Executive Summary

The Evolve2Care Project (N° 101158152) seeks to transform transitional care through innovation, collaboration, and evidence-based strategies. Deliverable D1.1, titled "Roadmap on Navigating the Complexities of Enabling Innovative Technologies in Transitional Care," provides a comprehensive framework to guide stakeholders in addressing the multifaceted challenges of integrating HealthTech solutions into transitional care settings.

Deliverable D1.1 is based on an extensive cross-analysis of literature, surveys, and interviews involving six target groups:

- **Innovators (TG#1):** Start-ups, SMEs, corporates, and researchers developing HealthTech solutions.
- **Accelerators/Investors (TG#2):** Entities supporting the growth and scaling of innovations.
- **Living Labs (TG#3):** Testbeds enabling real-world evaluation of technologies.
- **End-Users (TG#4.1 and TG#4.2):** Healthcare providers (care units, hospitals, practitioners) and individuals (patients and carers).
- **Policymakers (TG#5):** Regulatory bodies shaping legal and operational frameworks.
- **EU Initiatives (TG#6):** Broader European programmes promoting innovation and collaboration.

The main findings are categorised into five domains:

- **Legal and Regulatory:** Challenges in compliance, data protection, and cross-border integration of solutions.
- **Fiscal:** Financial constraints and the need for sustainable funding models.
- **Technical:** Issues related to interoperability, data security, and scalability.
- **Operational:** Barriers in workflow integration, change management, and stakeholder collaboration.
- **Economic and Social ("Other"):** Addressing inequities and fostering public trust in transitional care innovations.

This report integrates findings from literature reviews, surveys, and stakeholder interviews to provide a comprehensive analysis of transitional care innovation. By combining quantitative and qualitative data, the study identifies key drivers, barriers, and intersections influencing the development and adoption of innovative healthcare technologies. The insights highlight areas of alignment and divergence across

stakeholder groups, offering actionable recommendations for improving transitional care ecosystems.

The roadmap serves as a strategic guide, providing tailored recommendations for overcoming barriers and leveraging drivers:

Key Drivers of Innovation

1. Regulatory Support and Flexibility:

- A supportive and adaptive regulatory environment is essential for fostering innovation. Regulatory drivers include incentives for compliance, flexible frameworks, and policy alignment with emerging technologies.
- Stakeholders universally agree on the importance of streamlined regulations to facilitate technology adoption, especially in home care and AI-driven solutions.

2. Technological Advancements:

- Wearable devices, AI, and telemedicine are transforming transitional care. Innovations in predictive analytics and real-time monitoring enhance patient-centred care and efficiency.
- Digital tools such as remote monitoring and telehealth are pivotal in addressing accessibility challenges.

3. Collaboration and Stakeholder Engagement:

- Collaboration among healthcare providers, patients, researchers, and developers drives successful innovation.
- Co-designing solutions and leveraging feedback loops through pilot projects are critical for refining and scaling technologies.

Barriers to Innovation

1. Regulatory Challenges:

- The complexity and variability of regulatory frameworks hinder the rapid deployment of new technologies. Lengthy approval processes and fragmented regional regulations exacerbate delays.
- Innovators seek harmonised regulations to balance safety with the flexibility needed for innovation.

2. Funding and Financial Constraints:

- Financial challenges include securing sustainable funding and navigating reimbursement systems.

- Startups face difficulties in moving from prototypes to scalable solutions due to limited investment.

3. **Technology Integration and Interoperability:**

- Existing healthcare systems often struggle to integrate new technologies due to interoperability issues and the lack of standardisation.
- While innovators focus on technical alignment, end-users emphasise usability and accessibility.

Advancing transitional care innovation requires coordinated efforts to address legal and regulatory, fiscal, technical, operational and other (economic and social) challenges. By fostering collaboration, promoting user-centred designs, and ensuring sustainable funding, stakeholders can create an integrated system that benefits patients and healthcare providers. The findings underline the importance of aligning diverse perspectives to achieve impactful and scalable solutions for transitional care.

It is important to note that this deliverable highlights the interim findings. These findings refer to the initial exploration and identification of barriers and enablers.

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1. Introduction

Deliverable 1.1 - Roadmap on navigating the complexities of enabling innovative technologies in transitional care serves as a foundational step in the Evolve2Care project that aims at advancing innovation in transitional care through the identification and analysis of key drivers and barriers. Transitional care, which bridges the gap between healthcare settings and home-based recovery, faces unique challenges stemming from legal, regulatory, fiscal, technical, and operational complexities. These factors often impede the development and adoption of innovative technologies essential for improving patient outcomes.

This deliverable addresses these challenges by conducting a two-phase research effort. The first phase focuses on gathering insights through literature reviews, surveys, and stakeholder interviews, to map the landscape of enablers and obstacles to innovation. The second phase builds on this foundation, incorporating findings from the execution of real-world Use Cases that will take place within Living Labs, addressing the needs of Innovators, to deepen the analysis and validate the initial results. With the term Use Cases we refer to the selected mini-consortia of Living Labs – Innovators that will be selected through the project Open Calls.

By synthesising these insights into a comprehensive final report, Deliverable 1.1 aims to provide actionable knowledge and a strategic roadmap to support innovators, policymakers, and stakeholders in overcoming barriers and fostering a resilient, patient-centric healthcare system.

1.1. Project Overview

EVOLVE2CARE focuses on HealthTech experimentation practice to standardise and enhance the collaboration between Living Labs and innovators in the context of the Transitional Care sector. Challenges ranging from aging population to complexity of medical conditions and regulatory frameworks bring a growing recognition of the importance of experimentation practises. By subjecting innovations to real-world environments that involve end-users and stakeholders, EVOLVE2CARE provides innovators with access to services for testing and validating research and products.

The project focuses on three Use Cases (UC): i) Hospital discharge management; ii) Homecare monitoring solutions; and iii) Aging population & care transitions, engaging stakeholders across the whole value chain to examine complexities, barriers and enablers that regulatory framework poses to the development and commercialisation of healthcare innovations.

1.2. Purpose and scope of the deliverable

The purpose of Deliverable 1.1 - Roadmap on navigating the complexities of enabling innovative technologies in transitional care is to identify and analyse the key drivers and barriers affecting the development of innovative technologies in transitional care. This includes examining legal, regulatory, fiscal, technical, and operational challenges to provide a foundational understanding for enabling HealthTech innovation. The deliverable aims to guide stakeholders in navigating complexities and fostering an ecosystem supportive of innovation.

The scope of **Deliverable 1.1** encompasses:

1. Data Collection and Analysis:
 - Conducting literature reviews, surveys responses and stakeholder interviews.
 - Focusing on challenges and opportunities in transitional care innovation.
2. Phased Approach:
 - Phase 1 (Months 1–4): Initial exploration and identification of barriers and enablers.
 - Phase 2 (Months 19–24): In-depth analysis of findings from Use Case implementations in Living Labs.
3. The **output** of the deliverable:
 - Creation of an interim report (M4) summarising early findings.
 - Development of a detailed final report (M24) integrating insights from both phases, with contributions from all partners.
4. The **impact** of the deliverable:
 - Dissemination of the final report to stakeholders and the public, offering a roadmap for addressing challenges in the transitional care innovation landscape.

Deliverable D1.1 captures both the interim (M4) and final findings (M24), contributing to the project's overall objective of enabling HealthTech innovation. The final report (M24) will be developed by Sploro with contributions from all partners, and it will serve as a foundational guide for navigating the complexities of fostering innovation in transitional care. It will be disseminated to stakeholders and made publicly available to ensure broad impact.

1.3. Objectives of the Interim Phase

The interim phase of Deliverable 1.1 focuses on identifying the key drivers and barriers that influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care. The primary objectives include:

- **Identifying Drivers and Barriers:** Understanding the factors that enable or hinder HealthTech innovation, including regulatory, fiscal, technical, and operational challenges.
- **Laying the Foundation for Further Analysis:** Establishing a baseline of knowledge to guide the second phase of the task, which will incorporate insights from the implementation of Use Cases in Living Labs. This deliverable also lays the foundation for identifying the stakeholders needs and requirements (D1.2) and also refining the EVOLVE2CARE use cases (D1.3).

By achieving these objectives, the interim phase provides the groundwork for informed decision-making and strategic planning in subsequent phases of the project.

1.4. Scope of this Report

The interim report encompasses the activities conducted during the first four months of the project, focusing on three core areas of investigation:

- **Literature Review:** A comprehensive analysis of existing research to identify known challenges, gaps, and opportunities in transitional care innovation.
- **Surveys:** Targeted questionnaires distributed to key stakeholders and patients to gather diverse perspectives on barriers and enablers.
- **Stakeholder Interviews:** Qualitative insights from interviews with experts and practitioners, providing a deeper understanding of real-world challenges and opportunities.

This phase establishes an evidence-based understanding of the innovation landscape in transitional care, aligning all partners and stakeholders for effective collaboration in the project's next stages.

2. Methodology

This chapter outlines the methodological framework employed during the interim phase of the Evolve2Care project (please see Figure 1. Methodological Framework Employed). To address the complex and multidisciplinary nature of transitional care innovation, a multi-method approach was adopted, integrating both qualitative and quantitative techniques. This approach ensured a comprehensive understanding of the drivers, barriers, and opportunities influencing the development of HealthTech solutions in this sector.

The chapter details the research process, encompassing data collection, analytical techniques, and collaboration strategies. Each subchapter provides an in-depth overview of the methodologies applied to ensure rigor, relevance, and inclusivity in deriving insights.

Figure 1. Methodological Framework Employed

2.1. Target audiences

According to the Table 1. Target audiences’ classification, the pool of targeted audiences that form the EVOLVE2CARE stakeholders’ community has been primarily identified and comprises stakeholders that can impact and can be impacted by the project’s efforts and outcomes. Such audiences can be enlisted according to the following classification:

Table 1. Target audiences’ classification

Target audiences	Brief description, benefits and related impact
TG#1: Innovators	This group represents startups, SMEs corporates, and researchers focused on HealthTech solutions. They provide insights into the technological, operational, and market-oriented challenges and opportunities for innovation in the project’s case study field.

TG#2: Accelerators and Investors	Organisations and individuals providing funding and mentorship to innovative projects comprise this group. Their feedback can be valuable focusing on funding gaps, market dynamics, and investment priorities.
TG#3: Living Labs	This group consists of Living Labs certified by ENoLL, specifically active on Health and Wellbeing, who contribute perspectives on the practicalities of real-world experimentation, including resource allocation and stakeholder engagement.
TG#4.1: End-users (Care Units, Hospitals, Practitioners)	This group includes hospital administrators, clinicians, and healthcare professionals who provide valuable insights into the practical deployment and adoption of innovative solutions within healthcare systems.
TG#4.2: End-users (Individuals)	Patients and caregivers (informal or formal) who experience the challenges of transitional care firsthand are included in this group. They can contribute personal insights on usability, accessibility, and the real-world impact of innovation in the Transitional Care sector.
TG#5: Policymakers and Regulatory Bodies	This group entails policymakers and representatives from regulatory bodies whose perspectives on legislative and compliance challenges affecting HealthTech solutions are integral.
TG#6: EU Initiatives	This group is formed from representatives from EU-funded projects and initiatives, including EIT Health, that can share insights on leveraging existing networks and frameworks to foster innovation.

2.2. Literature Review Methodology

The literature review focused on analysing existing research, reports, and case studies relevant to innovation in transitional care. Sources were selected based on their relevance, credibility, and alignment with the project's objectives. Please refer to the list of selected inspected literature in Chapter 0List of all sources used for the literature review and data collection of the current deliverable.

The literature review adopted a systematic approach involving the following steps:

1. **Initial Pool Creation:** A diverse set articles, reports, and case studies were initially selected based on their relationship to transitional care. Sources included peer-reviewed journals, healthcare innovation reports, policy documents, industry white papers, and relevant news pieces. The reviewed literature included scholarly publishers (such as MDPI, IJIC, and ScienceDirect), projects promoted by the European Commission (such as VITALISE and TRANS-SENIOR), hospitals and nursing homes (such as the Veterans Health Administration), and European universities (such as the University of Groningen and the Catholic University of Leuven). The keywords used for the literature search were: **“healthcare”, “health-tech innovation”, “transitional care”, “drivers and barriers of transitional care”, “nursing home”, “hospital daycare”, “informal caregiver”, and “healthcare regulation”**. A list of the articles selected for this review is available in the Annex 9.1 List of all sources used for the literature review and data collection.
2. **First Round of Filtering:** Non-scientific literature was excluded to focus on high-quality, evidence-based sources directly aligned with the research objectives.
3. **Geographical and Contextual Refinement:** Literature was further refined to focus primarily on Europe, the region of Evolve2Care's activities. However, relevant and impactful insights from U.S.-based studies were retained.
4. **Categorisation of Drivers and Barriers:** Findings were organised into five domains based on their relevance to specific stakeholder groups (target groups).

Figure 2. Overview of the screening process for literature inclusion illustrates the literature screening process for this deliverable. The initial literature review included **30 sources** covering diverse perspectives on innovation in transitional care. After an initial screening, **non-scientific sources were excluded**, reducing the pool to **15 academic articles**. A final filtering step prioritised **European studies**, though some **U.S. papers were retained** due to their relevance. Ultimately, **10 articles** were selected for in-depth review.

Figure 2. Overview of the screening process for literature inclusion

2.3. Surveys Methodology

Surveys were designed to gather quantitative and qualitative data from a broad range of stakeholders involved in transitional care, ensuring diversity in insights and perspectives.

- **Design:** Surveys included a mix of closed-ended and open-ended questions to capture both measurable data and qualitative feedback.
- **Target Audience:** TG#1: Innovators, TG#2: Accelerators/Investors, TG#3: Living Labs, TG#4.1: End-users (care units, hospitals, practitioners), TG#4.2: End-users (individuals), TG#5: Policymakers / Regulatory Bodies, TG#6: EU Initiatives.
- **Distribution Channels:** Surveys were disseminated through email, project partner networks, and online platforms (e. g., LinkedIn, Facebook)
- **Summary of Response Demographics:** Respondents included representatives from researchers, SMEs, startups, corporates, practitioners, hospitals, living labs, technology providers, national government health departments and patient groups, providing a comprehensive snapshot of the ecosystem.
- **Data analysis** included statistical analysis of quantitative responses to identify trends and patterns, and thematic coding of qualitative answers to capture nuanced stakeholder perspectives.

2.4. Interviews Methodology

Interviews were conducted to gather qualitative insights from participants engaged in transitional care and healthcare innovation.

- **Profiles of Interviewees:** Participants included innovators, investors, patient representatives, end-users (healthcare professionals, practitioners, individuals) policymakers and EU Initiatives.
- **Key Topics and Structure of Discussions:** Interviews focused on exploring:
 - Perceived drivers and barriers to innovation.
 - Experiences with transitional care challenges.
 - Suggestions for improving the adoption of innovative solutions.

Qualitative data analysis was performed using thematic coding to extract key insights and identify patterns across stakeholder perspectives. This approach ensured a deep understanding of stakeholder experiences and expectations.

2.5. Collaboration and Alignment

Collaboration among project partners was a cornerstone of the methodology, ensuring consistency and alignment across research activities. Regular virtual meetings facilitated knowledge sharing, progress tracking, and harmonisation of efforts, fostering a unified approach to achieving project objectives.

- **Role of Partners:** Each partner contributed their expertise to specific aspects of data collection and analysis, fostering a multidisciplinary approach.
- **Regular Virtual Meetings:** Weekly regular scheduled meeting facilitated coordination, enabling partners to review progress, discuss challenges, and validate preliminary findings.
- **Communication tools** like Slack or Mail were used to facilitate quick exchanges and real-time updates, ensuring seamless collaboration among team members and stakeholders.

For the Surveys and Interviews phase, each partner was assigned a specific target group by the task leader. The assignment of target groups was based on the expertise of each partner. The details of the assignments are outlined in Table 2. Target Groups Partner Assignments:

Table 2. Target Groups Partner Assignments

Target Groups	Assigned Partner
TG#1: Innovators	Sploro
TG#2: Accelerators/Investors	AV
TG#3: Living Labs	ENoLL IVZW
TG#4.1: End-users (Care Units, Hospitals, Practitioners)	AUTH
TG#4.2: End-users (Individuals)	AUTH
TG#5: Policymakers/Regulatory Bodies	VILABS
TG#6: EU Initiatives	SPLORO

This collaborative and iterative process ensured that all activities remained aligned with the overarching goals of the Evolve2Care project and maximised the relevance and utility of the findings.

3. Insights from the Literature Review

The aim of this literature review was to gather significant, credible, and verified information about the key drivers and barriers influencing the development of innovative technologies in transitional care. This foundational research ensures the Evolve2Care project is informed by state-of-the-art knowledge, avoids duplication of existing findings, and maximises the project's impact within the healthcare innovation landscape.

3.1. Key drivers and barriers identified from existing research

The scope of the literature review was carefully defined to align with the objectives of the Evolve2Care project, focusing on:

- Transitional care as the central theme.
- Emphasis on European contexts while incorporating relevant insights from the United States to broaden perspectives.
- Drivers and barriers categorised into five domains: legal and regulatory, fiscal, technical, operational, and other (economic and social).

Refer to the list of selected inspected literature in Chapter 0 List of all sources used for the literature review and data collection of the current deliverable. After conducting an extensive literature review, a comprehensive list of **84 drivers** and **105 barriers** were identified, which have been summarised in the table below (Table 3. Drivers and Barriers Extracted from the Literature Review Phase). It is important to note that in this table, some of the drivers and barriers may appear the same for different key domains. This repetition reflects either their prevalence across multiple articles reviewed or their relevance to more than one of the key domains under consideration.

The drivers and barriers identified in the literature were divided into five primary categories:

- **Legal and Regulatory:** Frameworks that govern healthcare policies and transitions, as well as compliance challenges with policies and standards.
- **Fiscal:** Financial incentives or constraints impacting innovation.
- **Technical:** Adoption and integration of new technologies.
- **Operational:** Practical execution of transitional care processes.

- **Other (Economic and Social):** Broader societal and economic factors, such as public awareness, societal acceptance of innovations, cultural attitudes, workforce availability, and equity in access to care.

Important to note that the category **Other** (Economic and Social) was identified during the Literature Research phase.

Each driver and barrier category aligns with specific stakeholder groups, reflecting the unique challenges and priorities they face:

- **TG#1 Innovators:** Primarily affected by operational, technical, and regulatory challenges.
- **TG#2 Accelerators/Investors:** Concerned with technical feasibility and regulatory frameworks.
- **TG#3 Living Labs:** Focused on technical and regulatory hurdles during solution development.
- **TG#4 End Users:** Split into:
 - **TG#4.1: Care providers**
 - **TG#4.2: Individuals**Both are affected by operational and technical aspects of transitional care.
- **TG#5 Policymakers and Regulatory Bodies:** Impacted by legal, regulatory, and fiscal barriers.
- **TG#6 EU Initiatives:** Addressing high-level legal, regulatory, and fiscal challenges across regions.

Content analysis was used to identify recurring themes and knowledge gaps, providing a foundation for synthesizing insights from the literature.

Table 3. Drivers and Barriers Extracted from the Literature Review Phase

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
TG#1 Innovators: Drivers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplification of policies and regulations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase in funding • Market Incentives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of AI and personalised care • Telemedicine and digital health 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration with healthcare providers • Internal evaluation and improvement • Enhanced funding and investment • Involvement of healthcare professionals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging broad stakeholder networks • Public-private partnerships
TG#1 Innovators: Barriers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complexity of healthcare laws and regulations • Slow or unclear regulatory approval processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of funding • Excessive cost of development and implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of understanding/communication between caregiver categories • Presently unmet caregiver needs • Difficulty setting boundaries in family-health professionals • Need for multidata analysis • Lack of resources to implement new solutions • Data anonymity and security 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty in collaborating workflows • Difficulty in information exchange • Presently unmet caregiver needs • Lack of swiftness in decision making • Lack of resources to implement new solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A
TG#2 Accelerators/Investors: Drivers				

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geographical emplacement • Simplification of policies and regulations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geographical emplacement • Adequate funding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of new technologies (AI, telemedicine, digital health) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging broad stakeholder networks • Technical skills in informal caregivers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging broad stakeholder networks
TG#2 Accelerators/Investors: Barriers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unclear paths to regulatory approvals • Lack of real data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inexperience in sales/marketing • Financial instability • Excessive cost of development and implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slow technical development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor integration within healthcare ecosystem 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A
TG#3 Living Labs: Drivers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geographical emplacement • Simplification of policies and regulations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geographical emplacement • Adequate funding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous tailoring and tuning of care • Integration of innovative technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal evaluation and improvement • Patient and caregiver involvement • Multi-disciplinary teams professionals and patients • Intra-organisation transitions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A
TG#3 Living Labs: Barriers				

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data anonymity and security • Slow or unclear approval processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of funding • Lack of support from stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presently unmet caregiver needs • Difficulty setting boundaries in family-health professionals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Misleading, inaccurate, or incomplete information • Lack of involvement in organisations • Lack of resources to implement new solutions • Resistance to change to innovative technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A
TG#4.1 End-users (care units, hospitals, practitioners): Drivers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geographical emplacement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geographical emplacement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of innovative technologies (AI, telemedicine, digital health) • Improvement of communication after discharge • Caregiver's technical skills and training • Continuous tailoring and tuning care 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient engagement through good quality of life • Effective communication between patient-family and caregivers • Patient and family engagement • Training to caregivers • Internal evaluation and improvement • Intra-organisation transitions • Previous planification of transitional care services • Interdisciplinary teams 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging broad stakeholder networks
TG#4.1 End-users (care units, hospitals, practitioners): Barriers				

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data anonymity and security • Need to anticipate patient's needs to healthcare policies • Slow regulatory processes • Complicated compliance with healthcare laws 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incomplete or delayed information transfer • Lack of understanding/communication between caregiver categories • Temporal/informal caregivers cannot start care process themselves • Lack of knowledge/faith from patients • Lack of technical skills in informal caregivers • Lack of technical skills in formal caregivers • Presently unmet caregiver needs • Difficulty setting boundaries in family-health professionals • Unclear roles and responsibilities • Need for multidata analysis • Lack of resources to implement new solutions • Data anonymity and security 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of knowledge/training for staff • Lack of data interoperability • Ambiguity or absence of information from professionals to informal caregivers • Poor integration within organisation • Lack of understanding/communication between caregiver categories • Mistakes, inaccuracies or incomplete information when going from paper to electronic records • Lack of technical skills in informal caregivers • Lack of patient engagement • Lack of swiftness in decision making • Resistance to change from healthcare staff 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial challenges
TG#4.2 End-users (individuals): Drivers				

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geographical emplacement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geographical emplacement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fluid communication between caregiver categories • Caregiver's technical skills • Acute-level services at home to avoid hospital transition • Continuous tailoring and tuning care • Higher-quality care in nurse homes • Patient support and education • Technical capacity for telemedicine • Acceleration in research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient engagement through good quality of life • Positive feelings, after transitional care is satisfactory • Engaging broad stakeholder networks • Fluid communication between patient-family and caregivers • Patient and family engagement • Training given to informal caregivers • Inclusion in decision process • Careful planification of transitions • Additional support for assistance in the transition • Follow-up care 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging broad stakeholder networks
<p>TG#4.2 End-users (individuals): Barriers</p>				

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data anonymity and security • Need to anticipate patient's needs to healthcare policies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incomplete or delayed information transfer • Lack of understanding/communication between caregiver categories • Lack of knowledge/faith from patients • Lack of technical skills in informal caregivers • Presently unmet caregiver needs • Unclear roles and responsibilities • Lack of resources to implement new solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficult, incomplete or delayed information transfer • Difficult communication with healthcare providers • Lack of follow-up care after discharge • Lack of understanding/communication between caregiver categories • Lack of technical skills in informal caregivers • Lack of equipment or support at home • Lack of support offered from institutions • Lack of inclusion in decision process • Unclear roles and responsibilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial challenges or difficulty accessing needed resources

TG#5 Policymakers / Regulatory Bodies: Drivers

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geographical emplacement • Acceleration in research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government incentives or funding programmes • Public-private partnerships among healthcare providers, tech companies and governments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New standards for transitional care pathways 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging broad stakeholder networks • Internal evaluation and improvement • Collaboration between healthcare providers, payers, and tech companies • Public awareness and education • Seamless data and information exchange 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging broad stakeholder networks
<p>TG#5 Policymakers / Regulatory Bodies: Barriers</p>				

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data anonymity and security • Need to anticipate patient's needs to healthcare policies • Lack of unified standards • Lack of training from healthcare workforce to adopt new technologies • Unclear regulatory frameworks • Resistance to change from healthcare providers • Slow approval processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of funding and support to research • Lack of public-private collaboration with healthcare providers, tech companies, governments, and institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of understanding/communication between caregiver categories • Need for multidata analysis • Data anonymity and security 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor integration within organisation • Lack of swiftness in decision making • Lack of involvement in organisations • Lack of resources to implement • Fragmentation of healthcare systems • Resistance to change from healthcare providers • Lack of training from the healthcare workforce to adopt new technologies • Inequitable access to innovative technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A
TG#6 EU Initiatives: Drivers				

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geographical emplacement • Simplification of policies and regulations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geographical emplacement • Adequate funding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of innovative technologies (AI, telemedicine, digital health) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging broad stakeholder networks • Technical skills in informal caregivers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engaging broad stakeholder networks
TG#6 EU Initiatives: Barriers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unclear paths to regulatory approvals • Lack of real data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inexperience in sales/marketing • Financial instability • Excessive cost of development and implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slow technical development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor integration within healthcare ecosystem 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • N/A

3.2. Analysis of Modifiers extracted from Literature Research

This section will continue with a general overview of some key statistics extracted from the list of barriers and drivers. With the term 'modifiers,' we refer to the drivers and barriers. First, Figure 3. Distribution of Barriers and Drivers Across Key Domains shows the distribution of drivers and barriers according to the categories they belong to.

The clear difference in numbers between Operational and Technical modifiers compared to the other categories provides an evident conclusion: the centre of the reviewed literature has been the patient. This observation highlights the pressing need to enhance existing tools and develop new technologies. The aim is to improve the quality of healthcare services provided and, as a result, significantly enhance the patient's quality of life.

Figure 3. Distribution of Barriers and Drivers Across Key Domains

The numbers show that Operational and Technical modifiers account for the majority of barriers and drivers. This suggests that research has focused primarily on ensuring care transitions are well-executed and supported by the necessary technological tools.

- The **Operational** category, with the highest number of both barriers (38) and drivers (35), underscores the importance of seamless care execution. This reflects the growing emphasis on coordination, efficiency, and integration in transitional care.

- The **Technical** category, while slightly lower in numbers, also plays a pivotal role. Barriers like data security and drivers such as advancements in research are central to addressing the challenges of integrating innovative tools into transitional care.

Other domains such as Legal/Regulatory, Fiscal, and Economic/Social (categorised as "Other") are less represented numerically but remain critical. For instance:

- Legal and Regulatory barriers (21) highlight the complexities of compliance with healthcare standards and data protection laws.
- Fiscal barriers and drivers, though evenly matched (12 each), point to the delicate balance of resource availability and financial challenges faced by stakeholders.
- Economic and social barriers and drivers refers to emphasising the financial, societal, and cultural factors that influence the development, adoption, and success of innovations in transitional care. These factors are critical as they address the broader ecosystem within which healthcare innovations operate, beyond technical and regulatory considerations.

This distribution reinforces the interconnected nature of these modifiers and highlights the potential for significant advancements in transitional care by addressing the most critical Operational and Technical challenges. By focusing on these areas, stakeholders can bridge existing gaps and enhance the overall quality of patient care.

3.2. Analysis of Modifiers based on Target groups

Figure 4. Drivers and Barriers per Target Groups illustrates the distribution of modifiers across various target groups. The following analysis was conducted in descending order of the number of modifiers associated with each target group.

TG#4.1 (Practitioners) and TG#4.2 (Public and Individuals)

The highest number of detected modifiers were related to Practitioners (**TG#4.1**) and Public and Individuals (**TG#4.2**). This reinforced the centrality of patients and their care in the transition process, as highlighted earlier.

Both **TG#4.1** and **TG#4.2** were significantly affected by **Operational** and **Technical** modifiers, as these categories often overlapped. Examples of correlations between these target groups included drivers such as "Patient and family engagement (in the transition)," "Training for caregivers," and "Follow-up care," paired with barriers such as "Lack of patient engagement," "Lack of technical skills in informal caregivers," and "Lack of follow-up after discharge." While these pairs of modifiers seemed

contradictory at first, this duality reflected significant efforts that had already been made in these areas, with much work still required to improve their effectiveness.

TG#5 (Policy Makers and Regulatory Bodies)

TG#5 remained a key player in healthcare activities. All technologies, products, and innovations had to comply with legislation and regulations, thus emphasising the importance of TG#5 in shaping the landscape for innovation.

The involvement of policymakers and regulatory bodies was demonstrated through drivers such as “Public-private partnerships among healthcare providers, tech companies, and governments,” “Acceleration in research,” and “Integration of innovative technologies (AI, telemedicine, digital health),” all of which had a positive impact on TG#1 and TG#3 (and showed a smaller correlation with TG#6). Barriers related to this group included “Lack of funding and support for research,” “Lack of unified standards,” and “Unclear regulatory frameworks.” These barriers underscored the need for streamlined regulatory processes to facilitate the quicker entry of innovative technologies into the healthcare market.

TG#1 (Innovators)

This group was the most transversal alongside Living Labs in the sense that their work was influenced by all other target groups, as demonstrated in Table 3. Drivers and Barriers Extracted from the Literature Review Phase.

Drivers for this group included “Increase in funding” (connected to TG#2 and TG#6), “Collaboration with healthcare providers” (primarily TG#4.1, but also TG#3 and TG#4.2), and “Simplification of policies and regulations” (related to TG#5 and TG#6). These drivers were counterbalanced by barriers such as “Lack of funding” (linked to TG#2 and TG#6), “Difficulty in collaborating workflows” (relevant to TG#3 and TG#4.1), and “Complexity of healthcare laws and regulations” (related to TG#5 and TG#6). The interplay between these drivers and barriers highlighted the critical role of innovators in bridging gaps across the healthcare ecosystem.

TG#3 (Living Labs)

Living Labs could be viewed as a central hub connecting Innovators, Practitioners, and Individuals. The fewer modifiers found in TG#3 compared to other target groups may have been attributed to the relative novelty of the Living Lab concept in healthcare innovation, which had not yet been as widely explored in the literature.

Nonetheless, the drivers and barriers identified for Living Labs were strikingly similar to those of the other groups, including drivers like “Integration of innovative technologies (AI, telemedicine, digital health),” “Adequate funding,” and “Simplification

of policies and regulations” (related to TG#1), and “Internal evaluation and improvement” (linked to TG#4.1), as well as “Training informal caregivers” (associated with TG#4.1 and TG#4.2). Barriers included “Lack of funding” and “Lack of resources to implement” (linked to TG#1), along with “Slow or unclear approval processes” (related to TG#1, TG#4.2, and TG#5).

TG#6 (EU Initiatives) and TG#2 (Accelerators and Investors)

According to the literature, TG#6 and TG#2 were among the least represented groups, but their importance was undeniable. Developing new solutions required substantial resources, especially in the healthcare sector, where costs were particularly high.

This was reflected in the literature, which highlighted the significance of funding and public-private partnerships. Drivers such as “Adequate funding” and “Government incentives or funding programmes” underscored the critical role of external support. However, barriers such as “Lack of funding,” “Excessive cost of development and implementation,” and “Poor integration within the healthcare ecosystem” were also prevalent. These challenges further emphasised the need for targeted initiatives to address the financial and operational hurdles faced by these groups.

Figure 4. Drivers and Barriers per Target Groups

3.3. Conclusion of the Literature Phase

This distribution of modifiers across the various target groups revealed that TG#4.1 (Practitioners) and TG#4.2 (Public and Individuals) were most significantly impacted by operational and technical modifiers. Additionally, the data pointed to the necessity for further development in patient and caregiver engagement, improved training, and enhanced follow-up care. TG#1 (Innovators) and TG#3 (Living Labs) also played key roles

in driving innovation, although they faced substantial barriers related to funding, collaboration, and regulatory challenges.

From the sheer volume of identified drivers and barriers, a critical observation emerges: in this era of rapid technological advancement, where connectivity and innovation define modern life, the fact that barriers outnumber drivers suggests a significant insight. While technology continues to evolve and offer solutions, the persistent prevalence of barriers underscores the imperative to prioritise the human-centric approach in innovation and implementation.

This finding highlights a pressing need to focus on the individual—patients, caregivers, and healthcare professionals—rather than solely on technological solutions. Emphasising user-centricity will ensure that the innovations being developed are not only technically advanced but also accessible, equitable, and impactful in addressing the challenges faced in transitional care.

4. Survey Results

This section analyses the results of the surveys phase, focusing on the demographic composition of respondents and the emerging trends from their feedback. Key findings are organised around the six target groups, offering a nuanced understanding of the challenges and enablers perceived by Innovators, Accelerators, Living Labs, End-users, Policymakers, and EU Initiatives. These insights establish a baseline for further validation through interviews and Use Case activities.

4.1. Overview of participants

The survey engaged a diverse group of stakeholders critical to the innovation ecosystem in transitional care. It is important to note that each offering unique perspectives.

4.1.1. Respondents Target Groups Analysis

As can be observed from Table 4. Respondents Target Groups Coverage the survey targeted a range of key stakeholders across the innovation ecosystem in transitional care, categorised into six distinct Target Groups (TGs). The analysis of responses demonstrates the breadth of participation and highlights which stakeholder groups were most actively engaged during the survey phase.

- **TG#1: Innovators** accounted for the largest number of responses, with 36 participants contributing insights. This group includes researchers, startups, SMEs, and corporates, reflecting the central role of innovators in shaping the development of innovative solutions in transitional care. They provided insights into the technological, operational, and market-oriented challenges and opportunities for innovation.
- **TG#2: Accelerators/Investors** contributed 6 responses, offering perspectives on the financial and business strategies that influence innovation adoption. Their participation highlights the importance of investment-related viewpoints in overcoming fiscal barriers and driving innovation.
- **TG#3: Living Labs**, which are critical for testing and co-creating solutions, provided 8 responses. This level of engagement underscores their active role in fostering collaboration and practical implementation of innovative technologies.

The **End-users** category, which is divided into two subgroups, also showed notable participation:

- **TG#4.1: Care Units, Hospitals, and Practitioners**, representing professional end-users, contributed 11 responses. This reflects the critical role of healthcare providers in identifying operational and technical barriers to innovation.
- **TG#4.2: Individuals**, including patients, families, and informal caregivers, provided 10 responses. Their input ensures that the voice of individual end-users is adequately captured, particularly regarding user-centric challenges and enablers.
- **TG#5: Policymakers/Regulatory Bodies**, essential for addressing legal and regulatory barriers, accounted for 2 responses, reflecting limited but significant engagement from this group.
- Similarly, **TG#6: EU Initiatives**, representing collaborative projects and programmes at the European level, also contributed 2 responses, highlighting their role in driving innovation through policy alignment and funding mechanisms.

This distribution of responses highlights a robust representation from Innovators and End-users, while also integrating perspectives from Living Labs, financial stakeholders, policymakers, and EU initiatives. These insights provide a comprehensive foundation for understanding the drivers and barriers across the innovation ecosystem in transitional care.

Table 4. Respondents Target Groups Coverage

Target Group Number	Target Group Name	Number of answers received
TG#1	Innovators	36
TG#2	Accelerators/Investors	6
TG#3	Living Labs	8
TG#4.1	End-users (Care Units, Hospitals, Practitioners)	11
TG#4.2	End-users (Individuals)	10
TG#5	Policymakers/Regulatory Bodies	2
TG#6	EU initiatives	2

4.1.2. Respondents' Geographical Coverage Analysis

The geographical distribution of survey responses highlights the diversity and breadth of stakeholder engagement during the interim phase of this deliverable. This section provides an analysis of the responses received, categorised by country groups: EU Member States, Associated Countries, and Non-EU Countries.

As can be observed from Table 5. Survey Geographical Coverage respondents represented multiple EU countries, ensuring broad geographical coverage and reflecting varied healthcare systems and innovation environments.

- EU Member States:** A significant proportion of responses—45 in total—were received from 17 different EU Member States. This strong representation underscores the relevance and alignment of the Evolve2Care project with European stakeholders, who are directly impacted by the project's outcomes. The broad participation from EU Member States ensures that the findings are highly reflective of the regulatory, operational, and technical challenges within the region. It also strengthens the applicability of the insights to the project's implementation context, as Evolve2Care primarily focuses on healthcare systems within the EU.
- Associated Countries:** Responses from Associated Countries totalled 7, spanning 4 countries. While the number of responses was 9.33% of the total received responses, the inclusion of these countries is valuable, as they often share similar healthcare frameworks and innovation challenges with EU Member States. The perspectives provided by these stakeholders contribute to a more nuanced understanding of drivers and barriers in regions closely aligned with the EU's strategic priorities in healthcare innovation.
- Non-EU Countries:** A notable 23 responses were received from 12 non-EU countries. This representation highlights the global relevance of transitional care innovation and the interest of stakeholders beyond the EU in the Evolve2Care project's objectives. Insights from non-EU countries, particularly those with advanced healthcare systems or unique approaches to transitional care, provide valuable comparative data. They also offer perspectives that can inform potential scalability and adaptability of solutions developed within the Evolve2Care framework.

Table 5. Survey Geographical Coverage

Country	Number of answers received	Number of Countries
EU Member State	45	17
Associated Countries	7	4
Non-EU Countries	23	12

Implications of Geographical Coverage

The survey phase successfully captured diverse geographical insights, with responses from a total of 33 countries. The top five EU Member States with the highest number of

responses during the survey phase were Greece, Spain, France, Romania, and Bulgaria. This widespread participation enhances the robustness of the findings and ensures that the analysis accounts for a variety of healthcare systems, cultural contexts, and innovation ecosystems. The broad geographical representation aligns with the project's goals of fostering interoperability, inclusivity, and scalability of transitional care solutions.

The analysis also highlights potential areas for targeted follow-up in the final phase, particularly in regions or stakeholder groups that may require additional engagement to ensure comprehensive representation.

4.1.3. Respondents Age Coverage Analysis

As can be observed from Table 6. Age Groups Coverage, the survey responses spanned a diverse range of age groups, providing insights from various generational perspectives. A total of 22 responses were received from individuals **aged between 36 and 50 years**, representing the largest group of participants. This was closely followed by 21 responses from individuals **aged older than 50 years**, highlighting significant engagement from experienced professionals or stakeholders.

Participants aged **between 20 and 35 years** accounted for 19 responses, showcasing contributions from younger adults, often associated with innovative and emerging viewpoints. The **younger than 20 years** category had the lowest representation, with only 5 responses, reflecting limited participation from the youngest demographic. Additionally, 8 participants chose not to disclose their age.

This distribution demonstrates that the survey effectively captured input across a range of age groups, with a notable focus on middle-aged and senior participants, ensuring that the findings reflect a well-rounded demographic profile relevant to transitional care innovation.

Table 6. Age Groups Coverage

Age Groups	Number of answers received
Younger than 20	5
Between 20 and 35	19
Between 36 and 50	22
Older than 50	21
No answer	8

4.1.4. Respondents Gender Analysis

As stated in the Table 7. Respondents Gender, the survey captured responses from a diverse range of genders, contributing to an inclusive analysis of perspectives. Among the respondents, 40 identified as **woman**, making up the majority of the participants. This highlights significant engagement from women, who are often key stakeholders in healthcare and transitional care sectors.

22 respondents identified as **man**, representing the second-largest group and indicating balanced contributions from multiple gender perspectives. Additionally, 3 respondents identified as **non-binary**, emphasising the importance of including voices from underrepresented gender identities in the discussion.

A smaller group of respondents, 9 individuals, preferred not to disclose their gender, and 1 respondent identified as "**Other**," ensuring that even non-traditional gender categories were represented.

This distribution underscores the inclusivity of the survey design, which successfully engaged respondents across a range of gender identities. It provides a well-rounded dataset for understanding the diverse perspectives on the drivers and barriers influencing innovation in transitional care.

Table 7. Respondents Gender

Gender	Number of answers received
Woman	40
Man	22
Non-binary	3
Preferred not to say	2
Other	1
No answer	7

4.2. Emerging trends and key findings from responses

Each section of this chapter provides a comprehensive analysis of the drivers and barriers identified for each target group in part, based on the survey responses received during the survey phase of this deliverable. The findings are categorised into six domains: legal and regulatory, fiscal, technical, operational, and economic/social. Each domain highlights the factors influencing innovation in transitional care and clinical

pathways, providing valuable insights for addressing challenges and leveraging enablers.

4.2.1. Analysis of Drivers and Barriers for TG#1: Innovators

The identified drivers for TG#1: Innovators that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care, based on the survey results, are as follows:

1. Legal and Regulatory Drivers:

- **Regulatory Shifts:** The survey highlighted the importance of regulatory changes that support innovative care models, such as reimbursement for telehealth services and value-based care frameworks. Simplified regulatory pathways and faster approval timelines for healthcare technologies were identified as key enablers.
- **Incentives for Innovation:** Policies incentivising the adoption of performance-based reimbursement models, such as pay-for-performance are seen as pivotal for fostering innovation.

2. Fiscal Drivers:

- **Increased Funding:** Enhanced funding and investment in health tech startups are critical drivers, enabling innovators to develop and scale new solutions.
- **Market Incentives:** Market-driven incentives for early adoption of disruptive technologies encourage innovators to accelerate the development and deployment of solutions.

3. Technical Drivers:

- **Advances in Technology:** Key technical drivers include advancements in AI and machine learning, which enable predictive analytics and decision support tools. These technologies play a crucial role in improving care coordination and patient outcomes.
- **Integration of Digital Health Tools:** The integration of digital tools, such as remote monitoring systems and electronic health records (EHRs), enhances interoperability and operational efficiency.
- **Expansion of Infrastructure:** The growing use of digital health infrastructure, such as telehealth and remote patient monitoring tools, supports broader adoption of innovative care models.

4. Operational Drivers:

- **Collaboration:** Partnerships between technology innovators and healthcare providers, including hospitals and insurers, were frequently cited as a significant enabler. Such collaborations facilitate the co-development and implementation of innovative solutions.
- **Clinical Understanding:** Internal capabilities, such as a deep understanding of clinical workflows and healthcare challenges, are essential for innovators to develop solutions that align with real-world needs.
- **Access to Evidence:** The availability of clinical data and real-world evidence to validate and scale solutions was highlighted as critical to success.

5. Economic and Social Drivers

- **Personalised Care Demand:** The growing demand for personalised care models, including genomics and precision medicine, was noted as a key driver.
- **Integrated Care Models:** Shifts toward integrated care models that combine inpatient, outpatient, and home care provide opportunities for innovation.
- **Patient-Centric Solutions:** Enhanced patient demand for technology-driven and personalised care experiences underscores the need for innovative solutions.

The identified barriers for TG#1: Innovators that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care, based on the survey results are as follows:

1. Legal and Regulatory Barriers:

- **Regulatory Fragmentation:** Innovators face challenges navigating fragmented and unpredictable regulatory frameworks, particularly between different regions. Variations in requirements, such as those between the EU and the US, complicate compliance.
- **Reimbursement Uncertainty:** Uncertainty surrounding reimbursement models for innovative care pathways hinders widespread adoption.
- **Approval Challenges:** Barriers to obtaining FDA or CE mark approvals for new healthcare technologies slow down the development and deployment process.

2. Fiscal Barriers:

- **High Costs:** The high costs associated with the development, validation, and implementation of innovative solutions, especially clinical trials, were noted as significant barriers.
- **Limited Capital:** A lack of access to investors willing to take on pre-revenue risks in health tech presents a challenge for innovators, as highlighted in open responses.

3. Technical Barriers:

- **Integration Challenges:** Difficulty integrating new technologies with existing healthcare systems and workflows was the most frequently mentioned technical barrier.
- **Data Interoperability:** A lack of interoperability and standardised data formats for digital health tools was identified as a persistent challenge (as noted in open responses).

4. Operational Barriers:

- **Resistance to Adoption:** Resistance from healthcare providers and patients to adopt new technologies remains a significant obstacle.
- **Adoption Timelines:** Long timelines for technology adoption in healthcare settings delay the impact of innovations.
- **Collaboration Gaps:** Limited collaboration between technology innovators and traditional healthcare systems, such as hospitals and insurers, hinders progress.

5. Economic and Social Barriers

- **Economic Constraints:** Economic challenges, such as fewer resources to support healthcare innovation due to demographic shifts (e.g., aging populations) and economic downturns, were noted in open responses.
- **Lack of ROI Evidence:** A lack of clear evidence demonstrating the return on investment (ROI) for innovative solutions makes it difficult to secure stakeholder buy-in.

Based on the results obtained, the following recommendations can be concluded regarding the drivers and barriers that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care for Target Group 1:

1. Addressing Barriers:

- **Streamline Regulatory Processes:** Simplifying and harmonising regulatory frameworks across regions would help reduce compliance complexity and accelerate approval timelines.
- **Incentivise Funding:** Governments and private investors should create incentives to attract more capital to health tech innovations, particularly in early-stage development.
- **Secure Reimbursement Models:** Work with policymakers to establish transparent and sustainable reimbursement schemes, including value-based care models, to incentivise adoption.
- **Enhance Collaboration:** Encouraging stronger partnerships between innovators and traditional healthcare systems can bridge gaps in adoption and integration.

- **Reduce Development Costs:** Collaborate with governments and private entities to create funding programmes specifically targeting the high costs of clinical trials and validation.
- **Foster Adoption Through Engagement:** Educate healthcare providers and patients on the benefits of new technologies while building trust through demonstration pilots and user-friendly solutions.
- **Bridge Collaboration Gaps:** Create networks and shared platforms to connect innovators with hospitals, insurers, and other stakeholders for co-development and streamlined implementation.

2. Leveraging Drivers:

- **Capitalise on Technology Advances:** Innovators should prioritise leveraging AI, machine learning, and remote monitoring tools to meet growing demand for personalised and integrated care models.
- **Promote Value-Based Care Models:** Highlighting the benefits of value-based care frameworks can help drive policy changes and secure stakeholder support.
- **Focus on Patient Engagement:** Solutions that enhance patient engagement and demonstrate measurable improvements in outcomes will gain greater acceptance.
- **Expand Funding and Investment Opportunities:** Leverage increased availability of health tech funding to secure resources for scaling solutions. Engage with venture capital and grant providers focusing on disruptive healthcare technologies.
- **Collaborate for Success:** Build strategic partnerships with healthcare providers to ensure solutions are clinically relevant and operationally efficient.
- **Respond to Market Demands:** Develop patient-centric solutions that address the growing desire for personalised care and integrated service models, ensuring alignment with consumer expectations.
- **Promote ROI Evidence:** Use real-world data and clinical evidence to showcase the economic and operational benefits of innovations, fostering stakeholder confidence and support.

This analysis provides a detailed understanding of the enablers and challenges faced by innovators in transitional care and clinical pathways. By addressing the barriers and leveraging the drivers outlined above, stakeholders can foster an ecosystem that supports sustainable and impactful healthcare innovations.

4.2.2. Analysis of Drivers and Barriers for TG#2: Accelerators/Investors

The identified drivers for TG#2 Accelerators/Investors that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care, based on the survey results, are as follows:

1. Legal and Regulatory Drivers:

- **Regulatory Framework:** Investors recognise the importance of clear regulatory pathways that facilitate timely approvals, such as EMA/FDA approvals or GDPR, to support the adoption of new technologies.
- **Changes in Regulatory Frameworks:** Anticipation of regulatory changes that enable innovation is seen as a future driver for growth.
- **Reimbursement Models:** A strong alignment with regulatory requirements, including reimbursement models like value-based care or outcome-based reimbursement, is seen as critical to ensuring stakeholder buy-in.

2. Fiscal Drivers:

- **Resource Allocation:** Adequate funding and technical resources are considered essential enablers for scaling innovative solutions. Investors are looking for startups that can clearly demonstrate cost savings or improved efficiency.
- **Cost Savings and Efficiency:** Clear demonstration of cost savings or improved efficiency is a significant motivator for investment.
- **Value-Based Care Incentives:** Fee-for-service models combined with value-based care incentives are attractive business models, promoting fiscal sustainability.

3. Technical Drivers:

- **Data Privacy and Security:** Data privacy and security best practices are increasingly important, particularly as more digital health tools are integrated into care models.
- **Advanced Data Analysis Tools:** Platforms that improve multi-data analysis and decision-making are crucial technical drivers.
- **Technology Adaptability:** Startups that offer scalable, adaptable technologies with proven product-market fit are more attractive.
- **AI and Machine Learning:** Advances in AI and machine learning are seen as key technical drivers that can enable predictive analytics and real-time decision support.

4. Operational Drivers

- **Partnerships:** Strong partnerships between healthcare providers and tech startups are crucial for bridging gaps in adoption and integration.
- **Familiarity with Transitional Care:** Most stakeholders have some level of familiarity with transitional care innovations, reducing the barrier to adoption.
- **Home Healthcare and Patient-Centred Models:** Growth in home healthcare and telemedicine indicates a focus on operational efficiency and patient-centric approaches.

5. Economic and Social Drivers

- **Evidence of Patient Impact:** Strong clinical outcomes and patient impact are critical to investors, with a preference for startups that can demonstrate significant patient benefit.
- **Behavioural Health and Personalised Solutions:** Interest in innovations addressing mental health and personalised care solutions points to growing social awareness
- **Clear Communication and Collaboration:** The need for better collaboration between caregivers, patients, and professionals fosters trust and adoption.
- **Impact of AI and Digital Tools:** Expansion of AI, telemedicine, and personalised medicine reflects economic priorities for advancing healthcare efficiency and accessibility.

The identified barriers for TG#2 Accelerators/Investors that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care, based on the survey results, are as follows:

1. Legal and Regulatory Barriers:

- **Unclear Regulatory Pathways:** The ambiguity and complexity of regulatory requirements, such as delays in EMA/FDA approvals, pose significant risks for investors.
- **Reimbursement Challenges:** Uncertainty around reimbursement models for new technologies hinders adoption.
- **Alignment with Regulatory Standards:** Difficulty ensuring alignment with regulations like GDPR and HIPAA can hinder scaling and implementation.

2. Fiscal Barriers:

- **High Costs:** High costs associated with clinical trials, product development, and scaling pose a barrier to investment.
- **Limited Capital:** Insufficient funding options and lack of investor interest in pre-revenue risks in health tech are challenges.

- **Financial Instability:** Unsustainable burn rates or lack of stable funding poses risks to long-term innovation success.

3. Technical Barriers

- **Data Interoperability:** There is a need for standardised data formats and better interoperability for digital health tools.
- **Integration Challenges:** Difficulty integrating new technologies into existing healthcare workflows remains a key challenge.
- **Insufficient Clinical Validation:** Lack of robust real-world data or clinical validation undermines confidence in new solutions.
- **Weak Intellectual Property (IP):** Absence of strong IP or proprietary technology diminishes competitive advantage.

4. Operational Barriers

- **Resistance to Adoption:** Resistance from healthcare providers to adopt new technologies remains a major barrier.
- **Commercialisation Risks:** Investors are wary of unproven business models or unclear strategies for scaling and commercialisation.
- **Integration Challenges:** Difficulty in integrating new technologies into existing healthcare systems remains a significant challenge.
- **Inexperience in Transitional Care:** Limited familiarity or expertise in transitional care among stakeholders slows adoption.

5. Economic and Social Barriers

- **Market Acceptance:** A lack of understanding and acceptance of new technologies among healthcare professionals, caregivers, or patients can impact growth and adoption (5 responses).
- **Evidence of ROI:** A lack of clear evidence demonstrating the return on investment (ROI) for innovative solutions makes it difficult to secure stakeholder buy-in (2 responses).
- **Behavioural and Cultural Resistance:** Reluctance to shift from traditional care models creates resistance to innovation.

Based on the results obtained, we can conclude the following recommendations regarding the drivers and barriers that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care for Target Group 2:

1. Addressing Barriers

- **Harmonise Regulatory Processes:** Streamlining and harmonising regulatory frameworks across regions would help reduce compliance complexity and accelerate approval timelines.
- **Clarify Regulatory Pathways:** Advocate for streamlined regulatory processes and provide clear guidance on compliance with EMA/FDA approvals, GDPR, and HIPAA to reduce ambiguity and expedite approval timelines.
- **Enhance Collaboration:** Encouraging stronger partnerships between technology innovators and traditional healthcare systems can bridge gaps in adoption and integration.
- **Ensure Reimbursement Viability:** Collaborate with policymakers to establish transparent and predictable reimbursement models, including value-based care incentives, to improve adoption prospects for innovative technologies.
- **Market Incentives:** Governments and private investors should create incentives to attract more capital to health tech innovations, particularly in early-stage development.
- **Strengthen Data Interoperability:** Promote the adoption of standardised data formats and interoperability frameworks to facilitate integration with existing healthcare workflows.
- **Enhance Clinical Validation:** Invest in generating robust clinical and real-world data to validate innovations and increase confidence in their effectiveness.
- **Address Market Resistance:** Provide education and training programmes for healthcare providers and patients to reduce resistance and enhance the understanding of new technologies.

2. Leveraging Drivers:

- **Capitalise on Technology Advances:** Innovators should prioritise leveraging AI, machine learning, and remote monitoring tools to meet growing demand for personalised and integrated care models.
- **Promote Scalable, Adaptable Technologies:** Emphasise startups with scalable, adaptable solutions that address technical challenges and show product-market fit, ensuring long-term growth potential.
- **Leverage Regulatory and Reimbursement Alignments:** Capitalise on existing regulatory frameworks and the shift towards value-based care to attract investment and align business models with healthcare priorities.
- **Promote Value-Based Care Models:** Highlighting the benefits of value-based care frameworks can help drive policy changes and secure stakeholder support.
- **Focus on Patient Engagement:** Solutions that enhance patient engagement and demonstrate measurable improvements in outcomes will gain greater acceptance.

- **Focus on Proven Impact:** Highlight innovations with strong evidence of patient impact, clinical outcomes, and cost efficiency to demonstrate ROI and attract investor interest.
- **Strengthen Partnerships:** Facilitate collaborations between healthcare providers and startups to bridge gaps in adoption and integration, showcasing operational feasibility.
- **Address Social Drivers:** Support innovations that align with the growing demand for personalised care, mental health solutions, and telemedicine, ensuring alignment with societal and economic needs.

This analysis provides a detailed understanding of the enablers and challenges faced by TG#2 investors in transitional care and clinical pathways. By addressing the barriers and leveraging the drivers outlined above, stakeholders can foster an ecosystem that supports sustainable and impactful healthcare investments.

4.2.3. Analysis of Drivers and Barriers for TG#3: Living Labs

The identified drivers for TG#3: Living Labs that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care, based on the survey results, are as follows:

1. Legal and Regulatory Drivers:

- **Flexible Regulatory Frameworks:** A flexible regulatory environment is essential to support innovation without compromising safety. This flexibility helps Living Labs experiment with new technologies and care models in real-world settings.
- **Regulatory guidance and support:** Helping living labs navigate approval processes
- **Advocacy and policy influence:** Efforts to shape policies to support innovation
- **Strong Partnerships:** Living Labs facilitate collaborations between innovators, healthcare providers, and patients. These partnerships help navigate regulatory requirements and ensure that innovations are aligned with clinical standards and regulations.

2. Fiscal Drivers:

- **Clear Demand for Solutions:** There is a demand for solutions that address specific challenges in transitional care, such as reducing readmissions and improving patient outcomes. This demand can provide fiscal incentives for Living Labs to support innovation.

- **Financial incentives and grants:** Availability of funding for development and scaling
- 3. Technical Drivers:**
- **Access to Real-world Test Environments:** Living Labs provide access to real-world test environments, such as hospitals, rehab centres, and home care settings, which are crucial for validating solutions. These settings are essential for testing and refining new technologies and care models.
 - **Innovative digital solutions:** Development of AI-powered tools and telehealth it is a notable driver of the innovation for transitional care related to Living Labs group.
- 4. Operational Drivers:**
- **Patient and Caregiver Involvement:** Engaging patients and caregivers in the co-design and testing of solutions is a key operational driver. Their involvement ensures that solutions are practical and meet the real-world needs of patients during care transitions.
 - **Training programmes:** Preparing healthcare providers for new technologies.
 - **Strong partnerships:** Collaboration between Living Labs, providers, and patients
 - **Real-world test environments:** Validating solutions in hospitals, rehab centres, or home care settings.
- 5. Economic and Social Drivers:**
- **Demand for Data-driven Solutions:** There is an increasing need for data-driven solutions that can demonstrate value, such as cost savings and improved care efficiency. Living Labs can leverage this demand to support the development of innovative, data-informed care models.
 - **Patient-centred design:** Involving patients and caregivers in creating impactful solutions
 - **Multidisciplinary collaboration:** Involving diverse stakeholders for effective implementation

The identified barriers for TG#3 Living Labs that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care, based on the survey results, are as follows:

- 1. Legal and Regulatory Barriers:**
- **Regulatory Delays:** Regulatory barriers such as slow approval processes or unclear guidelines can hinder the adoption of new technologies. These delays can slow the innovation cycle within Living Labs.

- **Fragmented policies:** Regulatory misalignment across healthcare settings complicates integration
 - **Ethical concerns:** Challenges around data privacy, governance, and sharing in compliance with legal frameworks
- 2. Fiscal Barriers:**
- **Funding Challenges:** Living Labs struggle with securing adequate funding or investment to support the scaling of new solutions. This fiscal barrier can limit their ability to implement and validate new innovations.
 - **Unclear reimbursement pathways:** Insufficient or ambiguous structures for compensating innovative care models and technologies.
- 3. Technical Barriers:**
- **Resistance to Change:** Healthcare providers may resist adopting new models or technologies. This reluctance can be a significant hurdle, particularly in a Living Lab setting where integration with existing systems is crucial.
 - **Data interoperability:** Difficulty in integrating systems across different healthcare settings
 - **Limited technological readiness:** Challenges in adapting existing infrastructure to support new solutions
 - **Evidence gaps:** Difficulty in demonstrating measurable outcomes and effectiveness of new solutions
- 4. Operational Barriers:**
- **Fragmented Healthcare Systems:** The fragmented nature of healthcare systems can complicate the implementation and integration of new solutions across different care settings. This fragmentation can affect the continuity and scalability of innovations.
 - **Resistance to change:** Living Labs may be reluctant to adopt new models or technologies
 - **Workforce readiness:** Lack of training or skills among healthcare professionals to use new technologies.
 - **Patient engagement issues:** Patients or caregivers unwilling or unable to adopt new care models or technologies.
- 5. Economic and Social Barriers:**
- **Challenges in Demonstrating Effectiveness:** Innovators face difficulties in proving the effectiveness of new solutions. Demonstrating real-world value, such

as improved patient outcomes or reduced readmissions, is essential for gaining stakeholder buy-in and scaling innovations.

- **Limited market access:** Difficulty in expanding beyond Living Lab environments to broader healthcare networks.
- **Patient adoption challenges:** Barriers like digital literacy or resistance to new technologies.
- **Lack of stakeholder alignment:** Difficulty in engaging healthcare providers, payers, and other key stakeholders early in the process.

Based on the results obtained, we can conclude the following recommendations regarding the drivers and barriers that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care for Target Group 3:

Addressing Barriers:

- **Streamline Regulatory Approval:** Simplify regulatory processes to speed up the approval of new technologies, ensuring Living Labs can quickly implement and validate new innovations.
- **Enhance Funding Opportunities:** Develop targeted funding programmes that support Living Labs in testing and scaling innovations, including grants, government-backed initiatives, and private sector investment.
- **Strengthen Inter-Lab Collaborations:** Foster collaboration among Living Labs to share resources, knowledge, and best practices, which can help overcome individual barriers to innovation.
- **Overcome Resistance to Change:** To address healthcare providers' resistance to new models or technologies, Living Labs should focus on demonstrating the real-world effectiveness of innovations through data-driven evidence. Training programmes and tailored solutions that ease the integration of new technologies will also help in this regard.
- **Improve Data Interoperability:** Invest in standardising data formats and improving the interoperability of systems across different healthcare settings to facilitate seamless integration of new solutions.
- **Increase Stakeholder Alignment:** Early engagement of key stakeholders (healthcare providers, payers, patients, and caregivers) can help align goals and expectations, fostering smoother implementation of new technologies and care models.

Leveraging Drivers:

- **Prioritise Patient-Centred Design:** Focus on designing solutions that meet the specific needs of patients and caregivers during care transitions. Engage

stakeholders early in the development process to ensure solutions are practical and user-friendly.

- **Capitalise on Digital Health Innovations:** Utilise digital health technologies like telemedicine and AI-driven systems to enhance care continuity and interoperability across care settings.
- **Invest in Capacity Building:** Provide professional development programmes for healthcare providers within Living Labs to enhance their skills in adopting and using new technologies effectively.
- **Promote Strong Partnerships:** Leverage the existing strong partnerships between Living Labs, healthcare providers, and patients. These collaborations can help navigate regulatory challenges, accelerate innovation, and ensure solutions meet clinical needs and standards.
- **Utilise Real-World Test Environments:** Take full advantage of Living Labs' access to real-world test environments to validate and refine solutions. These environments provide valuable insights into the practical application and impact of new technologies and care models.
- **Focus on Data-Driven Solutions:** The increasing demand for data-driven solutions can be leveraged to develop technologies that demonstrate clear cost savings, improved patient outcomes, and efficiency. Living Labs should focus on providing evidence of effectiveness to drive adoption.
- **Engage Patients and Caregivers:** Continued patient and caregiver involvement in the co-design and testing of solutions ensures that innovations meet real-world needs and are more likely to be accepted by end-users.
- **Encourage Multidisciplinary Collaboration:** Foster collaboration among diverse stakeholders, including healthcare providers, technology developers, policymakers, and patients. This will enhance the impact of innovations and ensure that all perspectives are considered in the development and implementation process.

This analysis provides a comprehensive overview of the enablers and challenges faced by Living Labs in transitional care, specifically within the context of TG#3. Addressing these barriers and leveraging the identified drivers will help Living Labs create a supportive environment for sustainable healthcare innovation.

4.2.4. Analysis of Drivers and Barriers for TG#4.1: End-users (Practitioners)

The identified drivers for TG#4.1: End-users (Care Units, Hospitals, Practitioners) that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care, based on the survey results, are as follows:

1. Legal and Regulatory Drivers:

- **Regulatory alignment:** Compliance with privacy laws and insurance reimbursement policies, mentioned as a driver by respondents.
- **Support for data interoperability:** Regulations encouraging or mandating seamless data sharing across healthcare settings (noted as a critical need for data integration and interoperability by respondents).

2. Fiscal Drivers:

- **Financial support** or adequate reimbursement models were rated highly. This reflects the critical importance of financial sustainability to foster the adoption of transitional care innovations.
- **Cost-efficiency focus:** Innovations demonstrating potential cost savings (e.g., reduced readmissions, fewer complications) are more likely to be adopted, with evidence-based validation highlighted as necessary.
- **Institutional investments:** Budget allocation for integrating new technologies into clinical settings (e.g., EHR systems and digital health tools mentioned as widely used).

3. Technical Drivers:

- **Existing technical adoption:** Technological advancements such as digital health tools, remote monitoring, and telehealth are being actively used, with digital health tools (e.g., care coordination apps) and EHR systems being among the most frequently cited tools.
- **Data sharing and interoperability:** The ability to share patient data seamlessly across settings was highlighted as critical.
- **Proven impact of innovations:** Positive outcomes reported, such as quicker and more precise decision-making by rural practitioners using telehealth and online platforms.

4. Operational Drivers:

- **Positive Outcomes Drive Adoption:** Clear evidence of positive patient outcomes or improved care quality was identified as a key motivator for adopting innovations.

- **Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** Collaborative, interdisciplinary care teams drive innovation by improving operational efficiency.
- **Integration into workflows:** The ability of innovations to align with existing workflows, such as EHR integration, is vital.
- **Strong leadership support:** Leadership backing within healthcare organisations facilitates the adoption of innovative solutions.
- **Staff training and support:** Availability of adequate training for using new tools effectively is considered essential.

5. Economic and Social Drivers

- **Improved patient outcomes:** Patient engagement and willingness to participate in transitional care models were mentioned by 2 respondents. While the response rate was lower, the qualitative feedback highlights its potential role in driving care outcomes.
- **Fluid Communication:** Social determinants like ease of communication and patient education also play a role (e.g., patient satisfaction tied to faster diagnosis as mentioned in qualitative responses).
- **Patient engagement and rural impact:** Tools that empower patients, especially in underserved or rural areas, are seen as beneficial (e.g., telehealth solutions improving accessibility).

The identified barriers for TG#4.1: End-users (Care Units, Hospitals, Practitioners) that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care, based on the survey results, are as follows:

1. Legal and Regulatory Barriers:

- **Regulatory complexity and slow processes:** Difficulty navigating compliance with healthcare laws and regulations (e.g., privacy laws, slow approval processes).
- **Lack of clear guidelines for interoperability:** Absence of regulatory standards for seamless data sharing across systems, which is a significant challenge for respondents prioritising data integration.
- **Reimbursement uncertainties:** Lack of alignment between regulatory frameworks and reimbursement policies for new technologies (noted by 4 respondents as a barrier)

2. Fiscal Barriers:

- **Budgetary limitations:** High implementation costs hinder the adoption of innovations.
- **Unclear or insufficient reimbursement models:** A lack of financial sustainability for innovations due to unclear reimbursement policies

- **High implementation costs:** Initial expenses for adopting or scaling technologies, such as infrastructure, software, and training

3. Technical Barriers:

- **Integration challenges:** Difficulty integrating new technologies into existing workflows (e.g., EHR) was reported by respondents, making it one of the most pressing challenges.
- **Lack of interoperability:** Limited ability of new tools to share data seamlessly across different care settings, a major barrier for respondents who emphasised data sharing.
- **Privacy and security concerns:** Although not frequently mentioned, potential issues with patient data sharing can inhibit trust in adopting digital health tools.

4. Operational Barriers:

- **Resistance to change:** Resistance to change from healthcare staff is the most frequently cited challenge. This indicates a widespread reluctance to adopt new workflows or technologies.
- **Insufficient staff training:** Lack of training and support for healthcare professionals to effectively use innovative tools.
- **Increased workload during implementation:** Initial adoption of innovations often increases the workload, requiring additional time for training, troubleshooting, and workflow adjustments.

5. Economic and Social Barriers:

- **Patient reluctance:** Hesitation to adopt new technologies or processes was reported by respondents, indicating a challenge in achieving patient buy-in for technological innovations.
- **Collaboration gaps:** Limited communication and coordination among multidisciplinary teams reported by respondent as a limiting factor.
- **Lack of evidence-based validation:** Absence of sufficient proof that innovations improve outcomes or cost-efficiency, which affects stakeholder confidence (noted as a critical need by respondents).

Based on the results obtained, we can conclude the following recommendations regarding the drivers and barriers that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care for Target Group 4.1:

Addressing Barriers:

- **Training and Support:** Increase investment in training programmes to equip healthcare professionals with the skills needed to use new technologies effectively (addressing insufficient training and resistance to change).
- **Financial Models:** Develop clearer and more robust reimbursement models to support innovation sustainability and address financial barriers.
- **System Integration:** Prioritise integrating new technologies into existing workflows (e.g., seamless EHR integration) to reduce operational disruptions and enhance staff adoption rates.
- **Simplify Regulatory Processes:** Efforts should be made to streamline regulatory processes, particularly concerning privacy laws and approval procedures. Establishing clear guidelines for interoperability and data sharing will reduce complexity and facilitate smoother integration of new technologies.
- **Address Integration and Interoperability Challenges:** Investments should be made in standardising data formats and ensuring the seamless integration of new tools into existing systems, such as EHR platforms. This will improve the flow of information across healthcare settings and enhance operational efficiency.
- **Demonstrate Evidence-Based Impact:** Focus on generating and sharing robust evidence demonstrating that new technologies improve patient outcomes and deliver cost-efficiency. This evidence will increase stakeholder confidence and facilitate broader adoption.

Leveraging Drivers:

- **Demonstrating Positive Outcomes:** Showcase evidence-based success stories where innovations have improved patient outcomes or operational efficiency, motivating stakeholders to adopt similar solutions.
- **Fostering Collaboration:** Strengthen collaboration among interdisciplinary teams to promote knowledge sharing and streamline care coordination processes.
- **Patient Engagement:** Develop strategies and tools to better engage patients and their families in the care transition process.
- **Promote Financial Support and Reimbursement Models:** Leverage the strong fiscal drivers, such as clear demand for cost-saving solutions and financial support, by aligning new technologies with existing reimbursement models and demonstrating their potential to reduce costs and improve patient outcomes.
- **Build on Existing Technical Adoption:** Build on the already existing adoption of digital health tools, remote monitoring, and telehealth by expanding and enhancing these technologies. Demonstrating proven impacts, such as improved

decision-making and patient outcomes, will encourage further adoption and investment.

- **Foster Positive Patient Outcomes:** Leverage the operational driver of positive outcomes to drive further adoption. Highlighting the improvements in care quality and patient satisfaction will encourage healthcare providers to adopt and integrate innovative solutions.
- **Encourage Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** Capitalise on the operational benefit of interdisciplinary collaboration by promoting team-based approaches to healthcare. This will enhance the integration of new technologies and ensure they align with the needs of all stakeholders, including healthcare providers, patients, and caregivers.

The adoption of innovative solutions in transitional care by TG#4.1: End-users hinges on addressing barriers such as staff resistance, financial sustainability, and system interoperability while leveraging drivers like evidence-based outcomes, collaboration, and technological advancements. By focusing on training, integration, robust reimbursement frameworks, and seamless integration, the healthcare sector can overcome these challenges and improve transitional care processes.

4.2.5. Analysis of Drivers and Barriers for TG#4.2: End-users (Individuals)

The identified drivers for TG#4.2: End-users (Individuals - Patients) that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care, based on the survey results, are as follows:

1. Legal and Regulatory Drivers:

- **Mandated discharge planning requirements:** Regulations that require hospitals to provide discharge plans could drive innovation in creating tools and resources to enhance communication and coordination during care transitions.
- **Standards for patient rights and informed consent:** These foster the development of user-friendly educational resources for care plans, ensuring patients fully understand post-transition steps.

2. Fiscal Drivers:

- **Financial aid for patients:** The potential for financial assistance programmes is a key driver. Many respondents highlighted the need for improved access to financial aid, which could motivate policymakers and organisations to create such systems.

3. Technical Drivers:

- **Advancements in digital health platforms:** The availability of digital communication tools (mentioned in improvement suggestions) is a driver for improving communication and coordination during care transitions.
- **Interoperability between healthcare systems:** Seamless exchange of health data across providers enables better care coordination, a critical requirement from the survey results.
- **Remote monitoring technologies:** Tools like wearable devices or remote consultations can support health monitoring post-transition, reducing the burden on caregivers and enhancing safety.

4. Operational Drivers:

- **Integration of care coordination roles:** The survey identifies a gap in care coordination, emphasising the operational value of roles like discharge planners and case managers to streamline care transitions.
- **Simplified communication workflows:** Responses show a need for better communication, driving operational improvements in how care plans, medication instructions, and follow-ups are shared with patients.
- **Training for healthcare providers:** Innovations in operational training models for clinicians and caregivers to improve their ability to manage and support care transitions.

5. Economic and Social Drivers:

- **Growing caregiver burden:** The expressed need for family or caregiver support programmes highlights an opportunity to enhance social support systems, which could drive better outcomes in care transitions.
- **Shift towards patient-centred care:** The trend of involving patients and families in care decisions drives innovation in personalised care solutions and educational resources
- **Demand for equitable healthcare access:** Financial and logistical challenges faced by patients underscore the need for cost-effective, universally accessible solutions in transitional care

The identified barriers for TG#4.2: End-users (Individuals - Patients) that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care, based on the survey results, are as follows:

1. Legal and Regulatory Barriers:

- **Fragmented healthcare regulations:** Differences in laws and standards between healthcare providers (e.g., hospitals, primary care, long-term care) complicate care coordination and data sharing.
- **Data privacy concerns:** Stringent privacy laws (e.g., GDPR) make it challenging to implement interoperable systems that seamlessly share patient information across providers.
- **Lack of enforcement of discharge standards:** While discharge planning is often mandated, the inconsistent enforcement of these standards limits innovation and accountability in transitional care.

2. Fiscal Barriers:

- **High cost of services:** Financial challenges reported by patients indicate that many cannot afford necessary post-transition support, reducing the adoption of innovative solutions.
- **Limited funding for transitional care programmes:** A lack of dedicated budgets or reimbursement for transitional care initiatives hinders their implementation and scalability.
- **Insurance coverage gaps:** Many transitional care services, such as home care or caregiver support, may not be covered adequately by health insurance, creating financial barriers for patients.

3. Technical Barriers:

- **Lack of interoperable systems:** The inability of healthcare providers to share information efficiently limits the development of coordinated care solutions.
- **Insufficient digital infrastructure:** Patients often do not receive or have access to digital tools (e.g., apps, portals) that could improve communication and resource availability.
- **Low adoption of telehealth and remote monitoring:** Limited utilisation of technologies such as telehealth or wearable devices due to accessibility or awareness issues hinders innovation.

4. Operational Barriers:

- **Inadequate communication workflows:** Survey responses highlight gaps in communication during transitions, which are exacerbated by poorly coordinated workflows between providers.
- **Shortage of care coordinators:** A lack of professionals dedicated to discharge planning and post-transition support impedes effective care transitions.
- **Insufficient provider training:** Healthcare providers may lack the training or tools to ensure patients are adequately prepared for transitions.

- **Complexity of care transitions:** Transitions involving multiple providers or settings are often disorganised, creating additional challenges for patients and caregivers.
- 5. Economic and Social Barriers:**
- **Caregiver burden:** Emotional stress and a lack of caregiver support, as highlighted in the survey, reflect the economic and social difficulties families face during care transitions.
 - **Inequitable access to resources:** Patients with limited financial means or living in underserved areas face challenges in accessing necessary support services, including home care and transportation.
 - **Stigma and lack of awareness:** Patients may not seek available resources due to stigma, cultural barriers, or insufficient awareness of their options.
 - **Inadequate support for vulnerable populations:** Groups such as the elderly or those with chronic illnesses face additional hurdles due to a lack of tailored solutions.

Based on the results obtained, we can conclude the following recommendations regarding the drivers and barriers that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care for Target Group 4.2:

Addressing Barriers

- **Simplify Regulatory Standards:** Work towards standardising healthcare regulations across providers to facilitate smoother care coordination and data sharing. Efforts should also be made to ensure consistent enforcement of discharge planning mandates, holding providers accountable for delivering high-quality, coordinated care.
- **Improve Data Privacy and Interoperability:** Address data privacy concerns by establishing secure yet interoperable systems that allow seamless sharing of patient information across different care settings. This will improve care coordination and enable more effective transitional care.
- **Increase Financial Accessibility:** Develop financial aid programmes and strengthen insurance coverage for post-transition care services. Ensuring that insurance covers key transitional care needs, such as home care or caregiver support, will reduce financial barriers for patients.
- **Expand Digital Access and Infrastructure:** Invest in digital infrastructure and tools that enable patients to communicate effectively with care teams, manage health data, and receive remote monitoring support. These tools should be made accessible to all patients, particularly in underserved areas.

- **Enhance Communication Workflows:** Improve communication processes between healthcare providers to ensure that patients receive clear, timely information about their care transitions. This will address the operational challenge of poor coordination and inadequate information flow.
- **Enhanced Emotional Support:** Provide emotional support resources for patients and caregivers, addressing the significant stress reported.

Leveraging Drivers

- **User-friendly guides:** Build on existing positive experiences with discharge instructions and educational resources to create standardised, user-friendly **guides** for care transitions.
- **Investment in technology:** Develop digital tools to improve communication and follow-up care, leveraging technology as a key driver.
- **Enhanced education and training:** Promote social support programmes, such as family caregiver networks, to mitigate the burden on individual caregivers.
- **Targeted support for caregivers and vulnerable groups,** focusing on affordability, accessibility, and community resources.
- **Promote Financial Support Programmes:** Leverage the fiscal driver of financial aid by advocating for the creation of financial assistance programmes for patients, particularly those in vulnerable populations. This will enable wider adoption of innovative transitional care solutions and enhance care accessibility.
- **Utilise Digital Health Advancements:** Build on the technical drivers of digital health platforms and remote monitoring by expanding their use in transitional care. These technologies can improve communication, provide real-time health monitoring, and empower patients to take control of their health post-discharge.
- **Strengthen Care Coordination Roles:** Leverage the operational driver of care coordination by expanding the roles of discharge planners and case managers. These professionals play a crucial part in streamlining care transitions and ensuring patients receive adequate support throughout the process.
- **Enhance Patient-Centred Care:** Capitalise on the trend toward patient-centred care by developing personalised care solutions that involve patients and their families in decision-making. This approach will enhance patient engagement and improve the overall transition process.
- **Focus on Equitable Access to Care:** Leverage the growing demand for equitable healthcare access to create cost-effective, universally accessible transitional care solutions. This will ensure that patients from all socioeconomic backgrounds can access the care and resources they need to succeed in their transitions.

The analysis highlights significant barriers related to financial challenges, operational inefficiencies, and emotional stress during care transitions for individuals and their families. Recommendations focus on addressing these gaps through improved communication, financial assistance, and better access to home-based care services. Leveraging drivers such as existing social support systems and digital tools can create a more cohesive and supportive care transition experience for end-users.

4.2.6. Analysis of Drivers and Barriers for TG#5: Policymakers/Regulatory Bodies

The identified drivers for TG#5: Policymakers/Regulatory Bodies that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care, based on the survey results, are as follows:

1. Legal and Regulatory Drivers:

- **Establishment of National Standards for Transitional Care Pathways:** Highlighted as a critical enabler. Clear standards provide a foundation for consistent innovation and quality assurance across care settings.
- **Supportive Regulation for Innovation and Patient Safety:** Although not directly emphasised in the responses, creating an enabling regulatory environment is implicitly necessary for fostering innovation.

2. Fiscal Drivers:

- **Clear Reimbursement Policies:** Clear reimbursement policies for new technologies and care models, such as telehealth and remote monitoring, were identified as enablers to scaling innovations effectively.
- **Government Incentives and Funding Programmes:** Strongly supported as a driver. Financial backing enables pilot projects and scaling efforts, especially for novel care models and technologies.

3. Technical Drivers:

- **Data interoperability** enabling seamless information exchange across care settings was considered a significant driver to facilitate care coordination and innovation adoption.
- **Support for Emerging Technologies:** While not directly mentioned, integrating AI, digital health tools, and telehealth within existing frameworks remains a technical necessity.

4. Operational Drivers:

- **Alignment with Value-Based Care Models:** While only tangentially acknowledged, operational structures that emphasise outcomes over service volume can drive sustainable innovation.
- **Collaboration Between Stakeholders:** Although not directly highlighted, fostering partnerships between healthcare providers, payers, and technology developers can improve the operational integration of new solutions.

5. Economic and Social Drivers:

- **Public awareness and education** programmes to increase patient and caregiver engagement were emphasised as significant drivers for innovation in this context.
- **Equity and Access:** The importance of equitable access, was emphasised in responses, underpins successful adoption in diverse populations.

The identified barriers for TG#5: Policymakers/Regulatory Bodies that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care, based on the survey results, are as follows:

1. Legal and Regulatory Barriers:

- **Slow or cumbersome regulatory approval processes** were cited as a challenge, potentially delaying the adoption of new technologies and care models.
- **Lack of Unified Standards for Transitional Care Pathways:** Fragmentation of healthcare systems and the lack of unified standards for transitional care pathways were recognised as impediments to scaling innovations.
- **Resistance to change:** Traditional healthcare institutions (e.g., hospitals and insurance companies) may resist adopting new technologies, as noted by respondents.

2. Fiscal Barriers:

- **Unclear reimbursement models** or a lack of financial incentives for new care models and technologies were considered a critical barrier.
- **Limited Financial Incentives:** Government programmes and incentives are insufficiently aligned with the needs of innovators, further stalling progress.

3. Technical Barriers:

- **Data Interoperability Issues:** Identified as a primary technical challenge. Inconsistent or incompatible systems across healthcare settings prevent seamless data sharing and coordination.

4. Operational Barriers:

- **Resistance to change** from healthcare providers and traditional institutions was noted as a barrier to innovation adoption.
- **Fragmentation of Healthcare Systems:** Highlighted as a key challenge. Disjointed systems across hospitals, clinics, and home care providers hinder the integration of innovative care models.
- **Inadequate Training for Workforce:** It was noted that the lack of skilled healthcare professionals to adopt and use new technologies is a common operational issue.

5. Economic and Social Barriers

- **Resistance to Change from Providers:** Identified as a barrier. Healthcare providers may be reluctant to adopt new care models, especially when they perceive disruption to their workflows or lack confidence in the innovations.
- **Inequitable Access to Innovations:** Underserved populations or rural areas often face challenges accessing advanced technologies, creating disparities in care.

Based on the results obtained, we can conclude the following recommendations regarding the drivers and barriers that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care for Target Group 5:

Addressing Barriers

- **Streamline Regulatory Processes:** Reduce the complexity and delays in the regulatory approval processes for new technologies and care models. Simplifying these processes will help accelerate the adoption of innovations in transitional care.
- **Establish Unified Standards:** Work towards developing national standards for transitional care pathways to ensure consistency and coherence across healthcare settings. This would help standardise practices, reduce fragmentation, and facilitate the widespread adoption of innovative solutions.
- **Foster Change Management:** Address the resistance to change within traditional healthcare institutions by promoting awareness campaigns, providing evidence of the benefits of innovation, and offering incentives for early adoption.
- **Develop Clear Reimbursement Models:** Create transparent reimbursement policies that align with emerging care models and technologies, such as telehealth and remote monitoring. This will reduce financial uncertainty and promote broader adoption of innovations.

- **Improve Interoperability:** Invest in initiatives that promote seamless data sharing and improve interoperability between healthcare systems. This will address technical barriers and enhance care coordination across various settings.
- **Enhance Workforce Training:** Address the lack of skilled healthcare professionals by investing in training programmes to equip them with the necessary skills to adopt and use new technologies effectively.

Leveraging Drivers

- **Leverage National Standards for Care Pathways:** Use the establishment of national standards for transitional care pathways as a foundation to support the scaling of innovative technologies. Standardisation will provide a framework for ensuring quality care and consistency across the system.
- **Support Financial Incentives and Government Funding:** Utilise government incentives and funding programmes to support pilot projects and scale up the adoption of innovative technologies. Such funding will enable innovators to test and refine their solutions before broader implementation.
- **Promote Data Interoperability:** Strengthen the focus on data interoperability, ensuring that health data can flow seamlessly across various care settings. This is essential for enabling effective care coordination and fostering innovation in transitional care.
- **Align with Value-Based Care Models:** Foster the alignment of new technologies with value-based care models, which Emphasise outcomes and patient satisfaction. This will encourage the adoption of innovations that improve care quality and efficiency.
- **Increase Public Awareness:** Leverage public education programmes to engage patients and caregivers, helping them understand the value of innovative transitional care solutions. Raising awareness will encourage adoption and improve patient and caregiver participation in care transitions.
- **Focus on Equity and Access:** Promote equity by ensuring that all populations, including those in rural and underserved areas, have access to innovative technologies. This will support the widespread adoption of transitional care innovations and reduce disparities in healthcare access.

Policymakers and regulatory bodies in transitional care play a crucial role in enabling innovation. The primary drivers include government funding, national standards, and reimbursement policies. However, significant barriers such as regulatory delays, fragmentation of healthcare systems, and data interoperability challenges need to be addressed. Focused efforts on aligning regulatory frameworks with innovation needs

and streamlining reimbursement structures can accelerate the adoption and scaling of transitional care innovations.

4.2.7. Analysis of Drivers and Barriers for TG#6: EU Initiatives

The identified drivers for TG#6: EU Initiatives that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care, based on the survey results, are as follows:

1. Legal and Regulatory Drivers:

- **Alignment with regulatory requirements:** Alignment with data privacy and security standards (e.g., GDPR) was highlighted as a key driver. Additionally, efforts to align healthcare technologies with regulatory frameworks such as EMA or FDA approvals appear to play a significant enabling role. This compliance facilitates trust and adoption of solutions, particularly in cross-border contexts.
- **Changes in government policy:** Policies that encourage innovation in healthcare (e.g., streamlined regulatory pathways) are seen as a trend that could drive adoption.

2. Fiscal Drivers:

- **Investments in AI and machine learning technologies** indicate growing fiscal support for these innovative approaches. This focus on fiscal backing, particularly in technologies with predictive and analytical capabilities, suggests an optimistic financial outlook.
- **Adequate resources or funding:** While no direct responses indicated fiscal drivers, the mention of cost savings and evidence of efficiency improvements reflects an indirect fiscal enabler. EU funding opportunities and grants may further boost innovation.
- **Value-based care models:** A potential shift toward financial structures that reward outcomes over services can support innovative technologies in transitional care.

3. Technical Drivers:

- **Expansion of AI and machine learning:** Expansion of AI and machine learning for predictive analytics and decision-making, along with strong interest in remote patient monitoring (RPM), digital health platforms, and personalised care solutions, represents a key technical enabler.
- **Advanced multi-data analysis tools:** Advanced multi-data analysis platforms were also recognised for improving decision-making processes in healthcare.

- **Growth of telemedicine:** The adoption of telehealth and virtual care models demonstrates a technological shift that supports innovation.
- **Interoperability solutions:** Integration with existing systems is essential for enabling seamless data flow and care coordination.

4. Operational Drivers:

- **Strong collaboration and communication** between healthcare professionals and informal caregivers were identified as significant operational drivers. Aligning professional advice with family decisions enhances the feasibility and operationalisation of innovative solutions.
- **Training and upskilling:** Responses highlight the need for guided training programmes to enhance understanding and acceptance of new technologies among stakeholders.
- **Clinical validation and evidence generation:** Strong emphasis on clinical outcomes and real-world validation drives confidence in scaling innovations.
- **Scalability and adaptability:** Solutions that can be scaled across diverse care settings and adapted to different needs are prioritised.

5. Economic and Social Drivers:

- **Guided training programmes** and knowledge-building were emphasised as critical for fostering adoption. EU initiatives promoting such training create an environment where new technologies can be integrated more effectively into healthcare systems.
- **Patient and caregiver engagement:** Tools that improve decision-making and align professional healthcare advice with family input are key enablers.
- **Focus on home healthcare and personalised care:** Growth in patient-centred care models, including home healthcare solutions and precision medicine, aligns with societal needs for improved care accessibility and outcomes.
- **Awareness of mental health integration:** While not a direct focus in the survey, social drivers like addressing mental health gaps could become pivotal in holistic transitional care.

The identified barriers for TG#6: EU Initiatives that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care, based on the survey results, are as follows:

1. Legal and Regulatory Barriers:

- **Regulatory hurdles and compliance requirements:** Complex compliance requirements and unclear regulatory pathways were identified as significant

barriers, with delays in obtaining EMA or FDA approvals negatively impacting innovation timelines.

- **Delays in regulatory processes:** Moderate-to-strong impact of delays in obtaining regulatory approvals affects the development and adoption of new technologies.
- **Lack of standardisation:** Variability in care pathways and integration challenges within health systems hinder the implementation of innovative solutions.

2. Fiscal Barriers:

- **High costs of development:** High costs associated with clinical trials and product development were cited as major fiscal challenges.
- **Limited payer coverage or reimbursement:** Limited payer coverage and reimbursement options also hinder financial sustainability for scaling innovative solutions.
- **Financial instability:** The risk of unsustainable burn rates or underfunding impedes progress for startups in transitional care.

3. Technical Barriers:

- **Lack of standardisation** in care pathways and challenges with integrating new technologies into existing systems were seen as critical obstacles. Poor integration potential reduces the scalability and applicability of solutions.
- **Integration challenges:** Poor integration potential with existing healthcare systems and technologies slows the adoption of innovative solutions.
- **Insufficient clinical evidence:** Lack of robust real-world data and clinical validation undermines confidence in the effectiveness of new solutions.
- **Interoperability issues:** Limited compatibility between existing IT systems and new innovations complicates implementation and scalability.

4. Operational Barriers:

- **Resistance to change:** Reluctance to adopt new technologies, often due to unfamiliarity or lack of training, is a significant barrier.
- **Inadequate training programmes:** A lack of guided training for healthcare professionals, caregivers, and patients' limits understanding and acceptance of innovations.
- **Scalability challenges:** Unproven business models and difficulty in scaling solutions across diverse healthcare settings present operational risks.

5. Economic and Social Barriers:

- **Lack of engagement:** Limited engagement with end-users, including healthcare professionals, caregivers, and patients, weakens the adoption of solutions. Additionally, uncertainty around reimbursement policies creates economic instability.
- **Uncertainty in adoption:** Strong impact of the lack of understanding and acceptance of new technologies among healthcare professionals and caregivers impedes market growth.
- **Limited focus on underserved areas:** Behavioural health and chronic disease management innovations are not prioritised, leaving gaps in comprehensive transitional care.

Based on the results obtained, we can conclude the following recommendations regarding the drivers and barriers that have the potential to influence the development of innovative technologies in transitional care for Target Group 6:

Addressing Barriers

- **Financial incentives:** Introduce grant programmes or co-funding mechanisms to offset the high costs of clinical trials and development.
- **Streamline Regulatory Processes:** Simplify and accelerate regulatory approval processes (e.g., EMA, FDA) to reduce delays and enhance innovation timelines. Additionally, clear and unified regulatory pathways for transitional care technologies can encourage faster adoption and cross-border integration.
- **Standardise Care Pathways:** Promote standardisation across care pathways to enhance interoperability and integration of innovative solutions. Establishing common frameworks will ensure seamless adoption of technologies and reduce variability in care.
- **Support for Financial Sustainability:** Address the high costs of clinical trials and product development by offering financial incentives, subsidies, and access to EU funding programmes. Additionally, improve payer coverage and reimbursement models to ensure the financial sustainability of innovations.
- **Encourage Robust Clinical Validation:** Invest in programmes that support real-world data collection and clinical validation to build trust and confidence in new technologies. This will address the lack of clinical evidence and ensure solutions meet safety and efficacy standards.
- **Combat Resistance to Change:** Mitigate resistance by providing training programmes that enhance understanding of new technologies among healthcare professionals, caregivers, and patients. Emphasise the value and long-term benefits of adopting innovations in transitional care.

- **Focus on Underserved Areas:** Prioritise innovations that address gaps in transitional care, particularly in underserved areas, such as behavioural health and chronic disease management. This will ensure that solutions are accessible to all populations.
- **Promote standardisation:** Develop standardised frameworks for care pathways to facilitate easier integration and scalability of solutions.
- **Education and training:** Implement comprehensive training programmes for healthcare providers and caregivers to address resistance and knowledge gaps.

Leveraging Drivers

- **Expand data analytics:** Support the development of advanced data analysis tools to streamline decision-making and predictive care approaches.
- **Promote Alignment with Regulatory Requirements:** Leverage the alignment with regulatory standards (e.g., GDPR, EMA, FDA) to foster trust in new technologies and ensure smoother market entry. Regulatory compliance can also serve as a competitive advantage in the EU and beyond.
- **Invest in AI and Machine Learning:** Expand investments in AI, machine learning, and other advanced technologies to enhance predictive analytics, decision-making, and personalised care solutions. This technological shift is critical for scaling innovation in transitional care.
- **Utilise EU Funding Opportunities:** Capitalise on EU funding programmes and grants to support innovation, especially for projects focused on AI, machine learning, remote patient monitoring, and telemedicine. Such funding will help sustain startups and scale successful pilot projects.
- **Foster Strong Collaboration:** Encourage strong collaboration and communication between healthcare professionals, caregivers, and technology developers. This collaboration will facilitate the integration of new solutions and ensure they are tailored to the needs of end-users.
- **Support Value-Based Care Models:** Utilise the growing emphasis on value-based care to promote outcome-driven technologies in transitional care. Financial structures that reward value over volume will encourage the adoption of innovations that improve patient outcomes.
- **Enhance Public Engagement:** Leverage the focus on patient and caregiver engagement to ensure that innovations are user-friendly and address the real needs of those undergoing care transitions. This can help increase adoption and improve the overall effectiveness of transitional care solutions.

TG#6 highlights the EU's potential to foster innovation in transitional care and clinical pathways through a balanced approach of addressing barriers and leveraging drivers.

Investments in AI and machine learning, guided training, and better collaboration can propel advancements in the sector. However, overcoming fiscal, regulatory, and operational challenges requires targeted support and systematic policy interventions to maximise the impact of EU initiatives.

4.3. Summary of Key Modifiers based on Survey Results

In this section, the drivers and barriers explained in Chapter 4.2 of the current deliverable are summarised. Please refer to Table 8. Summary of Key Modifiers Based on Survey Results, for a better overview of the key drivers and barriers drafted from the Survey Phase.

Table 8. Summary of Key Modifiers Based on Survey Results

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
TG#1 Innovators: Drivers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reimbursement for telehealth services • Value-based care frameworks • Simplified regulatory pathways • Faster approval timelines for healthcare technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced funding and investment in health tech startups • Market Incentives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advancements in AI and machine learning • Integration of Digital Health Tools • Expansion of Infrastructure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partnerships between technology innovators and healthcare providers • Availability of clinical data and real-world evidence • Clinical Understanding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personalised care models • Integrated Care Models • Patient-Centric Solutions
TG#1 Innovators: Barriers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory Fragmentation • Reimbursement Uncertainty • Approval Challenges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Excessive cost of development and implementation • Limited Capital 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty integrating new technologies • Lack of resources to implement new solutions • Data Interoperability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance to adopting new technologies • Long timelines for technology adoption • Collaboration Gaps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic Constraints • Lack of ROI Evidence
TG#2 Accelerators/Investors: Drivers				

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory Framework • Reimbursement Models • Anticipation of regulatory changes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adequate funding • Cost Savings and Efficiency • Value-Based Care Incentives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical resources • Data Privacy and Security • Advances in AI and machine learning • Technology Adaptability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partnerships • Familiarity with Transitional Care • Home Healthcare and Patient-Centred Models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence of Patient Impact • Behavioural Health and Personalised Solutions • Clear Communication and Collaboration • Impact of AI and Digital Tools
TG#2 Accelerators/Investors: Barriers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unclear Regulatory Pathways • Reimbursement Challenges • Alignment with Regulatory Standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Excessive cost of development and implementation • Limited Capital • Financial Instability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Interoperability • Integration Challenges • Insufficient Clinical Validation • Weak Intellectual Property 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance to adopt new Technologies • Commercialisation Risks • Integration Challenges • Inexperience in Transitional Care 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market Acceptance • Behavioural and Cultural Resistance • Lack of ROI Evidence
TG#3 Living Labs: Drivers				

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexible Regulatory Frameworks • Regulatory guidance and support • Advocacy and policy influence • Strong Partnerships 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear Demand for Solutions • Financial incentives and grants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to Real-world Test Environments • Innovative digital solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient and Caregiver Involvement • Training programmes • Strong partnerships • Real-world test environments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demand for Data-driven Solutions • Patient-centred design • Multidisciplinary collaboration
TG#3 Living Labs: Barriers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory Delays • Fragmented policies • Ethical concerns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding Challenges • Unclear reimbursement pathways 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance to Change • Data interoperability • Limited technological readiness • Evidence gaps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance to change • Fragmented Healthcare Systems • Workforce readiness • Patient engagement issues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges in Demonstrating Effectiveness • Limited market access • Patient adoption challenges • Lack of stakeholder alignment
TG#4.1 End-users (care units, hospitals, practitioners): Drivers				

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory alignment • Support for data interoperability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial support • Cost-efficiency focus • Institutional investments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing technical adoption • Data sharing and interoperability • Proven impact of innovations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive Outcomes Drive Adoption • Interdisciplinary Collaboration • Integration into workflows • Strong leadership support • Staff training and support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved patient outcomes • Fluid Communication • Patient engagement and rural impact
TG#4.1 End-users (care units, hospitals, practitioners): Barriers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory complexity and slow processes • Lack of clear guidelines for interoperability • Reimbursement uncertainties 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Budgetary limitations • Unclear or insufficient reimbursement models • High implementation costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration challenges • Lack of interoperability • Privacy and security concerns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance to change • Insufficient staff training • Increased workload during implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient reluctance • Collaboration gaps • Lack of evidence-based validation
TG#4.2 End-users (individuals): Drivers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mandated discharge planning requirements • Standards for patient rights and informed consent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial aid for patients 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advancements in digital health platforms • Interoperability between healthcare systems • Remote monitoring technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of care coordination roles • Simplified communication workflows • Training for healthcare providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Growing caregiver burden • Shift towards patient-centred care • Demand for equitable healthcare access

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
TG#4.2 End-users (individuals): Barriers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fragmented healthcare regulations • Data privacy concerns • Lack of enforcement of discharge standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High cost of services • Limited funding for transitional care programmes • Insurance coverage gaps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of interoperable systems • Insufficient digital infrastructure • Low adoption of telehealth and remote monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inadequate communication workflows • Shortage of care coordinators • Insufficient provider training • Complexity of care transitions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Caregiver burden • Inequitable access to resources • Stigma and lack of awareness • Inadequate support for vulnerable populations
TG#5 Policymakers / Regulatory Bodies: Drivers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of National Standards for Transitional Care Pathways • Supportive Regulation for Innovation and Patient Safety 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear Reimbursement Policies • Government Incentives and Funding Programmes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data interoperability • Support for Emerging Technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alignment with Value-Based Care Models • Collaboration Between Stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public awareness and education • Equity and Access
TG#5 Policymakers / Regulatory Bodies: Barriers				

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slow or cumbersome regulatory approval processes • Lack of Unified Standards for Transitional Care Pathways • Resistance to change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unclear reimbursement models • Limited Financial Incentives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Interoperability Issues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance to change • Fragmentation of Healthcare Systems • Inadequate Training for Workforce • Resistance to Change from Providers • Inequitable Access to Innovations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance to Change • Inequitable Access to Innovations
TG#6 EU Initiatives: Drivers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alignment with regulatory requirements • Changes in government policy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investments in AI and machine learning technologies • Adequate resources or funding • Value-based care models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expansion of AI and machine learning • Advanced multi-data analysis tools • Growth of telemedicine • Interoperability solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong collaboration and communication • Training and upskilling • Clinical validation and evidence generation • Scalability and adaptability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guided training programmes • Patient and caregiver engagement • Focus on home healthcare and personalised care • Awareness of mental health integration
TG#6 EU Initiatives: Barriers				

D1.1 - Roadmap on navigating the complexities of enabling innovative technologies in transitional care

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory hurdles and compliance requirements • Delays in regulatory processes • Lack of standardisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High costs of development • Limited payer coverage or reimbursement • Financial instability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of standardisation • Integration challenges • Insufficient clinical evidence • Interoperability issues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance to change • Inadequate training programmes • Scalability challenges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of engagement • Uncertainty in adoption • Limited focus on underserved areas

4.4. Cross-Analysis drafted from the Surveys Responses

The cross-analysis of the target groups (Innovators, Accelerators/Investors, Living Labs, End-users, Policymakers/Regulatory Bodies, and EU Initiatives) reveals key patterns in both drivers and barriers to innovation in transitional care solutions. The overarching themes emphasise the need for regulatory harmonisation, financial support, technological interoperability, operational collaboration, and societal shifts toward patient-centred care.

1. Legal and Regulatory

Across all target groups, the need for simplified and clear regulatory frameworks stands out as a fundamental driver. **Innovators** and **Accelerators/Investors** highlight the importance of reimbursement models and faster regulatory approvals, crucial for fostering innovation. Similarly, **Living Labs** and **Policymakers/Regulatory Bodies** emphasise flexible regulatory guidance and national standards to support innovation and ensure patient safety. However, **regulatory fragmentation** remains a persistent barrier, with **Innovators** and **End-users** (care units and individuals) facing slow approval processes, unclear guidelines, and challenges related to data privacy and compliance. The harmonisation of **regulatory standards** and **faster approval processes** would provide a **solid foundation** for **all groups**.

2. Fiscal Drivers and Barriers

Financial support is a crucial enabler for innovation in transitional care. **Accelerators/Investors** and **EU Initiatives** emphasise government incentives, funding programmes, and investments in emerging technologies like AI and machine learning. Additionally, **Living Labs** and **End-users** benefit from grants and institutional investments. However, excessive development and implementation costs, coupled with insufficient reimbursement models, are barriers that hinder progress. Groups such as **Innovators** and **Accelerators/Investors** face high costs, limited capital, and financial instability, which impede the scaling of innovative solutions. Addressing funding challenges, clarifying reimbursement pathways, and enhancing market incentives are key steps to overcome fiscal barriers.

3. Technological Drivers and Barriers

The advancement of digital health technologies, particularly AI, interoperability solutions, and infrastructure, is a common driver across target groups. **Innovators** and

Accelerators/Investors emphasise the promise of new technologies to improve care delivery and patient outcomes. **Living Labs** benefit from access to real-world test environments, which facilitate the practical application of innovative digital solutions. However, technical barriers such as **data interoperability, integration challenges, and evidence gaps** remain widespread. Both **Accelerators/Investors** and **Living Labs** are particularly impacted by insufficient clinical validation and interoperability issues, which hinder the successful implementation of new technologies. Overcoming these challenges will require a concerted effort to standardise data formats, improve interoperability, and gather robust clinical evidence to support the adoption of new solutions.

4. Operational Drivers and Barriers

Operational drivers like **collaboration** and **partnerships** between healthcare providers and technology innovators are highlighted by multiple groups, particularly **Innovators, Living Labs, and End-users**. Strong partnerships and the availability of clinical data and real-world evidence are key enablers for operational success. Additionally, **training programmes** and **workforce readiness** are seen as essential for ensuring successful implementation and adoption. However, operational barriers such as **resistance to change, collaboration gaps, and insufficient staff training** are common across groups. The **End-users** (care units) particularly face integration challenges, while **Living Labs** and **Policymakers** struggle with workforce readiness and fragmented healthcare systems. Tackling these operational barriers requires fostering an environment of collaboration, providing robust training programmes, and aligning stakeholder goals to ensure smooth implementation.

5. Other (Economic and Social) Drivers and Barriers

Social drivers, including the shift towards **patient-centred care** and **multidisciplinary collaboration**, are highlighted as significant enablers of innovation. **Living Labs** and **EU Initiatives** particularly emphasise the importance of caregiver involvement, patient-centred design, and addressing caregiver burdens. On the other hand, **economic constraints** and **lack of ROI** evidence are major barriers, especially for **Innovators** and **Accelerators/Investors**, who face challenges in demonstrating the financial viability of new technologies. Cultural and behavioural resistance, as well as **inequitable access to resources**, particularly impact **End-users** (individuals). Addressing these barriers will require a focus on demonstrating the economic value of innovations, ensuring equitable access, and fostering societal acceptance of new care models.

4.5. Conclusion of Surveys Responses

The analysis of survey responses across the target groups reveals a consistent theme: innovation in transitional care requires the alignment of regulatory frameworks, financial support, technological advancements, operational readiness, and social shifts. Key barriers include regulatory fragmentation, high development costs, data interoperability issues, resistance to change, and challenges in demonstrating ROI.

To overcome these barriers and leverage the identified drivers, it is essential to:

- **Streamline regulatory processes** to facilitate faster approvals and clearer guidelines.
- **Enhance funding mechanisms** and clarify reimbursement models to address fiscal barriers.
- **Promote interoperability standards** and provide clinical evidence to support the adoption of new technologies.
- **Foster collaboration and provide training to** ensure workforce readiness and smooth operational integration.
- **Address social and economic barriers** by focusing on patient-centred care and demonstrating the value of innovations to various stakeholders.

By addressing these key areas, stakeholders can collectively drive the adoption of innovative solutions that improve transitional care, benefiting both patients and healthcare systems alike.

The survey results provide a comprehensive overview of the drivers, barriers, and opportunities shaping the transitional care innovation landscape. These insights will guide the design and implementation of the next phases of the Evolve2Care project, particularly in aligning Use Cases with stakeholder needs and ensuring the scalability and impact of proposed solutions. This foundational knowledge sets the stage for further exploration and validation through stakeholder interviews and Living Lab activities.

5. Insights from Stakeholder Interviews

The stakeholder interviews provided qualitative insights into the complexities of transitional care innovation. This section summarises the common themes, challenges, and enablers highlighted by interviewees. Their perspectives offer a deeper understanding of real-world barriers and opportunities, complementing the quantitative data from the survey and adding richness to the findings.

5.1. Overview of interviewees

The interview phase engaged a diverse group of stakeholders critical to the innovation ecosystem in transitional care. Interviewees were categorised based on the six target groups (TGs), each offering unique perspectives.

The analysis focuses on the 32 interviews conducted, representing 43% of the total responses received during the Surveys Phase.

5.1.1. Interviewees Target Groups Analysis

As can be observed from Table 9. Interviews Performed this phase targeted a range of key stakeholders across the innovation ecosystem in transitional care, based on the six distinct Target Groups (TGs). The analysis of responses demonstrates the breadth of participation and highlights which stakeholder groups were most actively engaged during the interview phase.

Table 9. Interviews Performed

Target Group Number	Target Group Name	Number of Interviews
TG#1	Innovators	8
TG#2	Accelerators/Investors	2
TG#3	Living Labs	4
TG#4.1	End-users (Care Units, Hospitals, Practitioners)	7
TG#4.2	End-users (Individuals)	7
TG#5	Policymakers/Regulatory Bodies	2
TG#6	EU initiatives	2

5.1.2. Interviewees' Geographical Coverage Analysis

The geographical coverage of the interviews conducted for the Evolve2Care project highlights the diversity of perspectives from stakeholders across various regions. According to Table 10. Interviews Geographical Coverage a total of 32 interviews were

performed, spanning EU Member States, Associated Countries, and Non-EU Countries. Below is the detailed analysis:

The majority of interviews were conducted within EU Member States, reflecting the project’s focus on addressing transitional care challenges within the European Union. This group provided valuable insights into regional variations in healthcare policies, regulatory frameworks, and innovation adoption rates. The high representation ensures that the findings are aligned with the broader EU context.

Stakeholders from Associated Countries contributed perspectives on how transitional care innovations can be adapted and integrated into healthcare systems outside the EU. Their feedback highlighted opportunities for collaboration and the importance of aligning standards and practices with EU initiatives to ensure interoperability.

The inclusion of a non-EU Countries provided a global perspective on transitional care innovation. This interview offered insights into unique challenges and opportunities outside the European regulatory and operational landscape, emphasizing the potential for knowledge exchange and international collaboration.

Table 10. Interviews Geographical Coverage

Country	Number of interviews performed	Number of Countries
EU Member State	27	5
Associated Countries	4	4
Non-EU Countries	1	1

The geographical analysis underscores the project’s comprehensive approach to capturing diverse perspectives from a range of regions. By engaging stakeholders from EU Member States, Associated Countries, and a Non-EU Country, the project ensures that its recommendations will be relevant, inclusive, and adaptable to various contexts within and beyond Europe.

5.1.3. Interviewees Age Coverage Analysis

As can be observed from Table 11. Interviewees Age Groups, the age coverage of the interviewees highlights a balanced representation of perspectives across different age groups, ensuring that the findings reflect a wide range of experiences and priorities. Below is the detailed analysis:

For **younger than 20** years category no responses were recorded in this age group, indicating a lack of representation from very young individuals. This could reflect the

limited involvement of this demographic in transitional care innovation or decision-making processes.

The age group **between 20 and 35** years, represented 31.25% of the total interviews performed. The majority of the interviews were conducted with early-career professionals and young innovators. Their insights focused on the adoption of new technologies, the importance of training opportunities, and the need for mentorship to navigate the complexities of transitional care innovation.

The category **between 36 and 50** years, represented 34.38% of the total interviews performed. Representing mid-career professionals, this group provided valuable perspectives on both operational and strategic challenges. They highlighted the importance of scalability, regulatory compliance, and fostering collaborations across different sectors.

For **older than 50** years, which also represented 34.38% of the total interviews performed, this group brought significant experience and institutional knowledge to the discussion. Their feedback emphasised the importance of sustainability, long-term planning, and the alignment of innovations with broader healthcare policies and strategies.

The age distribution of the interviewees demonstrates a broad range of perspectives, with balanced representation from younger, mid-career, and experienced professionals. This diversity ensures that the project’s findings and recommendations address the needs and priorities of stakeholders at different stages of their careers.

Table 11. Interviewees Age Groups

Age Groups	Number of interviews performed	% of the interviews performed
Younger than 20	0	0 %
Between 20 and 35	10	32 %
Between 36 and 50	11	34 %
Older than 50	11	34 %

5.1.4. Interviewees gender Analysis

As reflected in the Table 12. Interviewees Gender of the Interviewees, the gender distribution of the interviewees reflects a strong representation of women, indicating significant female involvement in the transitional care innovation ecosystem.

Women constituted the majority of interviewees, showcasing their active participation in various roles, including innovation, healthcare delivery, and policymaking. Their

insights emphasised the importance of addressing gender-specific challenges in transitional care, such as ensuring inclusive design and equitable access to healthcare solutions.

Male participants provided valuable perspectives, particularly in areas such as technological development, investment strategies, and regulatory frameworks. Their feedback highlighted the need for fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and aligning innovations with broader policy goals.

The gender analysis highlights the significant contributions of both women and men in driving innovation in transitional care. The balanced representation ensures that the project's findings are comprehensive and consider diverse viewpoints, ultimately contributing to more inclusive and effective solutions.

Table 12. Interviewees Gender of the Interviewees

Gender	Number of interviewees	% of interviewees
Woman	20	62 %
Man	12	38 %

5.2. Key modifiers from the Interviews Performed

The analysis of interviews performed provided real-valuable insights into the dynamics of transitional care innovation, highlighting critical drivers and barriers across diverse stakeholder groups. By engaging representatives from Innovators, Accelerators/Investors, Living Labs, End-users (both institutional and individual), Policymakers, and EU Initiatives, the findings paint a comprehensive picture of the ecosystem's strengths and challenges.

As noted in Table 13. Key Modifiers from Interviews performed, the findings were categorised into six domains: legal and regulatory, fiscal, technical, operational, and economic/social. Each domain highlights the factors influencing innovation in transitional care and clinical pathways, providing valuable insights for addressing challenges and leveraging enablers.

Table 13. Key Modifiers from Interviews performed

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
TG#1 Innovators: Drivers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory Flexibility • Supportive Regulatory Frameworks • Pilot-Friendly Environments • Compliance Incentives • Co-Design with Stakeholders • National Health Strategies Supporting Home Care 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of Funding and Resources • Cost Efficiency Through Technology • Government Grants and Subsidies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology Integration • Medication Management Systems • AI-Powered Predictive Analytics • Advancements in wearable technology and Internet of Things (IoT) solutions • Patient-centred technologies • Real-Time Monitoring • AI and Machine Learning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration and Stakeholder Engagement • Feedback Loops • Enhanced Care Coordination • Living Labs and Real-Life Experimentation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient-Centred Approach • Increased Accessibility • Empowerment Through Digital Tools • Cross-Border Collaboration
TG#1 Innovators: Barriers				

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complex Regulatory Requirements • Lengthy regulatory approvals • Data Privacy and Security Concerns • Slow approval processes • Compliance with diverse national regulations • Regulatory Approval for Medical Devices or AI Systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding Constraints • Reimbursement and Financial Incentives • High Upfront Costs of Innovation • Uncertain return on investment (ROI) • Limited funding • Compliance with diverse national regulations • Dependence on External Funding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Integration and Interoperability • Data Quality and Availability • User Experience Issues • Limited Infrastructure • Technology Development and Testing • Devices accuracy • Complexity of technology • Data Integration • Scalability of Solutions • Limited Accessibility to Telemedicine in Rural Areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workflow Integration Challenges • Training and Support Deficiencies • Complexity of Multi-stakeholder Involvement • Resistance to change • Fragmented care pathways • Lack of Standardisation • Staff Shortages and Workload 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance to Change • Lack of Awareness and Education • Economic Uncertainty • Limited Awareness • Insufficient Evidence of Effectiveness • Lack of trust • Digital literacy • Lack of Patient Engagement
TG#2 Accelerators/Investors: Drivers				

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Regulation and Coordination for AI Integration • Government Support for Home Care Services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Venture Capital and Public Funding Support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advancements in AI and Robotics • Wearable Devices and Monitoring Tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autonomous Technology for Home-Based Care • Hospital Digitisation • Innovative Technologies in Diagnostics and Patient Monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost-Effective Solutions • Social Acceptance
TG#2 Accelerators/Investors: Barriers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slow Regulatory Adaptation • Resistance to change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High Costs for new solutions • Unclear Financing Models • Funding Gaps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specialised, Difficult-to-Use Technologies • Lack of Standardisation in Hospital Information Systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market Inertia • Limited User Adoption • Lack of Support for Risky New Technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Resistance • Lack of Acceptance
TG#3 Living Labs: Drivers				

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder Inclusion • Collaborative Pilot Testing • Health Regulations Alignment • Opportunity to Develop a Framework 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public-Private Partnerships • Cost-Benefit Visibility • Affordability for End Users • Planned Fiscal Awareness Initiatives • Support for Bio-Health Technologies • Private Sector Engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Home-Based Health Monitoring • Simplified Technology for Elderly Users • Integration with Digital Platforms • Collaboration between faculties • Potential for Technological Advancements • Innovative Use of Monitoring Systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User-Centred Design • Matchmaking Platforms • Mobile Health Services • Integration of Real-Life Problems in Education • Quality Assurance in Education • Interdisciplinary Collaboration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Population Health Management • Success Stories and Awareness • Elderly Care Innovations • Community Engagement • Growing Interest in Transitional Care • European Collaboration Potential
<p>TG#3 Living Labs: Barriers</p>				

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory Approvals • Regulatory Complexity • Intellectual Property Issues • Alignment with Medical Professionals • Lack of Defined Regulatory Framework • Regulatory Uncertainty • Limited Focus on Transitional Care • Public Procurement Processes • Regional Disparities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High Costs of Innovation • Poor Awareness of Fiscal Incentives • Lack of Serial Production • Sustainability Challenges • Inconsistent Funding Structures • Funding Challenges in Public Systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complexity of Devices • Interoperability Issues • Reliability and Accuracy • Lack of Scalability • Legacy Infrastructure for Public systems • Data Integration Issues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to Healthcare Institutions for Pilot Testing • Stakeholder Resistance • Limited Feedback from End Users • Inconsistent Collaboration Among Universities • Weak Institutional Alliances • Stakeholder Misalignment • Bureaucratic Processes • Lack of Unified Strategies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inequitable Access • Low Awareness • Cultural Resistance • Public Sector Resistance to Change • Inequalities in Adoption • Region-Specific Challenges
<p>TG#4.1 End-users (care units, hospitals, practitioners): Drivers</p>				

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structured Home Visit Protocols • Compliance with New • Treatment Methods • Potential Regulatory Alignment with Research Innovations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government-Funded Programmes • Performance-Based Compensation • Potential Cost-Saving Technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital Documentation Platforms • Knowledge Validation Systems • Emerging Technologies for Monitoring • Real-Time Monitoring Tools • Advances in Surgical Tools and Technologies • Smart Health Devices • Innovative VR Training Programmes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardised Processes • Efficient Communication and Collaboration • Proactive Monitoring • Improved Patient Education • Tailored Post-Discharge Care • Opportunities for Residents to Test Tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced Patient Outcomes • Social Trust in Healthcare • Patient Empowerment • Increased Recovery Efficiency
<p>TG#4.1 End-users (care units, hospitals, practitioners): Barriers</p>				

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety Standard Compliance • Limited Regulatory Alignment • Bureaucratic Delays in Adoption • Lack of Standardised Protocols • Lack of Guidelines for Internal Collaboration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding Gaps • Cost of Implementation • Cost of Training and Resources • Limited Budget for Innovation • Infrastructure Challenges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Healthcare Platforms Reliability Issues • Need for Ongoing Support • Limited Digital Literacy • Specialised Training Needs • Integration into Existing Systems • Gaps Between Research and Practical Application • Staff Training and Integration Issues • Resistance to Technology Adoption by Older Adults 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective communication between stakeholders • Overwhelming Workloads • Integration Challenges • Inadequate Staff Support • Understaffing and Overwork • Fragmented Implementation • Resistance from Experienced Doctors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uneven Access to Care • Resistance to Change • Access Disparities Between Public and Private Healthcare • Inequities in Access • Disconnect Between Clinical Needs and Research Outputs

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
TG#4.2 End-users (individuals): Drivers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Privacy and Security Regulations • Telemedicine and Remote Care Legislation • E-Government Advancements • Clear Communication on Available Resources • Regulations Around Post-Treatment Consultations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insurance Coverage Expansion • Government Financial Support Programmes • Private Healthcare Access • Public Health Support for Home Care and Equipment • Efficiency of Short Hospital Stays • Cost-Effectiveness of Post-Discharge Care Models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interoperability Standards for Health Systems • Advancements in Wearable Technology • Improved User Experience Design • Basic Medical Tools for Home Monitoring • Potential for Innovative Tools • Telehealth and Remote Support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Care Coordination Models • Telehealth and Remote Follow-Up Services • Automated Discharge Planning Systems • Shortened Recovery Time in Private Care • Supportive Home Care and Family Assistance • Home Equipment Rentals • Clear Post-Discharge Instructions • Availability of Immediate Assistance Platforms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to Affordable Medical Transportation • Social Support Networks • Patient-Centred Care Initiatives • Caregiver Support • Public Insurance Role in Healthcare Access • Emotional Support and Care Quality

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
TG#4.2 End-users (individuals): Barriers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fragmented Health Information Systems • Limited Telemedicine Regulations • Bureaucratic Delays in Public Healthcare • Limited Flexibility in Public Healthcare • Insufficient Communication and Coordination • Limited Access to Post-Discharge Consultations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Out-of-Pocket Costs • Insurance Coverage Gaps • High Costs of Private Healthcare • Lack of Affordable Long-Term Care Solutions • High Costs of Home Care and Equipment • High Dependence on Family Caregivers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-User-Friendly Health Tools • Senior-Friendly Tools • Interoperability Issues • Limited Integration of Technologies • Lack of Technological Solutions for Home Recovery • Limited Use of Advanced Technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor Care Coordination • Poor Information Transfer Between Providers • Inconsistent Follow-Up Care • Inadequate Discharge Planning • Dependency on Family Support for Recovery • Inadequate Care Coordination • Difficult Transition from Hospital to Home • Inadequate Support for Self-Managed Recovery • Lack of Follow-Up Care for Complex Cases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited Access to Affordable Transportation • Social Isolation and Emotional Stress • Limited Awareness and Training on New Technologies • Inequality in Healthcare Access • Social Dependence on Family Caregivers • Limited Access to Full-Time Care • Impact of Understaffing on Care Quality • Limited Resources for Digital Support for Caregivers

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
TG#5 Policymakers / Regulatory Bodies: Drivers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Sharing Policies • Interoperability Standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding and Policy Support for IT Infrastructure • Innovation Procurement • EU Funding Programmes • Incentives for Digital Expertise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology Adoption for Interoperability • Testing and Validation of New Technologies • Digitisation of Healthcare Processes • Urgency of Technological Adoption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modernisation of Healthcare IT Systems • Public-Private Collaboration • Digital Health Record Systems • Support for Healthcare Providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainability in Care Services • Coordination Across Systems • Training and Capacity Building • Digital Tools for Healthcare Providers
TG#5 Policymakers / Regulatory Bodies: Barriers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Security and Privacy Concerns • Regulatory Variability Across Regions • Lack of Clear Legal Framework for Transitional Care • Regulatory Frameworks around the use of digital tools • Differences in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insufficient Investment in Healthcare IT Infrastructure • High Cost of New Technologies • Budget Constraints in Healthcare Systems • Long Adoption Cycles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outdated Healthcare IT Systems • Resistance to External Technological Solutions • Lack of Standardisation in Technological Solutions • Interoperability Issues • Infrastructure-Readiness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration Challenges in Healthcare Systems • Internal Focus on In-house Solutions • Limited Coordination Across Care Sectors • Bureaucratic Processes • Time and Resource Constraints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High Cost of New Technologies • Inequality in Healthcare Access • Resistance to Change in Care Practices • User Acceptance • Social Readiness for Digital Change

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
National Healthcare Systems				
TG#6 EU Initiatives: Drivers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentives for Adoption of New Technologies • Regulatory Support for Knowledge Transfer • Supportive Regulatory Frameworks • Regulations for Small Enterprises 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to Funding • Financial Incentives • Financial Funding for Startups • National and EU Funding for Research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Test Before You Invest Services • Automation and AI Integration • Integration of New Tools • Top-Tier Equipment and Facilities • High Expertise and Experience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration Across Stakeholders • Test and Pilot Opportunities • Support for Startups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for Entrepreneurs and Innovators • Networking and Knowledge Transfer

Legal and Regulatory	Fiscal	Technical	Operational	Other (economic and social)
TG#6 EU Initiatives: Barriers				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of regulatory incentives • Fragmented Regulatory • Systems Across EU Member States • Complexity of Legal Frameworks • Lack of Certification Bodies • Unclear Implementation of Health Data Regulations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insufficient Financial Support for Innovation • Unequal Access to Resources • Lack of Consistent and Sustainable Funding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interoperability Issues • Fragmentation of Information and Data • Slow Technological Integration • Lack of High Technical Expertise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of Human Resources with High Expertise • Lack of Synergies Between Stakeholders • Organisational Challenges in Public Health Sector • Challenges in Knowledge Transfer and Communication • Inefficiencies in Startup Processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public Health Sector Challenges • Population Decline and Its Impact on Healthcare Resources • Resistance to Change • Fragmented International Market • High Competition and Overwhelming Application Processes • Lack of Defined Structures in Certain Regulations

5.3. Cross-Analysis drafted from the Interviews Phase

The successful implementation and scaling of innovative healthcare solutions require a nuanced understanding of the factors that facilitate or hinder progress. Chapter 5.3 provides a comprehensive cross-analysis of the drivers and barriers identified across various target groups, including innovators, accelerators, living labs, policymakers, end-users, and EU initiatives.

By examining these factors through the lenses of legal and regulatory, fiscal, technical, operational, and economic/social dimensions, this chapter aims to highlight shared patterns and unique challenges faced by different stakeholders. This analysis serves to uncover synergies and discrepancies, offering insights into how cross-sector collaboration and targeted interventions can address barriers while leveraging key drivers.

The findings outlined in this chapter not only provide actionable recommendations but also establish a foundation for developing cohesive strategies to foster innovation, enhance interoperability, and promote equitable access to healthcare technologies across Europe and beyond.

1. Legal and Regulatory

Supportive regulatory frameworks are a recurring enabler across all target groups. Innovators (TG#1), living labs (TG#3), and EU initiatives (TG#6) benefit from harmonised European Union policies and compliance-friendly regulatory environments, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and Medical Device Regulation (MDR). However, flexibility in adapting such frameworks to emerging technologies remains a notable driver for fostering innovation.

Complex and fragmented regulatory landscapes remain a significant impediment. TG#1 (Innovators) and TG#6 (EU Initiatives) struggle with the lack of harmonised standards across member states, particularly concerning emerging AI-driven technologies.

2. Fiscal

Public funding mechanisms, venture capital, and tax incentives are observed as primary fiscal enablers for TG#2 (Accelerators), TG#5 (Policymakers), and TG#6 (EU Initiatives). Public-private partnerships also play a pivotal role in fostering technological development and adoption across multiple domains.

Insufficient funding, high costs of implementation, and reliance on short-term financing mechanisms hinder progress. TG#2 (Accelerators) and TG#5 (Policymakers) experience limitations in accessing sustainable investment models to scale their initiatives.

3. Technical

Advances in digital technologies, particularly in artificial intelligence (AI), wearable devices, and interoperable platforms, are widely recognised as transformative. TG#1 (Innovators), TG#3 (Living Labs), and TG#4.2 (End-Users: Individuals) particularly benefit from these advancements, which facilitate the development of patient-centred and predictive care solutions.

Barriers in achieving interoperability between digital health ecosystems are prevalent. TG#4.1 (End-Users: Practitioners) and TG#6 (EU Initiatives) cite the absence of common technical standards as a primary limitation to integrating data and infrastructure.

4. Operational

Cross-sectoral collaboration, stakeholder engagement, and standardised operational frameworks were frequently highlighted as critical enablers. TG#3 (Living Labs) and TG#4.1 (End-Users: Practitioners) demonstrated the importance of joint efforts to streamline processes and create integrated solutions tailored to healthcare systems.

Challenges in cross-sector coordination, resource allocation, and stakeholder alignment significantly impede progress. TG#3 (Living Labs) and TG#5 (Policymakers) identify these operational constraints as critical barriers to effective implementation.

5. Economic and Social

Social acceptance of digital health technologies, coupled with the increasing demand for patient-centric care models, serves as a foundational driver. TG#4.2 (End-Users: Individuals) and TG#6 (EU Initiatives) underscore the importance of empowering users through awareness campaigns and tools that enhance equity and accessibility in healthcare.

Resistance to change among stakeholders, inequitable access to resources, and varying levels of digital literacy are major hindrances. TG#4.2 (End-Users: Individuals) and TG#6 (EU Initiatives) are disproportionately affected by these socio-economic factors.

5.4. Conclusion of Interviews phase

The cross-analysis of drivers and barriers (modifiers) highlights the multifaceted nature of innovation in healthcare, emphasising the interplay between enabling factors and challenges. By strategically addressing barriers while leveraging key drivers, stakeholders can create a more favourable environment for the development, adoption, and scaling of health technologies.

Key drivers, such as regulatory frameworks that promote standardisation, fiscal incentives to support R&D, and technological advancements enabling interoperability, present substantial opportunities for accelerating innovation. Operational initiatives, such as fostering collaborative ecosystems and engaging end-users early in the process, further enhance the potential for success. Economic and social drivers, such as increased awareness of health equity and the prioritisation of patient-centred care, serve as critical motivators for stakeholders across the healthcare spectrum.

However, significant barriers persist. Regulatory fragmentation limited financial resources, and technical challenges, such as lack of interoperability and cybersecurity concerns, hinder progress. Operational inefficiencies, including insufficient communication between stakeholders and misalignment of goals, exacerbate these challenges. Economic and social barriers, such as disparities in access to innovation and resistance to change, also pose critical roadblocks.

To address these barriers, this analysis underscores the importance of targeted interventions. Recommendations include Harmonising regulatory frameworks across regions, increasing public and private funding for innovation, and investing in scalable technical solutions that prioritise security and interoperability. Additionally, fostering stakeholder collaboration and ensuring equitable access to health technologies are pivotal strategies for overcoming operational and social barriers.

By aligning efforts to Capitalise on drivers and mitigate barriers, stakeholders can build a more inclusive, sustainable, and impactful innovation ecosystem. This will not only accelerate the development and deployment of transformative healthcare solutions but also contribute to improving health outcomes across diverse populations in Europe and beyond.

6. General Findings

This chapter consolidates the insights gathered from the different research components of the Evolve2Care project, aiming to provide a deeper understanding of the current state and dynamics within the transitional care innovation ecosystem. It integrates findings to identify recurring themes, diverging perspectives, and areas for further investigation.

Through a detailed cross-analysis, this chapter explores the common and distinct challenges and enablers across various stakeholder groups, providing a nuanced picture of the landscape. It sets the stage for actionable recommendations and strategic directions that will guide the next phases of the project.

6.1 Cross-Analysis of Findings

This section integrates insights from **literature reviews**, **surveys**, and **stakeholder interviews** to paint a comprehensive picture of the challenges and opportunities within transitional care innovation. By combining quantitative and qualitative data, it provides a robust analysis of the ecosystem, highlighting areas of alignment and divergence across different stakeholder groups.

The integration process combines findings from the literature review, surveys, and stakeholder interviews to offer a holistic view of transitional care innovation. This multi-faceted approach allows for the identification of both commonalities and differences in perspectives across the research components. It helps to understand how various drivers and barriers intersect and impact the development and adoption of innovative technologies in transitional care.

Common Drivers Across Research Components:

From the literature, surveys, and interviews, several key drivers for innovation in transitional care emerge consistently:

- **Regulatory Support and Flexibility:** Both the literature review and interview insights emphasise the importance of a supportive and flexible regulatory environment. Key regulatory drivers identified include incentives for compliance with regulations, flexible frameworks for innovation, and the alignment of policies with new technologies. Stakeholders from all target groups (innovators, policymakers, and end-users) recognised that regulatory support facilitates smoother adoption and scaling of new technologies, particularly in the context of home care and AI integration.

- **Technological Advancements:** Advancements in wearable technologies, AI, and machine learning are common themes across the research components. Innovations in predictive analytics, real-time monitoring, and patient-centred technologies were highlighted as major enablers for improving transitional care. The integration of digital tools, such as telehealth and remote monitoring systems, emerged as a core driver of change, particularly in making care more accessible and efficient.
- **Collaboration and Stakeholder Engagement:** A strong theme that runs across all components is the need for collaboration among stakeholders—healthcare providers, patients, researchers, and technology developers. The survey data and interviews indicated that successful innovations in transitional care often stem from a collaborative approach, with stakeholders co-designing solutions. This finding aligns with literature suggesting that pilot projects and feedback loops are essential for refining and scaling new technologies in real-world healthcare settings.

Diverging Perspectives on Barriers:

While some barriers to innovation in transitional care were universally acknowledged, the severity and specifics of these barriers varied significantly across the research components:

- **Regulatory Challenges:** The literature review underscored the complexity and variability of regulatory frameworks across regions, highlighting the challenges posed by lengthy approval processes and the difficulty in aligning national regulations. In contrast, interviews with innovators and policymakers identified regulatory uncertainty and the lack of harmonised regulations as significant barriers to innovation. These differences underscore the tension between regulatory flexibility needed for rapid innovation and the regulatory rigor required to ensure safety and compliance.
- **Funding and Financial Constraints:** Funding emerged as a critical barrier across all components, but with different nuances. Innovators noted the difficulty in securing sufficient investment and the challenge of navigating reimbursement systems, while policymakers and accelerators pointed to the need for clearer financing models and more sustainable funding structures. The divergence in perspectives emphasises the need for a more cohesive financial strategy to support innovation, particularly for startups and small enterprises in transitional care.
- **Technology Integration and Interoperability:** Both the surveys and the literature identified interoperability as a major challenge in the integration of new

technologies into existing healthcare systems. Innovators and living labs reported significant hurdles in aligning new technologies with legacy systems, particularly in rural and under-resourced areas. The lack of standardisation in data formats and systems further complicates integration efforts. This barrier, however, was less pronounced in the interviews with end-users (both practitioners and patients), where concerns were more focused on the usability and accessibility of digital tools rather than technical interoperability.

Intersection of Drivers and Barriers:

The integration of insights from literature, surveys, and interviews reveals how certain drivers and barriers intersect and compound one another, creating both challenges and opportunities:

- **Regulatory Flexibility vs. Safety and Compliance Concerns:** While regulatory flexibility is crucial for fostering innovation, it must be balanced with safety and compliance concerns, particularly for medical devices and AI systems. Innovators noted that navigating this balance is one of the key challenges in ensuring that new technologies are both safe for patients and adaptable to evolving regulatory frameworks.
- **Technological Advancements vs. Limited Infrastructure:** The rapid pace of technological advancements in wearable devices, AI, and telemedicine presents significant opportunities for improving transitional care. However, these innovations often outpace the infrastructure needed to support them. Both living labs and healthcare providers expressed concerns about the limitations of existing systems to fully integrate these technologies, particularly in rural and underserved areas where access to infrastructure is limited.
- **Collaboration vs. Resistance to Change:** While collaboration is widely seen as a key driver of innovation, interviews with healthcare practitioners and patients revealed a significant barrier in the form of resistance to change. Healthcare providers, particularly experienced practitioners, expressed reluctance to adopt new technologies, fearing disruption to established practices. This resistance is compounded by a lack of training, trust, and perceived inefficiencies associated with new technologies.

Implications for Transitional Care Innovation:

- **Holistic Support Systems:** The integration of insights indicates the need for more holistic support systems to drive the adoption of new technologies. This includes not only regulatory and financial support but also dedicated training programmes for healthcare providers and patients to ensure the effective use of new tools.

Policies must address both the technological and human factors that influence the adoption of innovations in transitional care.

- **Customised Solutions for Different Stakeholder Groups:** Different stakeholders have different needs and concerns. For instance, policymakers are more focused on regulatory and infrastructure issues, while innovators are concerned with funding and technical challenges. Understanding these divergent perspectives is crucial for developing customised solutions that address the unique needs of each stakeholder group, while also promoting overall system-wide integration.
- **Sustainability of Innovations:** A key theme that emerged from the integration process is the need for sustainable innovations. This includes securing long-term funding and developing scalable solutions that can be implemented across different healthcare settings. Both literature and interviews highlighted the importance of demonstrating the long-term impact of innovations on patient outcomes and cost-efficiency to ensure widespread adoption.

The integration of insights from the **literature review, surveys, and interviews** offers a comprehensive view of the current state of transitional care innovation. It highlights common drivers, such as regulatory support, technological advancements, and collaboration, as well as diverging barriers, such as regulatory complexity, funding constraints, and technological integration challenges. Understanding how these factors intersect and impact the development and adoption of innovative technologies is crucial for shaping future strategies and ensuring the success of transitional care innovations. By addressing both common and unique concerns across stakeholder groups, we can foster a more integrated and efficient system of care that benefits patients, healthcare providers, and society as a whole.

6.2 Identification of recurring themes and diverging perspectives

This subchapter identifies recurring themes that emerged across the different data sources, such as regulatory complexities, the importance of user-centred design, and the role of funding as a key enabler. Additionally, it highlights diverging perspectives between stakeholder groups. For example, innovators may prioritise technical challenges, while end-users may focus on usability and accessibility concerns. These nuanced insights reveal areas where alignment is needed to advance transitional care innovations effectively.

Recurring Themes Across Data Sources:

Several recurring themes emerged across the different research components, illustrating the shared concerns, opportunities, and challenges in transitional care innovation.

- **Regulatory Complexities:** Regulatory complexities surfaced as a dominant theme across all data sources. The literature and interviews with policymakers highlighted the difficulties in aligning national and international regulatory frameworks to accommodate emerging healthcare technologies. Innovators also emphasised the need for clearer, more flexible regulatory pathways to bring new solutions to market. The lack of harmonisation across jurisdictions was a significant barrier, delaying the introduction of potentially impactful technologies. However, there was consensus that regulatory clarity and support would ease the adoption of innovations, making this an essential area for reform.
- **User-Centred Design and Usability:** The importance of user-centred design emerged as a critical theme, particularly in the surveys and interviews with end-users (healthcare providers, patients, and caregivers). Both innovators and end-users emphasised the need for technologies that are intuitive, easy to use, and address the specific needs of patients transitioning from hospital to home care. Healthcare professionals noted that usability was a major factor in the success of new technologies, as tools that are difficult to operate or integrate into existing workflows were likely to face resistance. This theme was further underscored by literature suggesting that successful innovation in transitional care must be aligned with the practical realities of everyday clinical practice and patient needs.
- **The Role of Funding as a Key Enabler:** Funding emerged consistently across all research components as a key enabler for the development and scaling of transitional care innovations. Innovators and accelerators identified the lack of financial resources as a significant barrier, hindering progress from prototypes to large-scale implementations. Policymakers, in turn, acknowledged the need for clear and sustainable funding models that would support both startups and large organisations in the healthcare space. The literature highlighted the importance of public-private partnerships to drive funding, especially for high-risk technologies that require extensive validation and pilot testing before they can be widely adopted.

Diverging Perspectives Among Stakeholder Groups:

While common themes emerged, there were also significant differences in the perspectives of various stakeholder groups, which highlighted areas where alignment is required to move forward effectively.

- **Innovators vs. End-Users (Healthcare Providers and Patients):** Innovators and end-users had divergent views on the technological aspects of transitional care innovations. Innovators primarily focused on the technical challenges of developing new tools, such as interoperability, data security, and scalability. They highlighted the need for platforms and devices that can function seamlessly across different healthcare settings. On the other hand, end-users, especially healthcare practitioners, emphasised usability and accessibility. They were more concerned with how well new technologies fit into their existing workflows and the degree to which these tools could be integrated into daily clinical practice. Similarly, patients and caregivers were primarily focused on the ease of use, the ability to personalise technologies to individual needs, and whether the technology could genuinely enhance the quality of care during transitions.
- **Innovators vs. Policymakers:** Innovators and policymakers also showed diverging perspectives, particularly regarding regulatory issues. Innovators expressed frustration with the slow pace of regulatory approval and the challenges posed by fragmented regulatory environments across countries. They advocated for more streamlined approval processes and greater flexibility in regulatory frameworks to allow for faster innovation and implementation. Policymakers, however, underscored the importance of maintaining stringent safety standards and regulatory oversight to protect patients from the risks associated with untested technologies. The challenge, therefore, lies in finding a balance between regulatory flexibility that fosters innovation and maintaining the necessary safeguards to ensure patient safety.
- **Healthcare Providers vs. Patients:** Another area of divergence was between healthcare providers and patients. Healthcare providers expressed concerns about the adoption of new technologies within clinical workflows, focusing on issues such as training requirements, cost, and integration with existing systems. On the other hand, patients were more focused on the practicality of using these technologies in everyday life. They were particularly concerned about the ease of understanding and operating new tools, as well as their ability to manage their care independently. These differing priorities reveal the need for innovations that not only address clinical efficacy but also empower patients with tools that are user-friendly and provide tangible benefits in managing their own health.
- **Living Labs vs. Innovators:** Living labs, which focus on the real-world testing and iteration of new healthcare technologies, had a slightly different focus compared to innovators. While innovators were concerned with the development and refinement of technology, living labs placed more emphasis on the importance of feedback loops and real-world testing in clinical environments. They advocated for more pilot studies and collaborative testing environments where technologies

could be tested and refined based on end-user experiences. Innovators, however, were more concerned with overcoming technical hurdles and market readiness, sometimes viewing feedback from living labs as an additional layer of complexity.

Areas for Alignment:

The diverging perspectives among stakeholder groups highlight several areas where alignment is needed to ensure the effective advancement of transitional care innovations:

- **Collaboration between Innovators and End-Users:** A key area for alignment is the collaboration between innovators and end-users to ensure that new technologies meet the practical needs of healthcare providers and patients. Engaging end-users in the design and testing phases of innovation can help identify usability issues early, ensuring that technologies are not only effective but also easy to use and integrate into daily practice.
- **Balancing Flexibility and Regulation:** Innovators and policymakers must work together to find a regulatory framework that balances the need for flexibility and rapid innovation with the imperative of ensuring patient safety. Harmonising regulations across countries and establishing clearer pathways for regulatory approval could accelerate the development and adoption of new technologies in transitional care.
- **Sustainable Funding Models:** The alignment of financial resources is another critical area. Policymakers and funding bodies must create more sustainable and clear funding models to support the development and scaling of transitional care innovations. This could include long-term funding commitments for pilot projects and public-private partnerships that encourage investment in high-risk but potentially high-reward technologies.

Implications for Transitional Care Innovation:

- **User-Centred, Interdisciplinary Approaches:** To foster the development of technologies that meet the needs of both healthcare providers and patients, interdisciplinary teams should be involved in the design and implementation of innovations. This will ensure that technological solutions are both clinically effective and user-friendly.
- **Clear and Flexible Regulatory Pathways:** Streamlining the regulatory approval process while maintaining patient safety is crucial. This requires continued collaboration between innovators, regulators, and healthcare providers to create regulatory frameworks that are flexible and responsive to new developments in technology.

- **Improved Funding Support:** Policymakers must create more robust funding structures that provide ongoing financial support for innovations in transitional care. This includes targeted funding for pilot projects, commercialisation efforts, and scaling-up successful innovations.

The identification of recurring themes and diverging perspectives highlights the complexity of advancing transitional care innovations. While there are shared challenges—such as regulatory complexities, the need for user-centred design, and the critical role of funding—there are also significant differences in priorities among stakeholders. Innovators, healthcare providers, policymakers, and patients each bring unique perspectives, and aligning these viewpoints is essential for fostering successful innovation in transitional care. By focusing on collaboration, flexibility in regulation, and sustainable funding, we can move toward a more integrated and effective system of transitional care.

6.3 Insights into legal, regulatory, fiscal, technical, and operational challenges

This sub-subchapter provides a focused examination of the insights into the legal and regulatory, fiscal, technical, operational and other (economic and social) challenges identified through the analysis. It identifies the specific issues that need to be addressed to enable the successful implementation of HealthTech innovations in transitional care.

1. Legal and Regulatory Challenges:

Legal and regulatory challenges have been recognised as significant barriers in the path of HealthTech innovations, especially in transitional care. A closer look at the insights gathered reveals a variety of complex issues that need to be addressed:

- **Fragmented and Inconsistent Regulations:** Stakeholders, particularly innovators and policymakers, highlighted the lack of uniform regulatory frameworks across different regions as a key challenge. While some countries have well-established regulatory pathways for digital health, others are still in the process of developing standards. This creates confusion and delays, especially for HealthTech solutions aiming for cross-border application. Regulatory complexity, particularly in Europe, hinders innovators' ability to scale solutions efficiently.
- **Regulatory Uncertainty in New Technologies:** The rapid pace of technological innovation often outstrips the ability of regulatory bodies to adapt. Solutions like wearables, telemedicine platforms, and AI-powered diagnostics are often assessed through existing frameworks that do not fully account for their unique

characteristics. This regulatory uncertainty creates a hesitancy in the market, with innovators unsure of the approval process and timeline, leading to delays in product development.

- **Data Privacy and Security Concerns:** Data privacy continues to be a major concern, especially with the increasing use of patient data in HealthTech solutions. Regulatory frameworks like GDPR in Europe impose strict requirements on data handling, creating complexities for innovators who must ensure compliance while also protecting user privacy. These data privacy concerns are particularly critical for HealthTech solutions that rely on cloud storage or involve cross-border data transfer.
- **Liability and Accountability:** The issue of liability is critical for HealthTech innovations, particularly when they interact directly with patient care. Innovators must navigate the complex question of who is responsible when a technological failure occurs. In many cases, the lack of clear liability frameworks increases the risk for innovators, slowing down the adoption of new technologies in healthcare settings.

2. Fiscal Challenges:

Fiscal constraints are another significant barrier to the adoption and scaling of HealthTech solutions. Financial concerns impact both innovators and healthcare providers, hindering the efficient implementation of innovations in transitional care:

- **Lack of Sustainable Funding and Investment:** Innovators reported significant difficulties in securing the necessary funding to develop and pilot new HealthTech solutions. While early-stage funding is available through venture capital and public funding programmes, there is a notable gap in funding for scaling innovations. The need for long-term investment to support the development of viable, sustainable solutions is critical, but many stakeholders expressed frustration with the instability of available funding.
- **High Upfront Costs of Implementation:** Healthcare providers expressed concern over the initial costs of adopting new technologies. Although HealthTech solutions may provide long-term cost savings, the upfront costs associated with purchasing, installing, and integrating new technologies are often a significant barrier. This is especially problematic in public healthcare systems with limited budgets, where economic sustainability and immediate ROI are key factors in decision-making.
- **Reimbursement Issues:** A critical fiscal challenge for healthcare providers is the lack of clear reimbursement structures for HealthTech innovations. Many HealthTech solutions, particularly those in transitional care, are not covered by

existing reimbursement policies. As a result, providers are hesitant to adopt new technologies that may not be reimbursed through traditional insurance or public funding systems. This creates a barrier to scaling innovative solutions, particularly those that could offer substantial benefits to patients during their transitions between care settings.

3. Technical Challenges:

The integration of HealthTech innovations into existing healthcare systems presents a range of technical challenges that need to be addressed to ensure seamless implementation:

- **Interoperability Issues:** The lack of standardisation and interoperability between different health systems is one of the most frequently mentioned technical challenges. Many HealthTech solutions require seamless data exchange between various healthcare systems, such as electronic health records (EHRs), diagnostic tools, and monitoring devices. However, these systems often use different formats and standards, which leads to inefficiencies, errors, and delays in patient care.
- **Scalability and Customisation:** Innovators highlighted the difficulty in ensuring that their solutions are scalable across different healthcare environments. Solutions that work in a small clinic may not be suitable for larger, more complex hospital settings, and vice versa. In addition, the need for Customisation to meet the specific needs of different patient groups, healthcare professionals, and institutions was emphasised as a key barrier to scalability.
- **User-Centred Design and Accessibility:** The technical design of HealthTech solutions must prioritise user-centred design, ensuring that the technology is intuitive, easy to use, and accessible to all users. This is particularly important for patients, who may have limited technical expertise. HealthTech solutions that are difficult for patients to use or understand can lead to disengagement and non-adoption, undermining the effectiveness of transitional care innovations.

4. Operational Challenges:

Operational challenges are often cited by healthcare providers as obstacles to implementing new HealthTech solutions, particularly in transitional care settings where continuity of care is crucial:

- **Integration into Existing Care Pathways:** The integration of new technologies into existing workflows is often more complicated than anticipated. Healthcare providers pointed out that HealthTech innovations often require significant

changes to care pathways, which can be met with resistance from staff and healthcare organisations. The need for effective change management strategies and the alignment of technology with existing processes is critical to ensure that new technologies are adopted smoothly.

- **Training and Support for Healthcare Professionals:** Operational difficulties arise when healthcare professionals are not adequately trained to use new technologies. Innovators and providers both expressed the need for comprehensive training programmes to ensure that all healthcare professionals are competent in using new tools. Ongoing technical support is also necessary to address any issues that arise after implementation.
- **Patient Engagement and Adoption:** Ensuring that patients understand and are willing to engage with new technologies is another key operational challenge. Patient education, trust-building, and ensuring that new technologies are user-friendly are essential to the successful implementation of HealthTech solutions in transitional care. Without active patient involvement, even the best-designed technologies may fail to deliver their intended outcomes.

5. Other (Economic and Social) Challenges:

In addition to the legal, regulatory, fiscal, technical, and operational challenges, there are also economic and social factors that impact the success of HealthTech innovations in transitional care:

- **Economic Viability and Long-Term Sustainability:** Economic concerns about the long-term sustainability of HealthTech solutions were expressed by several stakeholders. The cost-effectiveness of these innovations, especially in terms of improving patient outcomes and reducing healthcare costs, is critical for their long-term viability. The economic impact of adopting new technologies must be carefully evaluated to ensure that it aligns with the financial constraints of healthcare systems.
- **Social Acceptance and Trust:** Social factors, including public perception and trust in technology, play a significant role in the adoption of HealthTech solutions. Concerns about the dehumanisation of care, data privacy, and the potential for misuse of patient information were raised in interviews with patients and healthcare professionals. Building trust in HealthTech solutions is crucial to overcoming social resistance to innovation.

Summary of Challenges:

The insights into the challenges across the **legal and regulatory, fiscal, technical, operational,** and **economic/social domains** highlight the multifaceted nature of the barriers to HealthTech innovation in transitional care. Key challenges include:

- **Legal and Regulatory:** Fragmented regulations, regulatory uncertainty, data privacy concerns, and liability issues.
- **Fiscal:** Lack of sustainable funding, high implementation costs, and reimbursement challenges.
- **Technical:** Interoperability, scalability, user-centred design, and accessibility concerns.
- **Operational:** Integration into care pathways, need for training and support, and patient engagement.
- **Economic and Social:** Economic viability, long-term sustainability, and social acceptance/trust.

Addressing these challenges requires coordinated efforts from innovators, healthcare providers, regulators, and policymakers to create an environment conducive to the successful implementation and scaling of HealthTech innovations in transitional care.

The insights into the five domains reveal the complexity of introducing HealthTech solutions into transitional care settings. By identifying and addressing these challenges early, stakeholders can work together to pave the way for innovations that improve patient outcomes, enhance care coordination, and ultimately contribute to more efficient and effective transitional care systems.

7. Implications and Next Steps

This chapter outlines the implications of the interim findings for the Evolve2Care project and provides a roadmap for the next steps. The results from this phase offer a foundational understanding of the drivers and barriers influencing transitional care innovation, which will directly inform the refinement of the project's Use Cases but also the drive the selection and pathways of Innovators in transitional care. Furthermore, this chapter details the planned activities for the final phase, focusing on the analysis of Use Case outcomes and the preparation of the final deliverable.

7.1. Relevance to Use Case Refinement and Use Case Selection

The interim findings from **the literature review, surveys, and stakeholder interviews** provide invaluable insights into the **key drivers and barriers** that influence the development and implementation of innovative solutions in transitional care. These insights are essential for refining the Use Cases within the Evolve2Care project and also driving the design of specific KPIs for the evaluation of the Use Cases that would be selected through the calls, ensuring that they are grounded in real-world challenges and opportunities.

The analysis of the drivers and barriers are summarized below:

- **User-Centred Design:** The emphasis on user-centred design across stakeholder groups should be integral to the development of Use Cases that address the needs of both patients and healthcare providers. This is well in-line with the Living Lab methodology. The solutions should be designed with accessibility and ease of use as top priorities to ensure high levels of engagement and adoption.
- **Regulatory and Fiscal Considerations:** The identification of regulatory complexities and fiscal challenges will inform the development of Use Cases that consider the legal and financial landscape. By addressing these constraints early in the design phase, the project can ensure that proposed solutions are not only technically viable but also aligned with existing regulatory frameworks and financially sustainable models.
- **Interoperability and Integration:** The technical challenge of ensuring interoperability between systems is one of the primary concerns identified in the interim findings. The Use Cases will therefore need to prioritise seamless integration with existing health systems, ensuring that data flows smoothly between various platforms, such as EHRs and digital health tools.

- **Scalability and Customisation:** Insights into the challenges of scaling solutions across different healthcare environments will inform the design of adaptable Use Cases that can be tailored to different settings and patient groups. Customisation and scalability will be key considerations in ensuring the widespread applicability and success of the solutions.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** The emerging themes Emphasise the importance of active collaboration among innovators, regulators, and end-users. This ensures that the Use Cases address the priorities of all stakeholders and fosters greater adoption of innovative solutions.

7.2. Plans for the Final Phase

The final phase of the project (**Months 19-24**) will build upon the findings of this Deliverable and focus on analysing the outcomes of the Use Case activities within the Living Labs. Key planned activities include:

- **Execution and Monitoring of Use Cases:** The Living Labs will implement and monitor the Use Cases designed during the interim phase. This will involve iterative testing, real-world validation, and the collection of feedback from stakeholders.
- **Comprehensive Data Analysis:** The data gathered during the Use Case activities will be analysed to evaluate the effectiveness of the solutions in addressing identified challenges. This includes assessing their impact on transitional care, usability, and scalability.
- **Integration of Findings:** The final deliverable will synthesise insights from both the interim and final phases. This comprehensive report will outline the key drivers and barriers, actionable recommendations, and a roadmap for scaling innovative solutions in transitional care.
- **Dissemination and Stakeholder Engagement:** The final report will be shared with all project partners and stakeholders, including innovators, policymakers, and EU initiatives. Workshops and webinars will be organised to disseminate findings and gather additional feedback.

The final phase will culminate in the submission of the complete deliverable, consolidating all findings and providing strategic guidance for advancing innovation in transitional care. This phase represents the critical juncture where the project's insights are transformed into actionable outcomes, driving forward **the mission** of Evolve2Care.

8. Conclusion

The interim phase of the Evolve2Care project has provided valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities shaping innovation in transitional care. By leveraging a multi-method approach that combined literature reviews, surveys, and stakeholder interviews, the project has built a strong foundation for addressing the complexities of this sector. This chapter summarises the key achievements from the interim phase and underscores the importance of these findings in guiding the project's next steps and ultimate objectives.

8.1. Summary of key achievements from the interim phase

The interim phase of the Evolve2Care project has made significant strides in understanding the multifaceted landscape of transitional care. Key achievements include:

- **Comprehensive Data Collection:** Through a combination of literature reviews, surveys, and stakeholder interviews, the project has gathered a broad range of data that captures the diverse perspectives of stakeholders across the healthcare ecosystem. This data has been essential in identifying both commonalities and differences in perspectives, contributing to a nuanced understanding of transitional care.
- **Identification of Key Drivers and Barriers:** The analysis revealed critical drivers that facilitate innovation in transitional care, such as the importance of user-centred design, the role of funding as a key enabler, and the need for regulatory alignment. Concurrently, barriers were identified, including regulatory complexities, technical challenges, and the fiscal constraints that limit the scalability of solutions.
- **Cross-Analysis of Findings:** By integrating findings from multiple sources, the project has been able to provide a holistic view of the issues impacting transitional care innovation. This cross-analysis has highlighted recurring themes and diverging perspectives, offering actionable insights for the design and implementation of solutions.
- **Focused Examination of Legal and Regulatory, Fiscal, Technical, Operational and Other (Economic and Social) Challenges:** The insights into the specific challenges in these areas have provided a detailed roadmap for addressing critical obstacles. These insights are essential for ensuring that the innovations

developed within the Evolve2Care project are not only technically feasible but also legally compliant, financially viable, and operationally sustainable.

- **Stakeholder Engagement:** The engagement of diverse stakeholders, including innovators, healthcare providers, policymakers, EU initiatives and end-users, has enriched the project's understanding of the real-world challenges and opportunities in transitional care. This ongoing dialogue ensures that the project remains aligned with the needs and expectations of all relevant parties.

These achievements set the stage for the next phase of the project, where the findings will be translated into concrete Use Cases and real-world applications.

8.2. Importance of findings for the project's objectives

The insights gained during the interim phase are crucial for guiding the Evolve2Care project towards its ultimate objectives. These findings not only enhance the understanding of transitional care but also provide a strategic foundation for the project's next steps.

- **Informed Use Case Development:** The identification of key drivers, barriers, and challenges will directly inform the development of the project's Use Cases. By addressing these factors, the project can ensure that the solutions proposed are both practical and innovative. The insights into user-centred design, regulatory requirements, and interoperability will be instrumental in creating solutions that are feasible, scalable, and aligned with the needs of end-users.
- **Roadmap for Overcoming Barriers:** The detailed examination of barriers in legal, regulatory, fiscal, technical, and operational areas offers a clear roadmap for overcoming the obstacles that may impede the successful implementation of transitional care innovations. Addressing these challenges early in the design process will help mitigate risks and maximise the impact of the project.
- **Guiding Stakeholder Alignment:** The insights into diverging perspectives among stakeholders are crucial for ensuring alignment and collaboration across the project. The differences in priorities between innovators, healthcare providers, and end-users highlight the need for a balanced approach that incorporates the interests and concerns of all stakeholders. This understanding will foster better collaboration and help ensure that the solutions developed meet the needs of the entire healthcare ecosystem.
- **Strengthening the Final Deliverables:** The findings from the interim phase will inform the final phase of the project, where the solutions will be tested and

refined. By ensuring that the solutions are based on a thorough understanding of the landscape, the project is poised to deliver meaningful and impactful innovations in transitional care.

In conclusion, the interim phase has been instrumental in shaping the Evolve2Care project's direction. The insights gained will continue to inform and guide the development of innovative solutions, ensuring that the project remains focused on addressing the real-world challenges of transitional care. As the project moves into its final phase, these findings will be critical in ensuring that the solutions are not only technically successful but also impactful in improving care transitions for patients across Europe.

Annexes

List of all sources used for the literature review and data collection.

Peer- reviewed Articles:

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5. Cross, D. A., et al. (2019). Value-based programmes for improved cost efficiency in healthcare. *The American Journal of Managed Care*, 25(1), 34–40. Retrieved from https://ajmc.s3.amazonaws.com/media/pdf/AJMC_01_2019_Cross%20final.pdf
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Reports:

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10. European Commission. (2023). Final open access report for Horizon 2020 framework programmes. Retrieved December 16, 2024, from <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e507e3d47a&appld=PPGMS>

Surveys Questions templates.

Survey template for TG#1 Innovators

This survey looks at Innovators, Researchers, and Entrepreneurs' experiences in the development of innovative health tech solutions for transitional care and clinical pathways. Thank you for taking the time to participate in our research. Your feedback will provide valuable insights into how we can overcome challenges and accelerate the adoption of innovations that improve patient outcomes and care coordination.

1. How familiar are you with the concept of "transitional care" or "clinical pathways" in healthcare?
 - Very familiar
 - Somewhat familiar
 - Not familiar at all
2. Have you been involved in the development or evaluation of innovative solutions targeting transitional care or clinical pathways over the past two years?
 - Yes, actively involved in multiple projects
 - Yes, but only at a limited capacity
 - No, but currently exploring potential projects
 - No, but I'm interested in future opportunities
3. What do you believe are the most important drivers of innovation in the transitional care and clinical pathways sector? (Select up to 3)
 - Advances in AI and machine learning for predictive analytics and decision support
 - Growing demand for personalised care (e.g., genomics, precision medicine)

- Increasing emphasis on value-based care and outcomes-driven models
- Expanding use of remote patient monitoring (RPM) and digital health tools
- Demand for improved patient care coordination and reduced fragmentation
- Enhanced funding and investment in health tech startups
- Collaboration between technology innovators and healthcare providers (e.g., partnerships with payers, hospitals, or medical networks)
- Regulatory and policy shifts supporting new models of care (e.g., reimbursement for telehealth)
- Expansion of telemedicine and virtual care models (e.g., telehealth, remote monitoring)
- Other (please specify): _____

4. Which external factors do you believe will most accelerate the adoption of innovative solutions in transitional care or clinical pathways over the next 3-5 years? (Select up to 3)

- Changes in healthcare reimbursement policies that incentivise innovative care models (e.g., pay-for-performance, value-based care)
- Increased investment and funding in health tech innovations
- Stronger collaboration between startups and established healthcare organisations (e.g., hospital systems, insurance companies)
- Widespread adoption of AI, wearables, and digital health tools
- Shift toward integrated care models combining in-hospital, outpatient, and home care
- Regulatory support or simplification (e.g., faster approval processes for new healthcare technologies)
- Government or industry support for data privacy and security standards in digital health
- Enhanced patient demand for technology-driven, personalised care experiences
- Other (please specify): _____

5. What internal capabilities within startups or health tech companies do you believe are critical to driving successful innovation in transitional care or clinical pathways? (Select up to 3)

- A deep understanding of clinical workflows and healthcare system challenges
- Strong technical expertise in AI, machine learning, and data analytics
- A clear business model and pathway to profitability
- Proven ability to scale technology solutions across diverse healthcare settings
- Clinical validation and strong evidence of patient outcomes
- An experienced founding team with a mix of healthcare and technology expertise

- Effective partnerships with key stakeholders (e.g., hospitals, insurers, tech providers)
- Strong intellectual property (IP) and proprietary technologies
- Other (please specify): _____

6. What do you consider to be the biggest barriers to the successful development and scaling of innovative solutions in transitional care or clinical pathways? (Select up to 3)

- Regulatory challenges and the complexity of compliance with healthcare laws (e.g., FDA approval, HIPAA, GDPR)
- Resistance to adopting new technologies from healthcare providers or patients
- Lack of clear reimbursement models for digital health solutions or new care pathways
- Fragmentation of healthcare systems and difficulty integrating with existing workflows
- High development and implementation costs, particularly for clinical trials and product validation
- Long timelines for technology adoption in healthcare settings
- Insufficient clinical evidence or real-world data to support technology claims
- Limited collaboration between tech innovators and traditional healthcare systems (e.g., hospitals, insurers)
- Difficulty navigating the complex healthcare landscape and market dynamics
- Other (please specify): _____

7. To what extent do you believe regulatory challenges affect the speed and success of innovation in transitional care and clinical pathways? (Scale: 1 = No impact at all, 5 = Significant impact)

- 1 - No impact at all
- 2 - Minimal impact
- 3 - Moderate impact
- 4 - Strong impact
- 5 - Significant impact

8. What specific regulatory or compliance-related challenges do you believe most hinder innovation in this space? (Select up to 3)

- Slow or unpredictable regulatory approval processes for new technologies
- Uncertainty around reimbursement policies for new care models or digital health solutions
- Lack of clear standards for digital health data security and privacy

- Difficulty in navigating varying regulations across different markets or regions (e.g., EU vs. US)
- Barriers to obtaining FDA or CE mark approvals for new technologies
- Complex documentation and reporting requirements for clinical trials or pilot studies
- Other (please specify): _____

9. What market barriers do you think are most significant in preventing innovations in transitional care from reaching the scale they need to impact patient outcomes? (Select up to 3)

- Market fragmentation, with multiple competing players and no clear dominant solution
- Insufficient demand from healthcare providers or patients for new technologies
- Limited or unclear reimbursement options for innovative care models
- Difficulty in integrating new technologies with existing hospital or clinic systems
- High upfront investment required to develop and deploy solutions
- Limited evidence of return on investment (ROI) or effectiveness in improving patient outcomes
- Uncertainty about market readiness for disruptive innovations
- Other (please specify): _____

10. In your opinion, which factors are most important for enabling the scaling of innovative solutions in transitional care? (Select up to 3)

- Streamlined regulatory processes and clear reimbursement pathways
- Increased investment and funding for health tech innovation
- Effective public-private partnerships to promote technology adoption in healthcare
- Access to clinical data and evidence to support scaling efforts
- Strong collaboration between healthcare providers, insurers, and tech innovators
- Widespread training and education for healthcare professionals on new technologies
- Expansion of health tech infrastructure (e.g., broadband access for telehealth)
- Market incentives for early adoption of disruptive technologies
- Other (please specify): _____

11. Which technological innovations do you believe will be most important in enabling the future of transitional care? (Select up to 3)

- AI-driven decision support tools for clinicians and patients
- Wearables and remote monitoring tools for continuous patient data collection

- Virtual care models and telemedicine platforms for ongoing patient engagement
- Predictive analytics for identifying high-risk patients and improving care planning
- Advanced patient engagement platforms to improve adherence and care coordination
- Integration of digital health tools with electronic health records (EHRs)
- Personalised medicine and genomics for tailoring care pathways
- Other (please specify): _____

12. What do you see as the most critical market trends that will drive the next wave of innovation in transitional care or clinical pathways over the next 3-5 years?

- Growth in value-based care and performance-based reimbursement models
- Continued expansion of AI, machine learning, and predictive analytics in healthcare
- Increased adoption of home healthcare and remote patient monitoring technologies
- Shifts toward more personalised, precision care models using genomics and tailored treatments
- Widespread adoption of telemedicine and virtual care to improve access and reduce costs
- Enhanced focus on mental health and integrated behavioural health services
- Changing regulatory frameworks that incentivise innovation and streamline approval processes
- Other (please specify): _____

13. If you have been involved in the development or evaluation of startups in this space, can you share any lessons learned or best practices that have shaped your approach to overcoming barriers in transitional care?

[Open-ended response]

14. Would you be open to sharing more insights through an interview?

- Yes, I am available for an interview
- No, thank you

Survey template for TG#2 Accelerators/Investors

This survey looks at accelerators/investor attitudes and funding preferences regarding innovative health tech solutions for transitional care and clinical pathways. Thank you for taking the time to participate in our research. Your feedback will provide valuable insights into trends, opportunities, and challenges in this rapidly evolving sector.

1. How familiar are you with innovations in "transitional care" or "clinical pathways" in healthcare?

- Very familiar
- Somewhat familiar
- Not familiar at all

2. What is the primary focus of your investment portfolio?

- Digital health technologies
- Medical devices and wearables
- Telemedicine/telehealth platforms
- Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning for healthcare
- Healthcare IT and interoperability solutions
- Sector-agnostic
- Other (please specify): _____

3. Have you made investments in startups focused on innovative solutions in transitional care or clinical pathways **in the past 24 months?**

- Yes, multiple investments
- Yes, but only one or two investments
- No, but we are actively exploring opportunities
- No, but we are interested in the future

4. What types of innovation in transitional care or clinical pathways **interest you most** as a potential investment? (Select the top 3)

- AI and machine learning for predictive analytics and decision support
- Remote patient monitoring (RPM) technologies
- Digital health platforms for care coordination and patient navigation
- Personalised care solutions (e.g., genomics, precision medicine)
- Behavioural health innovations (e.g., teletherapy, digital mental health tools)
- Post-discharge management and readmission reduction technologies
- Home healthcare solutions (e.g., smart home devices, telehealth integration)
- Chronic disease management platforms (e.g., diabetes, cardiovascular care)
- Integrated care models (combining inpatient, outpatient, and home care)
- Other (please specify): _____

5. What are the key factors that would make you **more likely to invest** in an innovative startup in the transitional care or clinical pathways space? (Select the top 3)

- Evidence of strong clinical outcomes and patient impact
- Clear demonstration of cost savings or improved efficiency

- Scalable and adaptable technology or platform
- Partnerships with healthcare providers, payers, or other stakeholders
- Proven product-market fit and strong demand in the target market
- Strong intellectual property (IP) or proprietary technology
- Experienced and innovative founding team with healthcare and tech expertise
- Successful track record or validated pilots
- Alignment with regulatory requirements (e.g., GDPR, HIPAA, EMA/FDA approval)
- Other (please specify): _____

6. How do **you evaluate the "innovative potential"** of a startup in the transitional care or clinical pathway space?

- We prioritise technologies that have the potential to disrupt traditional care models and offer significant new approaches to patient management
- We look for innovations that improve existing care processes and optimise operational efficiencies
- We prefer innovations that leverage existing technologies in new ways (e.g., AI, telehealth) but do not require major systemic changes
- Innovation is less important than scalability and proven effectiveness in improving patient outcomes
- Other (please specify): _____

7. How important is the ability to **demonstrate innovation through clinical validation** or real-world evidence in your investment decision-making process?

- Extremely important – we need to see robust data to back up innovative claims
- Somewhat important – we prefer a balance of innovation and proven real-world success
- Not very important – we focus more on market potential and team experience
- Not important at all – we're more interested in the vision and scalability

8. What are the biggest **red flags or risks** you look for when **evaluating an investment** in a transitional care startup or solution? (Select all that apply)

- Lack of clinical validation or insufficient real-world data to support the effectiveness of the solution
- Unclear regulatory pathway or a high risk of delays in obtaining necessary approvals (e.g., EMA, FDA)
- Unproven business model or unclear strategy for commercialisation and scaling
- Weak intellectual property (IP) or absence of proprietary technology
- Inexperienced management team or lack of domain or sales expertise in healthcare and technology
- Limited customer or provider engagement or insufficient evidence of product-market fit

- High reliance on a single partner or customer without diversification
- Poor integration potential with existing healthcare systems or technologies
- Uncertainty around reimbursement and payer acceptance for new technologies or care models
- Financial instability or unsustainable burn rate
- Other (please specify): _____

9. How much do you believe the **lack of understanding and acceptance** of new technologies among healthcare **professionals, caregivers, or patients** impacts the growth and adoption of innovations in transitional care? (Scale: 1 = No impact at all, 5 = Significant impact)

- 1 - No impact at all
- 2 - Minimal impact
- 3 - Moderate impact
- 4 - Strong impact
- 5 - Significant impact

10. To what extent do you believe that **delays in regulatory processes** affect the development of new technologies or solutions for clinical pathways or transitional care? (Scale: 1 = No impact at all, 5 = Significant impact)

- 1 - No impact at all
- 2 - Minimal impact
- 3 - Moderate impact
- 4 - Strong impact
- 5 - Significant impact

11. What do you see as the **main barriers to scaling** innovative solutions in transitional care or clinical pathways?

- Regulatory hurdles and complex compliance requirements
- High costs associated with clinical trials and product development
- Limited payer coverage or reimbursement options
- Lack of standardisation in care pathways and integration into health systems
- Resistance from healthcare providers to adopt new technologies
- Difficulty in obtaining sufficient clinical evidence to support scaling
- Other (please specify): _____

12. Which of the following **drivers** do you believe can **most enable the successful adoption and scaling** of innovations in transitional care? (Select up to 3)

- Data privacy and security best practices
- Increased technical skills among informal caregivers (e.g., family members) to use new tools

- Advanced multi-data analysis tools and platforms that improve decision-making
- Adequate resources or funding for implementing new technologies
- Clear alignment between professional healthcare advice and family decision-making
- Strong communication and collaboration between family members and healthcare professionals regarding care decisions
- Other (please specify): _____

13. What **technological or market trends** do you think will **drive innovation** in transitional care or clinical pathways over the next 3-5 years? (Select all that apply)

- Expansion of AI and machine learning in clinical decision support and patient monitoring
- Growth of telemedicine and virtual care models (e.g., telehealth, remote monitoring)
- Advances in personalised medicine and genomics for targeted treatment pathways
- A shift toward value-based care and risk-sharing arrangements
- Integration of wearables and digital health tools for real-time data collection and intervention
- Increasing focus on mental health and behavioural health integration
- Growth of home healthcare and patient-centred care models
- Changes in government policy or regulatory frameworks that enable innovation
- Other (please specify): _____

13. If you have invested in or evaluated startups in this space, can you share any lessons learned or best practices that have influenced your investment decisions? [Open-ended response]

14. Would you be open to sharing your views more deeply in an interview?

- Yes, you may contact me
- No thanks

Survey template for TG#3 Living Labs

This survey seeks to understand the drivers and barriers that have been observed as you and your Living Lab assist innovators in developing their solutions and will help identify key systemic challenges and enablers that can facilitate or hinder the scaling of innovative solutions in transitional care (e.g., from hospital to home, rehabilitation settings, or long-term care).

1. Which Living Lab do you represent?

[Living Lab name]

2. What is the primary role of your Living Lab in supporting innovation in the transitional care sector? (Select all that apply)

- Testing and validating new technologies or care models in real-world settings
- Providing feedback and guidance to innovators on product development
- Facilitating collaborations between innovators, healthcare providers, and other stakeholders
- Providing funding or resources to help scale innovations
- Supporting data collection and analysis for pilot studies and trials
- Advocacy and policy influence to support innovation in transitional care
- Other (please specify): _____

3. From your experience, what are the key drivers that have enabled the successful development and scaling of innovations in transitional care within your Living Lab? (Select up to 3)

- Strong partnerships between innovators, healthcare providers, and patients
- Access to real-world test environments for validating solutions in actual care settings (e.g., hospitals, rehab centres, home care)
- Clear demand for solutions that address specific challenges in care transitions (e.g., reducing readmissions, improving patient outcomes)
- Patient and caregiver involvement in the co-design and testing of solutions
- Flexible regulatory frameworks that facilitate innovation without compromising safety
- Financial support or incentives to scale the solutions (e.g., grants, funding from government or private sector)
- Access to healthcare data and interoperability with existing systems (e.g., EHR, patient management systems)
- Evidence of effectiveness from pilot studies or trials that demonstrate real-world value
- Strong leadership and support from healthcare institutions or policy makers
- Clear reimbursement pathways for new care models or technologies (e.g., telehealth, remote monitoring)
- Other (please specify): _____

4. Which of the following factors have been most important in helping innovators in your Living Lab successfully engage with healthcare providers in the transitional care sector? (Select up to 3)

- Demonstrating a clear ROI or cost-saving potential for healthcare systems

- Tailoring solutions to the specific needs and workflows of healthcare providers
- Engaging key stakeholders (e.g., physicians, nurses, social workers) early in the development process
- Providing training and support for healthcare providers to use the new technology or care model
- Having a multidisciplinary team approach (e.g., including patients, healthcare professionals, and tech experts)
- Proving scalability and the potential for widespread adoption across healthcare settings
- Patient-centred design that addresses the needs of patients and families during care transitions
- Other (please specify): _____

5. From your experience, what are the biggest barriers that innovators in your Living Lab face in developing solutions for transitional care? (Select up to 3)

- Resistance to change from healthcare providers or institutions, who may be reluctant to adopt new models or technologies
- Regulatory barriers, such as slow approval processes or unclear guidelines for new technologies (e.g., telehealth, AI-based tools)
- Difficulty in demonstrating effectiveness or achieving measurable outcomes in care transitions (e.g., readmissions, patient satisfaction)
- Fragmented healthcare systems, which make it challenging to integrate solutions across different care settings (e.g., hospital, rehab, home care)
- Lack of financial support or difficulty securing funding to scale solutions
- Limited reimbursement or unclear reimbursement structures for new care models or technologies
- Challenges in data interoperability across different healthcare systems and providers
- Healthcare workforce readiness, including the lack of training or skills to use new technologies
- Patient engagement issues, where patients or caregivers may be unwilling or unable to adopt new technologies or care models
- Limited evidence to convince stakeholders (e.g., payers, providers) of the solution's value
- Other (please specify): _____

6. What are the biggest barriers to the scaling of innovations in transitional care that your Living Lab has observed? (Select up to 3)

- Lack of access to funding or investment for scaling

- Fragmentation of the healthcare system that prevents seamless integration across different settings
- Regulatory and policy hurdles, such as slow or uncertain regulatory approval processes
- Inconsistent or unclear reimbursement policies that do not support the adoption of new technologies or models
- Limited market access or challenges in reaching broader healthcare networks beyond the Living Lab or pilot sites
- Technological challenges, such as difficulties in ensuring data interoperability or system integration
- Healthcare provider readiness to adopt and implement new technologies or processes at scale
- Patient adoption barriers, such as lack of digital literacy or resistance to new care models
- Other (please specify): _____

7. How would you rate the effectiveness of your Living Lab in supporting innovators to address barriers to innovation in transitional care?

- Very effective – We have successfully helped innovators overcome most of the barriers to innovation
- Moderately effective – We have helped innovators address some barriers, but challenges remain
- Neutral – The Living Lab has had little impact on overcoming barriers to innovation
- Not effective – We have been unable to address most of the barriers faced by innovator
- Other (please specify): _____

8. In your experience, what types of support or resources have been most effective in helping innovators in the transitional care sector overcome these barriers? (Select up to 3)

- Access to real-world testing environments (e.g., hospitals, home care settings, rehab centres)
- Partnerships with healthcare providers or institutions to pilot new solutions
- Funding or grants to support the development and scaling of solutions
- Regulatory guidance or support in navigating approval processes
- Collaboration with payers or insurers to establish reimbursement models for new solutions
- Training programmes for healthcare providers to adopt new technologies or care models

- Patient feedback and co-design processes to ensure solutions meet patient needs
- Data access and support for ensuring interoperability with existing healthcare systems (e.g., EHR, telehealth platforms)
- Other (please specify): _____

9. What do you see as the most important future opportunities for innovation in transitional care that your Living Lab could help foster?

- Expanding the use of telehealth and remote monitoring for post-discharge care
- Developing AI-powered decision support tools to assist with discharge planning and risk prediction
- Improved patient education tools that empower patients and caregivers to manage transitions effectively
- Data-driven solutions for improving coordination between care providers across settings
- Integrated care models that bridge hospital, rehabilitation, and home care services seamlessly
- Innovative reimbursement models that support new care pathways and technologies
- Other (please specify): _____

10. What recommendations would you make to improve the environment for innovation in transitional care, based on your experience in the Living Lab?

[Open-ended response]

11. Would you be open to sharing your views more deeply in an interview?

- Yes, you may contact me
- No thanks

Survey template for TG#4.1 End-users (care units, hospitals, practitioners)

As a healthcare practitioner working in a clinical setting (e.g., hospital, rehab centre, care home), your insights are invaluable in understanding how innovative solutions are being applied to transitional care.

This survey aims to gather your views on drivers and barriers to innovation in transitional care, based on your clinical experience with patient transitions between different care settings (e.g., hospital discharge to home, rehab to long-term care, etc.).

The information you provide will help identify key areas for improvement and inform the development of future innovations in transitional care.

1. Which of the following best describes your role in a clinical or care facility setting?
 - Physician/Doctor
 - Nurse/Registered Nurse (RN)
 - Care Coordinator/Discharge Planner
 - Physical Therapist/Occupational Therapist
 - Social Worker
 - Nurse Practitioner/Advanced Practice Nurse
 - Administrator
 - Patient Assistant
 - First Responder (Ambulance, Paramedic)
 - Other (please specify): _____
2. In your clinical setting, are you currently involved in the transition of care process for patients (e.g., discharge planning, transfer between hospital and rehab, home care coordination)?
 - Yes, I am directly involved in the care transition process
 - No, but I collaborate with those involved in care transitions
 - No, I am not involved in care transitions
3. Have you encountered or worked with any innovative tools or technologies designed to improve transitional care in your setting? (Select all that apply)
 - Digital health tools or apps for care coordination (e.g., medication management, discharge instructions)
 - Remote patient monitoring (e.g., wearables or devices for monitoring health metrics after discharge)
 - Telehealth or virtual care solutions for follow-up care
 - Electronic health records (EHR) systems used for better care coordination
 - Artificial intelligence (AI) or decision support systems for discharge planning
 - Home healthcare services (e.g., in-home nursing, telehealth follow-up)
 - Other (please specify): _____
4. In your experience, which of the following areas are most in need of innovative tools, processes, or technologies? (Select all that apply)
 - Care coordination: managing transitions between healthcare settings (e.g., from hospital to home, rehab to long-term care)

- Medication management: ensuring patients take the correct medications after discharge and prevent medication errors
- Discharge instructions and follow-up: improving the clarity and accessibility of discharge instructions and ensure appropriate follow-up care
- Remote patient monitoring: monitoring patients' health metrics after discharge (e.g., wearables, home-based devices)
- Telehealth/Virtual care: providing follow-up care or consultations remotely, especially for patients in rural or underserved areas
- Data sharing and interoperability: ensuring seamless information exchange across healthcare settings (e.g., between hospitals, home care, rehab centres)
- Patient engagement: involving patients and families more effectively in the care process and ensuring they are equipped to manage transitions
- AI and decision support systems: assisting with discharge planning, risk prediction, or clinical decision-making during transitions
- Post-discharge home healthcare services: providing in-home care or remote follow-up (e.g., home nursing, telehealth follow-ups)
- Care team communication: improving communication among multidisciplinary teams involved in patient care transitions
- Social care integration: connecting healthcare and social services (e.g., home assistance, community resources)
- Other (please specify): _____

5. From your experience, what are the key drivers that make innovations in transitional care more likely to succeed in your clinical setting? (Select up to 3)

- Clear evidence of positive patient outcomes or improved care quality
- Integration of innovations with existing workflows (e.g., EHR systems, care coordination processes)
- Strong leadership support from hospital administration or care facility management
- Patient engagement and willingness to use new technologies or participate in new care models
- Availability of training and support for staff to effectively use the new tools or technologies
- Financial support or adequate reimbursement models that make innovation sustainable
- Collaboration between interdisciplinary teams (e.g., doctors, nurses, social workers, IT specialists)
- Regulatory alignment (e.g., compliance with privacy laws, insurance reimbursement policies)

- Patient and caregiver feedback showing that the innovation is helping them manage the transition better
- Other (please specify): _____

6. In your experience, what role do technological innovations play in improving transitional care in your care setting? (Select up to 3)

- They help coordinate care across different settings (e.g., hospital, rehab, home care)
- They enable remote patient monitoring, allowing for better management of patient's post-discharge
- They improve communication between healthcare teams across care settings (e.g., hospital to home, rehab centre to hospital)
- They allow for more timely follow-up care, reducing re-admissions and complications
- They enable personalised care based on data (e.g., risk prediction, chronic disease management)
- They increase patient education and engagement through apps or digital resources
- They allow for better data integration (e.g., patient data sharing between care settings)
- I have not seen any technological innovations implemented
- Other (please specify): _____

7. From your experience, what are the biggest barriers to the adoption of innovations in transitional care in your clinical setting? (Select up to 3)

- Resistance to change from healthcare staff (e.g., reluctance to adopt new technologies or workflows)
- Budgetary limitations (from institutional administration)
- Difficulty integrating new technologies into existing systems (e.g., EHR, care protocols)
- Insufficient training for staff to effectively use new tools or technologies
- Lack of reimbursement or unclear reimbursement policies for new care models or technologies
- High costs of implementing or scaling new technologies (e.g., devices, software, infrastructure)
- Patient reluctance to adopt new technologies or engage with digital tools
- Privacy and security concerns about patient data sharing or digital health tools
- Lack of evidence-based validation showing the effectiveness of innovation
- Inadequate collaboration between different healthcare providers or departments

- Regulatory barriers (e.g., slow approval processes, compliance with healthcare laws)
- Other (please specify): _____

8. What do you think is the biggest barrier to successfully scaling innovations in transitional care within your care setting?

- Resistance from staff to change established practices
- Financial barriers, such as costs of implementation or lack of reimbursement
- Lack of data interoperability between new technologies and existing systems (e.g., EHR)
- Limited training for healthcare providers to integrate new solutions into their workflows
- Patient engagement issues, where patients may not want to use new technologies or follow new models of care
- Other (please specify): _____

9. Based on your experience, how have innovations in transitional care impacted the quality of patient care in your setting?

- Improved quality of care (e.g., reduced re-admissions, fewer complications, better patient satisfaction)
- Moderately improved quality of care, but there are still challenges
- No noticeable improvement in quality of care
- Worsened quality of care (e.g., more confusion, increased burden on staff or patients)
- I have not observed any direct impact on quality of care
- We have not implemented any innovative solutions

10. What impact have innovations in transitional care had on staff workload in your clinical setting?

- Significantly reduced workload (e.g., streamlined processes, less manual work)
- Moderately reduced workload, but some challenges remain
- No change in workload – the innovations did not affect my daily tasks
- Increased workload (e.g., more time spent on training, troubleshooting, or coordinating care)
- We have not implemented any innovative solutions
- Other (please specify): _____

11. What are the most critical needs for improving transitional care in your clinical setting? (Select up to 3)

- Better integration of new technologies into daily workflows
- More training and support for staff to effectively use new tools
- Clearer reimbursement and funding models to support innovation
- Greater patient engagement tools or resources to help manage transitions
- Stronger communication and coordination between different care teams and settings
- More evidence-based solutions demonstrating improvements in outcomes or cost-efficiency
- Other (please specify): _____

12. Do you think that technological innovations will play a key role in improving transitional care in the future?

- Yes, technological innovations will be essential for improving care transitions
- Yes, but technology alone will not be enough – changes in care models and processes are also needed
- No, innovations may not significantly improve transitional care
- I am unsure

13. Do you have any recommendations or suggestions for improving the implementation and adoption of innovative solutions in transitional care?

[Open-ended response]

14. Would you be open to sharing your views more deeply in an interview?

- Yes, you may contact me
- No thanks

Survey template for TG#4.2 End-users (individuals)

This survey seeks to understand the experiences of individuals and caregivers during transitional care situations. Transitional care refers to the period when a patient moves between different care settings, such as from a hospital to home, or from one healthcare provider to another. These transitions can be challenging and have a significant impact on health outcomes. Your responses will help us identify key issues and areas for improvement to make these transitions smoother and more supportive for patients and their families.

1. Have you or a loved one experienced a care transition in the past 12 months? (e.g., moving from hospital to home, changing healthcare providers, or transitioning to long-term care?)
 - Yes, I or my loved one experienced a care transition
 - No, we have not experienced a care transition in the past year
2. If yes, what type of transition did you experience? (Select all that apply)
 - Hospital to home
 - Skilled nursing facility or rehab to home
 - Hospital to a rehabilitation or long-term care facility
 - Transition between different healthcare providers (e.g., from a hospital to a primary care doctor)
 - Change in treatment plan (e.g., new medications, surgery, or therapy)
 - Other (please specify): _____
3. How would you describe the level of communication you received from healthcare providers during the transition?
 - Excellent – I received clear and timely communication about what to expect
 - Good – Communication was mostly clear, but there were some gaps
 - Fair – Communication was unclear or incomplete
 - Poor – I received very little communication, and was unsure about what to do
4. What challenges did you face during the care transition? (Select up to 3)
 - Difficulty understanding discharge instructions or care plans
 - Lack of follow-up care or appointments after discharge
 - Difficulty reaching healthcare providers for questions or concerns
 - Confusion about medications or treatment regimen
 - Problems with coordinating care between different healthcare providers
 - Emotional stress or anxiety about managing the care transition
 - Difficulty accessing necessary medical equipment or support at home
 - Financial challenges or difficulty accessing needed resources (e.g., transportation, medications)
 - Other (please specify): _____
5. Were there any specific support services or resources provided to assist with the transition?
 - Yes, I received assistance from healthcare providers (e.g., a care coordinator, home health visits, discharge planning)
 - Yes, I received help from community organisations or other support systems

- No, I did not receive any additional support
 - I'm not sure
6. Did you feel prepared for the transition?
- Yes, I felt well-prepared and understood what was expected of me
 - Somewhat – I was somewhat prepared but had questions or concerns
 - No, I felt unprepared and confused about the next steps
 - I didn't have enough information to make an informed decision
7. How did the transition affect your or your loved one's health and well-being?
- Very positively – The transition was smooth, and I felt well-supported
 - Positively – There were some challenges, but we managed well overall
 - Neutrally – The transition didn't have a significant impact on health or well-being
 - Negatively – The transition caused stress or worsened health outcomes
 - Very negatively – The transition was difficult and negatively affected health outcomes
8. Did you or your loved one experience any complications (e.g., readmission, health decline, difficulty following instructions) following the transition?
- Yes, there were complications or readmissions after the transition
 - No, there were no complications
 - I'm not sure
9. If complications occurred, do you feel they could have been prevented with better support during the transition?
- Yes, better communication or support could have prevented complications
 - Maybe – More support might have helped, but it's hard to say
 - No, the complications were not preventable
 - I'm not sure
10. Did you receive any of the following support services during the transition? (Select all that apply)
- Care coordinator or discharge planner
 - Home health visits or follow-up calls from healthcare providers
 - Community-based services or home care assistance
 - Education or printed materials on self-care, medication management, or follow-up appointments
 - Access to a family or caregiver support group
 - A phone or online consultation with a healthcare provider after discharge

- Transportation assistance
- Other (please specify): _____

11. Which support services would have helped you most during the care transition? (Select up to 3)

- A care coordinator or case manager to help with planning and coordination
- Follow-up phone calls or visits from a healthcare provider to check on progress
- Access to online resources or educational materials on managing health at home
- Family or caregiver support programmes to assist with caregiving tasks
- Support with medication management or understanding prescriptions
- Help with arranging home care or community-based services (e.g., physical therapy, home healthcare)
- Other (please specify): _____

12. Were there any challenges you encountered when trying to access these services or supports?

- Yes, there were barriers (e.g., availability, cost, lack of information)
- No, the services were accessible and easy to use
- I did not try to access any services or supports

13. Overall, how satisfied were you with the care transition process?

- Very satisfied – Everything went smoothly, and I felt supported throughout
- Satisfied – Most things went well, but there were some challenges
- Neutral – I had some positive experiences, but there were also significant issues
- Unsatisfied – The process was difficult and poorly coordinated
- Very unsatisfied – The transition was overwhelming and poorly managed

14. What improvements would have made your care transition experience better?

[Open-ended response]

15. How can healthcare providers better support patients and families during care transitions? (Select up to 3)

- Provide clearer communication about care plans, medications, and follow-up appointments
- Offer more personalised care coordination (e.g., a dedicated care manager or support team)
- Ensure better access to home health services or post-discharge care
- Provide more educational resources or training on how to manage care at home
- Improve access to community resources or financial assistance for caregiving

- Offer more frequent follow-up care (e.g., phone calls or visits) to check on progress
- Other (please specify): _____

16. Would you be willing to participate in a follow-up interview to share more about your experiences with care transitions?

- Yes, I would be happy to participate
- No, thank you

Survey template for TG#5 Policymakers / Regulatory Bodies

Thank you for participating in this survey. As a policymaker involved in shaping the healthcare landscape, your insights are essential in understanding the drivers and barriers to innovations in transitional care. This survey aims to gather your perspective on how policies, regulations and mechanisms impact the adoption and scaling of innovative solutions in transitional care, particularly as patients move between different care settings (e.g., hospital to home, rehabilitation centres, long-term care).

1. Which of the following best describes your role in healthcare policy and regulation?

- Healthcare policymaker (e.g., government official, public health expert)
- Regulatory body (e.g., healthcare regulatory agency, insurance authority)
- Health system administrator or leader
- Other (please specify): _____

2. How familiar are you with the current state of innovation in transitional care (e.g., digital tools, remote monitoring, AI decision support)?

- Very familiar – I have extensive knowledge of innovations in transitional care
- Somewhat familiar – I am aware of the general trends but not deeply involved
- Not familiar – I have limited knowledge of innovations in transitional care
- I do not have any knowledge of this area

3. From your perspective, what are the key drivers that can enable the successful adoption and scaling of innovations in transitional care? (Select up to 3)

- Government incentives or funding programmes to support innovation in healthcare
- Clear reimbursement policies for innovative technologies or care models (e.g., tele-health, remote monitoring)
- Establishment of national standards for transitional care pathways

- Supportive regulation that fosters innovation while ensuring patient safety
- Collaboration between healthcare providers, payers, and tech companies to streamline innovation
- Public awareness and education programmes to increase patient and caregiver engagement
- Data interoperability to allow seamless exchange of information across care settings
- Alignment with value-based care models (focusing on patient outcomes rather than volume of services)
- Workforce development to equip healthcare providers with the skills to use innovative technologies
- Other (please specify): _____

4. What role do you believe government funding or financial incentives should play in encouraging innovation in transitional care?

- Very important – Government funding and financial incentives are crucial for accelerating innovation
- Moderately important – Financial incentives are useful but should be balanced with other factors (e.g., market demand, evidence of effectiveness)
- Not very important – Funding and incentives are secondary to other considerations like regulation or healthcare infrastructure
- Not important – Government should not play a role in funding or incentivising innovation in healthcare
- Other (please specify): _____

5. From a policy and regulatory perspective, what are the biggest barriers to the adoption and scaling of innovations in transitional care? (Select up to 3)

- Unclear reimbursement models or lack of financial incentives for new care models and technologies
- Slow or cumbersome regulatory approval processes for innovative technologies and care models
- Fragmentation of healthcare systems (e.g., different standards of care across hospitals, clinics, home care, etc.)
- Lack of unified standards (e.g., across the EU, or nationwide) for transitional care pathways that integrate innovations effectively
- Privacy and data security concerns (e.g., protecting patient data across different care settings)
- Resistance to change from healthcare providers, or institutions that are slow to adopt new models

- Limited evidence or data showing the effectiveness of innovations in improving patient outcomes
- Inadequate training for healthcare workforce to adopt innovative technologies or workflows
- Inequitable access to innovative technologies for certain patient populations or geographic areas
- Other (please specify): _____

6. What do you think is the biggest regulatory challenge for scaling innovations in transitional care across healthcare systems?

- Data interoperability issues across healthcare settings (e.g., hospital, rehab, home care)
- Old or 'legacy' reimbursement structures that do not cover innovative technologies or care models (e.g., telehealth, remote monitoring)
- Lack of clarity in regulatory frameworks regarding emerging technologies (e.g., AI, digital health tools)
- Resistance from traditional healthcare institutions (e.g., hospitals, insurance companies) to adopt innovative technologies
- Slow approval processes for innovative technologies or treatments
- Limited integration of value-based care models that incentivise innovation and patient outcomes over volume
- Other (please specify): _____

7. What types of policy interventions do you believe would most effectively support the adoption of innovations in transitional care? (Select up to 3)

- Creating funding programmes for pilot projects or research into new transitional care models
- Establishing clear reimbursement policies for innovative technologies and care models that improve patient transitions
- Developing national or regional standards for transitional care to guide innovation and ensure quality across settings
- Promoting public-private partnerships between healthcare providers, tech companies, and government to fund and implement novel solutions
- Incentivising the use of data-sharing technologies that improve care coordination (e.g., electronic health records, telemedicine)
- Expanding workforce development programmes to equip healthcare professionals with the skills needed to use innovative technologies effectively
- Other (please specify): _____

8. How do you see value-based care policies (e.g., pay-for-performance, outcome-based reimbursement) influencing the adoption of innovations in transitional care?

- Very positively – Value-based care policies will encourage the adoption of innovations that improve patient outcomes
- Somewhat positively – While value-based care models can help, other factors (e.g., funding, training) are also important
- Neutral – Value-based care is not significantly affecting the adoption of innovations in transitional care
- Not positively – Value-based care models may not align well with the current innovation landscape in transitional care
- I am unsure

9. What are the top priorities for healthcare policy and regulation to support the future of transitional care innovations? (Select up to 3)

- Enhancing interoperability between healthcare systems to facilitate seamless transitions
- Expanding telehealth services and ensuring reimbursement models are updated to cover them
- Establishing national standards for care transitions that include innovative technologies
- Providing funding and incentives to support research, development, and scaling of innovative transitional care solutions
- Developing a more flexible regulatory framework to speed up the approval of innovative technologies and models
- Ensuring equitable access to new innovations for underserved or rural populations
- Promoting patient and caregiver education to support the use of new care models and technologies
- Other (please specify): _____

10. Do you think that government policies will play a critical role in scaling innovations in transitional care over the next 3-5 years?

- Yes, government policies will be essential for scaling innovations and improving care transitions
- Yes, but policies need to be more aligned with innovation needs (e.g., better reimbursement structures)
- No, innovations will primarily be driven by the private sector or healthcare providers, not by government policy
- I am unsure

11. What recommendations would you offer to improve policy frameworks and regulatory support for innovation in transitional care?

[Open-ended response]

12. Would you be open to sharing your views more deeply in an interview?

- Yes, you may contact me
- No thanks

Survey template for TG#6 EU Initiatives

This survey looks at accelerators/investor/EU initiatives (e.g., EIT Health projects) attitudes and funding preferences regarding innovative health tech solutions for transitional care and clinical pathways. Thank you for taking the time to participate in our research. Your feedback will provide valuable insights into trends, opportunities, and challenges in this rapidly evolving sector.

1. How familiar are you with innovations in "transitional care" or "clinical pathways" in healthcare?

- Very familiar
- Somewhat familiar
- Not familiar at all

2. What is the primary focus of your investment portfolio?

- Digital health technologies
- Medical devices and wearables
- Telemedicine/telehealth platforms
- Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning for healthcare
- Healthcare IT and interoperability solutions
- Sector-agnostic
- Other (please specify): _____

3. Have you made investments in startups focused on innovative solutions in transitional care or clinical pathways in the past 24 months?

- Yes, multiple investments
- Yes, but only one or two investments
- No, but we are actively exploring opportunities
- No, but we are interested in the future

4. What types of innovation in transitional care or clinical pathways interest you most as a potential investment? (Select the top 3)

- AI and machine learning for predictive analytics and decision support
- Remote patient monitoring (RPM) technologies
- Digital health platforms for care coordination and patient navigation
- Personalised care solutions (e.g., genomics, precision medicine)
- Behavioural health innovations (e.g., teletherapy, digital mental health tools)
- Post-discharge management and readmission reduction technologies
- Home healthcare solutions (e.g., smart home devices, telehealth integration)
- Chronic disease management platforms (e.g., diabetes, cardiovascular care)
- Integrated care models (combining inpatient, outpatient, and home care)
- Other (please specify): _____

5. What are the key factors that would make you more likely to invest in an innovative startup in the transitional care or clinical pathways space? (Select the top 3)

- Evidence of strong clinical outcomes and patient impact
- Clear demonstration of cost savings or improved efficiency
- Scalable and adaptable technology or platform
- Partnerships with healthcare providers, payers, or other stakeholders
- Proven product-market fit and strong demand in the target market
- Strong intellectual property (IP) or proprietary technology
- Experienced and innovative founding team with healthcare and tech expertise
- Successful track record or validated pilots
- Alignment with regulatory requirements (e.g., GDPR, HIPAA, EMA/FDA approval)
- Other (please specify): _____

6. How do you evaluate the "innovative potential" of a startup in the transitional care or clinical pathway space?

- We prioritise technologies that have the potential to disrupt traditional care models and offer significant new approaches to patient management
- We look for innovations that improve existing care processes and optimise operational efficiencies
- We prefer innovations that leverage existing technologies in new ways (e.g., AI, telehealth) but do not require major systemic changes
- Innovation is less important than scalability and proven effectiveness in improving patient outcomes
- Other (please specify): _____

7. How important is the ability to demonstrate innovation through clinical validation or real-world evidence in your investment decision-making process?

- Extremely important – we need to see robust data to back up innovative claims
- Somewhat important – we prefer a balance of innovation and proven real-world success
- Not very important – we focus more on market potential and team experience
- Not important at all – we’re more interested in the vision and scalability

8. What are the biggest red flags or risks you look for when evaluating an investment in a transitional care startup or solution? (Select all that apply)

- Lack of clinical validation or insufficient real-world data to support the effectiveness of the solution
- Unclear regulatory pathway or a high risk of delays in obtaining necessary approvals (e.g., EMA, FDA)
- Unproven business model or unclear strategy for commercialisation and scaling
- Weak intellectual property (IP) or absence of proprietary technology
- Inexperienced management team or lack of domain or sales expertise in healthcare and technology
- Limited customer or provider engagement or insufficient evidence of product-market fit
- High reliance on a single partner or customer without diversification
- Poor integration potential with existing healthcare systems or technologies
- Uncertainty around reimbursement and payer acceptance for new technologies or care models
- Financial instability or unsustainable burn rate
- Other (please specify): _____

9. How much do you believe the lack of understanding and acceptance of new technologies among healthcare professionals, caregivers, or patients impacts the growth and adoption of innovations in transitional care?

(Scale: 1 = No impact at all, 5 = Significant impact)

- 1 - No impact at all
- 2 - Minimal impact
- 3 - Moderate impact
- 4 - Strong impact
- 5 - Significant impact

10. To what extent do you believe that delays in regulatory processes affect the development of new technologies or solutions for clinical pathways or transitional care?

(Scale: 1 = No impact at all, 5 = Significant impact)

- 1 - No impact at all
- 2 - Minimal impact
- 3 - Moderate impact
- 4 - Strong impact
- 5 - Significant impact

11. What do you see as the main barriers to scaling innovative solutions in transitional care or clinical pathways?

- Regulatory hurdles and complex compliance requirements
- High costs associated with clinical trials and product development
- Limited payer coverage or reimbursement options
- Lack of standardisation in care pathways and integration into health systems
- Resistance from healthcare providers to adopt new technologies
- Difficulty in obtaining sufficient clinical evidence to support scaling
- Other (please specify): _____

12. Which of the following drivers do you believe can most enable the successful adoption and scaling of innovations in transitional care? (Select up to 3)

- Data privacy and security best practices
- Increased technical skills among informal caregivers (e.g., family members) to use new tools
- Advanced multi-data analysis tools and platforms that improve decision-making
- Adequate resources or funding for implementing new technologies
- Clear alignment between professional healthcare advice and family decision-making
- Strong communication and collaboration between family members and healthcare professionals regarding care decisions
- Other (please specify): _____

13. What technological or market trends do you think will drive innovation in transitional care or clinical pathways over the next 3-5 years? (Select all that apply)

- Expansion of AI and machine learning in clinical decision support and patient monitoring
- Growth of telemedicine and virtual care models (e.g., telehealth, remote monitoring)
- Advances in personalised medicine and genomics for targeted treatment pathways
- A shift toward value-based care and risk-sharing arrangements

- Integration of wearables and digital health tools for real-time data collection and intervention
- Increasing focus on mental health and behavioural health integration
- Growth of home healthcare and patient-centred care models
- Changes in government policy or regulatory frameworks that enable innovation
- Other (please specify): _____

14. If you have invested in or evaluated startups in this space, can you share any lessons learned or best practices that have influenced your investment decisions? [Open-ended response]

15. Would you be open to sharing your views more deeply in an interview?

- Yes, you may contact me
- No thanks

Interview Guidelines

To ensure consistency, depth, and relevance in the data collection process, these guidelines provide a framework for conducting stakeholder interviews. All partners are encouraged to adhere to these instructions to maximise the value of the insights gathered.

1. Objectives of the Interviews

The primary goals of the interviews are to:

- Identify different key drivers and barriers to innovation in transitional care.
- Understand participant experiences, perspectives, and needs.
- Gather actionable insights to inform the design and implementation of Use Cases in Living Labs.

2. Approach

Interviews should be conducted to gather qualitative insights from participants engaged in transitional care and healthcare innovation.

- Profiles of Interviewees: Participants include innovators, investors, patient representatives, end-users (healthcare professionals, practitioners, individuals) policymakers and EU Initiatives.
- Minim of 5 interviews per target group, but remember that the focus is on quality and not quantity
- Target groups
 - TG#1: Innovators (researchers, SMEs, startups, corporates) – SPLORO

- TG#2: Accelerators / Investors - ANTHOLOGY VENTURES JSC
 - TG#3: Living Labs – ENoll
 - TG#4.1: End-users (care units, hospitals, practitioners) – AUTH
 - TG#4.2: End-users (individuals) – AUTH
 - TG#5: Policy makers / Regulatory bodies – Vilabs
 - TG#6: EU initiatives (e.g., EIT Health projects) – SPLORO
- Key Topics and Structure of Discussions: Interviews focused on exploring:
 - Perceived drivers and barriers to innovation.
 - Experiences with transitional care challenges.
 - Suggestions for improving the adoption of innovative solutions.

3. Interview Structure

Each interview should follow a semi-structured format, combining prepared questions with flexibility to explore emerging topics.

- Duration: 25 – 30 minutes.
- Mode: In-person, virtual, or phone interviews, based on participant availability.

3.1 Core Sections:

For TG#1 Innovators

- Introduction (5 minutes):
 - Introduce yourself, the project, and the purpose of the interview.
 - Assure confidentiality and explain how the data will be used.
 - Obtain consent for recording (if applicable).
 - Can you describe your role and involvement in transitional care?
- Drivers of Innovation (5 minutes):
 - What factors or conditions facilitate innovation in transitional care, in your own experience?
 - Are there any successful examples of innovative technologies you have observed or used?
- Barriers to Innovation (5 minutes):
 - What obstacles hinder the development and adoption of innovative technologies?
 - How do legal, regulatory, fiscal, technical, or operational challenges impact your work?

- Recommendations and Opportunities (5 minutes):
 - What could be done to address these barriers effectively?
 - How can collaboration among stakeholders improve outcomes?
- Closing (5 minutes):
 - Is there anything else you'd like to share?
 - Thank the interviewee for their time and contributions.

For TG#2 Accelerators/Investors

- Introduction (5 minutes):
 - Introduce yourself, the project, and the purpose of the interview.
 - Assure confidentiality and explain how the data will be used.
 - Obtain consent for recording (if applicable).
 - Can you describe your role as an investor and consultant?
- Drivers of Innovation (5 minutes):
 - What factors or conditions facilitate innovation (in transitional care), in your own experience?
 - Are there any successful examples of innovative technologies you have observed or used?
- Barriers to Innovation (5 minutes):
 - What obstacles hinder the development and adoption of innovative technologies?
 - How do regulatory, fiscal, technical, or operational challenges impact your work?
- Recommendations and Opportunities (5 minutes):
 - What could be done to address these barriers effectively?
 - How can collaboration among stakeholders improve outcomes?
- Closing (5 minutes):
 - Is there anything else you'd like to share?

For TG#3 Living Labs

- Introduction (5 minutes):
 - Introduce yourself, the project, and the purpose of the interview.
 - Assure confidentiality and explain how the data will be used.
 - Obtain consent for recording (if applicable).
 - Can you describe your role and involvement in transitional care?

- Drivers of Innovation (5 minutes):
 - What factors or conditions facilitate innovation in transitional care, in your own experience?
 - Are there any successful examples of innovative technologies you have observed or used?
- Barriers to Innovation (5 minutes):
 - What obstacles hinder the development and adoption of innovative technologies?
 - How do regulatory, fiscal, technical, or operational challenges impact your work?
- Recommendations and Opportunities (5 minutes):
 - What could be done to address these barriers effectively?
 - How can collaboration among stakeholders improve outcomes?
- Closing (5 minutes):
 - Is there anything else you'd like to share?

For TG#4.1 End-users (care units, hospitals, practitioners)

- Introduction (5 minutes):
 - Introduce yourself, the project, and the purpose of the interview.
 - Assure confidentiality and explain how the data will be used.
 - Obtain consent for recording (if applicable).
 - Can you describe your role and involvement in transitional care?
- Drivers of Innovation (5 minutes):
 - What factors or conditions facilitate innovation in transitional care, in your own experience?
 - Are there any successful examples of innovative technologies you have observed or used?
- Barriers to Innovation (5 minutes):
 - What obstacles hinder the development and adoption of innovative technologies?
 - How do regulatory, fiscal, technical, or operational challenges impact your work?
- Recommendations and Opportunities (5 minutes):
 - What could be done to address these barriers effectively?
 - How can collaboration among stakeholders improve outcomes?
- Closing (5 minutes):

- Is there anything else you'd like to share?

For TG#4.2 End-users (individuals)

- Introduction (5 minutes):
 - Introduce yourself, the project, and the purpose of the interview.
 - Assure confidentiality and explain how the data will be used.
 - Obtain consent for recording (if applicable).
 - In the past 12 months, have you been admitted to a hospital or other clinical setting (e.g., rehabilitation centre)? If so, can you share your experience with transitional care during that time?
- Drivers of Innovation (5 minutes):
 - Were any new technologies or tools used during your transition? If yes, how did they work for you?
 - Do you have any thoughts on other technologies that might have been helpful?
- Barriers to Innovation (5 minutes):
 - What challenges or difficulties did you encounter during your care transition?
 - What practical or organisational issues made it harder for you to get the care you needed?
- Recommendations and Opportunities (5 minutes):
 - What could be done to address these barriers effectively?
 - Are there any innovative tools or technologies you think could have made your transitional care experience easier or better?
- Closing (5 minutes):
 - Is there anything else you'd like to share?

For TG#5 Policymakers / Regulatory Bodies

- Introduction (5 minutes):
 - Introduce yourself, the project, and the purpose of the interview.
 - Assure confidentiality and explain how the data will be used.
 - Obtain consent for recording (if applicable).
 - Can you describe your role and involvement in transitional care?
- Drivers of Innovation (5 minutes):
 - What do you believe are the most significant policy drivers enabling innovation in transitional care within the EU?

- In your opinion, how do national and EU policies align to create a favourable environment for innovation in this field?
- How can policymakers further incentivise innovation and investment in healthcare technologies for transitional care?

- Barriers to Innovation (5 minutes):
 - What are the most significant regulatory or policy barriers that hinder innovation in transitional care?
 - How do legal, regulatory, fiscal, technical, or operational challenges impact your work?
 - Are there any legal frameworks or standards that currently restrict the adoption of new technologies in transitional care settings?
 - Do you foresee any potential barriers in aligning the regulatory requirements across different EU member states for innovative solutions in transitional care?

- Recommendations and Opportunities (5 minutes):
 - How do you think regulatory frameworks could be adapted to better support innovation while ensuring patient safety and quality of care?
 - What are the key policy considerations you take into account when evaluating new technological solutions for transitional care?
 - What key lessons have you learned from previous initiatives or pilot projects that could be applied to future transitional care innovations?

- Closing (5 minutes):
 - Is there anything else you'd like to share?

For TG#6 EU Initiatives

- Introduction (5 minutes):
 - Introduce yourself, the project, and the purpose of the interview.
 - Assure confidentiality and explain how the data will be used.
 - Obtain consent for recording (if applicable).
 - Can you describe your role and involvement in transitional care?

- Drivers of Innovation (5 minutes):
 - What do you believe are the main drivers enabling innovation in transitional care within the EU?
 - Are you aware of any EU initiative that work on creating a favourable environment for innovation in this field?

- What can your organisation offer to further incentivise innovation and investment in healthcare technologies for transitional care?
- Barriers to Innovation (5 minutes):
 - What are the most significant barriers that hinder innovation in transitional care in EU level?
 - How do legal, regulatory, fiscal, technical, or operational challenges impact your work?
 - Do you foresee any potential barriers in aligning the regulatory requirements across different EU member states for innovative solutions in transitional care?
- Recommendations and Opportunities (5 minutes):
 - How do you think regulatory frameworks could be adapted to better support innovation while ensuring patient safety and quality of care?
 - What key lessons have you learned from similar initiatives or pilot projects that could be applied to future transitional care innovations?
- Closing (5 minutes):
 - Is there anything else you'd like to share?

4. Data Collection and Documentation

4.1 Recording and Notes:

- Partners are encouraged to record interviews (with consent) for accuracy.
- Take detailed notes during the session to capture key points.

4.2 Data Format:

- Interviews detailed notes or summarise key points into a standardised template provided by the Evolve2Care task lead.

4.3 Submission Deadline:

- Submit completed templates to the task lead (Sploro) by January 10, 2025.

5. Ethical Considerations

- Ensure interviewees provide informed consent before participation.
- Maintain confidentiality by anonymising personal details in reports.
- Adhere to GDPR and other relevant data protection regulations.

6. Support and Contact

D1.1 - Roadmap on navigating the complexities of enabling innovative technologies in transitional care

- If you have any questions or require assistance with conducting interviews, please contact: Task Leader.